

**NON-PERFORMING ASSETS IN DISTRICT CENTRAL
CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU –
AN EMPIRICAL STUDY**

Thesis submitted to the
Madurai Kamaraj University for the award of the Degree of
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN COMMERCE

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This thesis is an original work of the candidate and to the best of my knowledge has not been submitted in part or in full, for any Diploma, Degree, Associateship, Fellowship or other similar title in this or any other university. No portion of the thesis is a reproduction from any source, published or unpublished without acknowledgement.

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DECLARATION

I declare that the thesis, **“NON-PERFORMING ASSETS IN DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU – AN EMPIRICAL STUDY”**, is the result of a study originally carried out by me under the guidance and supervision of **Dr. C. LAKSHMANAN**, Head, Research Centre in Commerce, Vivekananda College (Autonomous), Tiruvedakam West, Madurai. This work has not been submitted earlier, in full or in part, for any Diploma, Degree or any other award, in this or any other university.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS USED

A/c	-	Account
ACD	-	Agricultural Credit Department
APCOB	-	Andhra Pradesh State Co-operative Bank
ARCIL	-	Assets Reconstruction Company of India Limited
BIFR	-	Board for Industrial and Financial Reconstruction
BIS	-	Bank of International Settlement
CAC	-	Capital Account Convertibility
CAR	-	Capital Adequacy Ratio
CBSR	-	Committee on Banking Sector Reforms
CC	-	Cash Credit
CCB	-	Central Co-operative Bank
CPA	-	Critical Performance Area
CRR	-	Cash Reserve Ratio
CRWAR	-	Capital Risk Weighted Assets Ratio
DCCB	-	District Central Co-operative Bank
DEA	-	Data Envelopment Analysis
DRT	-	Debt Recovery Tribunal
GDP	-	Gross Domestic Product
HO	-	Head Office
IMF	-	International Monetary Fund

IRAC	-	Income Recognition Assets Classification
IVP	-	Indira Vikas Patra
KVP	-	Kisan Vikas Patra
KYC	-	Know Your Customer
NABARD	-	National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development
NPA	-	Non-Performing Asset
NPL	-	Non-Performing Loan
NSC	-	National Saving Certificate
OCC	-	Office of the Comptroller of Currency
OD	-	Overdraft
P & L A/c	-	Profit and Loss Account
PACB	-	Primary Agricultural Co-operative Bank
PACS	-	Primary Agricultural Co-operative Credit Societies
PLR	-	Prime Lending Rate
PSB	-	Public Sector Bank
RBI	-	Reserve Bank of India
RCS	-	Registrar of Co-operative Societies
RPCD	-	Rural Planning and Credit Department
RRB	-	Regional Rural Bank
SAO	-	Small Agricultural Outstanding
SBI	-	State Bank of India

SCB	-	State Co-operative Bank
SHG	-	Self Help Group
SLR	-	Statutory Liquidity Ratio
SPSS	-	Statistical Package for Social Science
SSI	-	Small Scale Industries
ST	-	Short Term
TNSCB	-	Tamil Nadu State Apex Co-operative Bank
UCB	-	Urban Co-operative Bank

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

In the 1990s India faced a serious balance of payments crisis. The Government of India approached the World Bank and the IMF for a hung loan to bail India out of the crisis. The World Bank and the IMF agreed to provide the required assistance subject to the condition that the government was to bring some changes in its economic policy. The Government of India agreed to the condition and initiated a number of policy changes to bring about a structured readjustment in the economy. One of these measures was Financial Sector Reforms.

There has been a progressive introduction of financial sector reforms and the financial sector as a whole is more sensitive now than before to the need to improve the strength and effective management to ensure financial stability. The government constituted two committees headed by M.Narasimham to go deep into the details of the imperative need for initiating financial sector reforms.

The financial system in India has built up a vast network of financial institutions and markets over the years. The banking sector accounts for about two-thirds of the assets of the organized financial sector. The first report of the Committee on Financial Systems released in 1991 made a few recommendations for building up a strong and efficient financial system. Accordingly, the first

phase of the current reform of the financial sector was initiated in 1992. The progress that has been made in a substantial, yet non-disruptive, manner has given the confidence to launch what has been described as the second generation reforms especially for the banking sector. The report of the Committee on Banking Sector Reforms (CBSR,1998) provided a framework for the second phase of reforms in the banking system.¹

The banking reforms focus on (i) Reduction of Pre-emption like high level Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) and Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR); (ii) A shift of banking sector supervision from intrusive microlevel intervention over credit decision toward prudential regulations and supervision for the creation of more competitive environment in financial sector; (iii) Interest rate and entry deregulation; and (iv) Adoption of prudential norms. The reform process aims at improving the productivity and efficiency in the financial sector in general and the banking sector in particular. The Indian banking sector reforms involve the twin stands of the stricter prudential norms and the deregulation of the operating environment. Weak banks, Strong banks and Potentially Weak Banks have been identified by the Verma Committee (1999) on the basis of seven financial performance parameters, namely, capital adequacy ratio, coverage ratio, return to assets, net interest margin, operating profits to average working funds, cost to income and per staff cost to interest income plus other income.

The extension of reforms, particularly prudential standards to co-operative banking institutions, an important component of the banking system, was a natural result of the financial weaknesses in co-operative banks. Co-operative banks operate at the village, district and state levels. The urgency and importance for the extension of reforms in co-operative banks was due to their reach and scale of operations. Accordingly, prudential standards covering capital adequacy, income recognition, asset classification and provisioning norms were made applicable to co-operative banks in a phased manner. However, co-operative reforms encompassing legal and administrative aspects have not taken place in India. This is on account of a multiplicity of controls. Anyhow the impact of the extension of prudential standards to co-operative banks has resulted in an increased intervention by the regulator and the Government.

The introduction of prudential norms has ushered in a new era in the reform process of banking industry as a whole. The identification of the NPAs as per the prudential norms specified by the RBI is a pre-requisite for the proper management of the NPAs. As per the guidelines of the RBI, the State Co-operative Banks and the Central Co-operative Banks started implementing the Prudential norms from the accounting year 1996-1997. One of the major reasons cited for the introduction of the norms has been the persistence of Non-performing Assets (NPAs) in banks. Loans or advances given by banks become Non-Performing when the interest and /or instalment of principal remains overdue for

more than 180 days. Advances which do not generate any income and which are doubtful affect the very vital function of banks viz. intermediation (mobilizing savings and providing finance for investment).

Loans and advances given by banks are classified as standard assets, sub-standard assets, doubtful assets and loss assets. Sub-standard assets, doubtful assets and loss assets together are called Non-Performing assets. Where assets are Non-performing a provision is required to be maintained. The total funds stuck in the Indian banking system in terms of bad loans, writeoffs and restructured assets have touched an alarming high of Rs. 2,36,000 crore, according to the Assets Reconstruction Company of India Limited (ARCIL) data:² As NPAs in the financial system are large in dimension, they require ongoing steps to unlock their values. Restructured assets (Rs. 92,000 crore) and NAPs of all scheduled commercial banks, financial institutions, non-banking financial companies and co-operative banks (1,11,000 crore) put together constitute a total NPAs of Rs. 2,03,000 crore besides NPA write-offs to the extent of Rs 33,000 crore. This has become a major problem threatening the viability of the entire banking system. The economy and the banking system are interdependent for their functioning and growth and any problem in one sector affects the other instantaneously.

The presence of huge non-performing assets in DCCBs in India and their continued unmitigated increase in absolute terms have had an adverse impact on the banking system, the fiscal exercise of the Government and the economy in general. The high level of non-performing assets reveals an inherent syndrome for inefficiency and poor credit management in the banks. The cancer - like phenomenon requires timely remedy; otherwise, it would be too late to treat. This study is an attempt to focus on the level of NPAs in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu over the study period. The study also makes an indepth analysis of the reasons for NPAs based on the opinion survey of officials.

1.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Banking activities involve taking as well as managing risk. Lending, for instance, involves the risk of the borrower defaulting, or paying the fixed rate of interest when interest rates are actually falling. Such risks cause banks to earn less than what they have to pay for deposits. The major risks which a typical banking entity is exposed to are credit risk, liquidity risk, interest rate risk, market risk and operational risk besides, new type of risks in the 21st century, such as money laundering risk, compliance risk, etc.³ But credit risk stands out as the most detrimental of them all. Credit risk is acute in DCCBs, since they are the important vessels of priority sector lending through their member PACBs.

The NPAs of the Indian banking system have assumed large proportions and are a continuing deterrent to the smooth flow of credit to the productive sectors of industry and agriculture. The high level committee on financial system constituted by the Reserve Bank of India in 1991 under the chairmanship of Sri M. Narasimham, observed that serious problems are plaguing the financial sectors which are reflected in the decline in productivity and efficiency. The erosion of profitability due to the deterioration in the quality of the loan portfolio was observed. The committee stressed the need for the introduction of financial reforms in the banking sector. After the implementation of the prudential norms in 1996-1997, the level of NPAs has been increasing in the DCCB. The gross NPAs of DCCBs in Tamilnadu was Rs.1,31,491.34 lakhs in 31.3.2005, which form 17.59 per cent of total gross NPAs to total gross loans and advances.⁴

At the macro level, NPAs have virtually stopped the supply line of credit to potential borrowers, which has a negative effect on capital formation and economic activity in the country. The point to note is that the increasing trend of NPAs in absolute terms is a cause for great concern as this has an adverse impact on the performance of the real economy due to the mishandling of resources by banks as an intermediary. The funds mobilized at a cost get stuck without any return either to the bank or to the economy. This reflects badly on the operational efficiency of banks which is essential for sustained improvement of economic activity and growth. According to an assessment, NPAs in India are 16 per cent

of the total loans given out by banks and financial institutions. These NPAs account for 14 per cent of the country's GDP.⁵

At the micro level, the unsustainable level of NPAs has eroded the profitability of banks through reduced interest income and increased provisioning requirements, besides restricting the recycling of funds leading to serious asset-liability mismatches. It has *inter alia* led to reduction in their competitiveness and erosion in their capital base.⁶ The presence of NPAs in the bank balance sheet corrodes the average earnings from loan assets and total assets.⁷ The interest spread, an indicator of the operating profitability, declines due to NPAs, since the interest income on NPAs cannot accrue due to prudential regulations; and provision also has to be created for NPAs from the operating profits. A large amount of managerial time and manpower have to be spent on monitoring the accounts in default, adding avoidable costs to transaction costs of lending operations, ultimately increasing the burden of the bank. Thus the profit margin is likely to be reduced further.

Lack of technological advancement which can help in reducing the cost of funds, faster movement of funds, ensuring efficient and effective payment and settlement, are also stated to be one of the reasons for growing NPAs. The major culprits behind high NPAs level are willful default, mismanagement and lack of planning. Public money obtained from banks has been systematically siphoned

away by our industries.⁸ The problem of NPAs has degenerated to such an extent that there is an effort to publish lists of defaulters because of whom, some of the banks are in dire financial straits.

The RBI Bulletin argues that India's high level of NPAs is a historical legacy. This is a rather dubious claim. It is far better to focus on the systemic failures such as lacunae in the credit recovery system arising from inadequate legal provision on foreclosure and bankruptcy, long drawn out legal procedures, and difficulties in the execution of the decrees awarded by the courts. These continue to be a feature of the present financial situation.⁹

The weak capital position of the Indian banking system is largely a reflection of the growing asset-quality problems stemming from weak underwriting and credit management systems and vulnerabilities of the Indian banking sector to the impact of globalisation on the country's key industrial sectors. The asset-quality position has also suffered from regulations with respect to lending to priority sectors.¹⁰

The effect of NPAs is gradually felt in all parts of the economy viz. savings, investments, production, employment and services, affecting adversely capital formation and economic growth, and causing fiscal deficit, inflation, and finally the country's rating and confidence level as far as the international image and standing are concerned. The efficiency of the banking system to act as an

efficient intermediary is dependent on its soundness based *inter alia* on its quality of assets, particularly advances.

The high level of NPAs in banks and financial institutions has been a matter of grave concern to the public especially as bank credit is a catalyst for the economic growth of the country. Any bottleneck in the smooth flow of credit, for which one cause is the mounting NPAs, is bound to create adverse repercussions in the economy. NPAs are not therefore the concern of only lenders.¹¹

The NPAs reflected in the books of banks do not show the complete picture because an identical amount has been written off from the books in the past several years. NPAs do not generate any revenue and impact the bottom line because the hard earned money from performing assets has to be diverted to meet the provisioning needs of NPAs.¹²

Not only high NPAs affect the profitability of the banks, but they also put stress on the financial system as a whole, as more capital has to be brought in. Besides, as NPAs increase, banks tend to shy away from further lending.¹³

World Bank studies have indicated that on a minimum Capital Adequacy Ratio of eight per cent, when the net NPAs of a bank reach 15 per cent, then its capital will get wiped out. Therefore, as a rule of thumb, when the net NPAs of

the banking system exceed 15 per cent, the system is likely to be in distress and to be unsound.¹⁴

The co-operative sector is plagued by many ills, both man-made and natural. They are affected by maladministration, mis-utilisation of funds, poor recovery, dual control, lack of professionalism, limited areas of operation, mounting NPAs, etc. The Government set up a task force for revamping the co-operative credit structure. Out of 23 DCCBs in Tamil Nadu, fourteen banks have a Gross NPA of above 15 per cent, while seven banks have Gross NPAs exceeding 20 per cent as on 31st March 2005.¹⁵

The loan portfolio with NPA reduces the liquidity and profitability position of the DCCBs. The next loan cannot be issued in time when the capital is locked idle; it will lead to erosion of financial resources. When the resources deployed by the DCCB and the PACB are locked up as NPAs and overdues respectively, the DCCBs and the PACB are not able to refinance from the apex bank. Recoveries also serve as an indicator of the quality of lending since repayments are expected from out of the incremental income generated by the productive use of loans.¹⁶

As a defaulter, the borrower is cut-off from any access to credit from these institutions affect the borrowers' productive enterprise. A much higher price has to be paid for any informal source of credit. Thus, the agriculturist and other

related enterprises suffer on account of non-availability of adequate credit supply for investment and working capital.

Decline in the profitability and liquidity ultimately affects the solvency position of the co-operative banks. Hence a probe into the impact of NPAs on the various performance variables of the banks has been made

One of the important limitations of the federal character of the Co-operative credit structure is that heavy overdues at the primary level make the societies dormant, creating a difficult situation for the central bank to borrow from higher financial agencies. This leads to a cumulative effect of more NPAs, overdues and dormancy in societies, stagnation if not recession of credit. Hence it is imperative to curb overdues at the primary level.¹⁷ Hence a complete examination into the reasons for higher NPAs would help suggest measures for controlling NPAs, improving banking operation and ultimately for reducing NPAs at the DCCBs' level.

1.2 RELEVANCE OF THE STUDY

Tamilnadu state, predominantly agricultural in nature, depends greatly on agricultural finance. Short-term credit forms a major portion of the agricultural credit disbursed by DCCBs. The impact of more lending to the agricultural sector might have contributed to a major portion of the NPAs in the banks. Since 23

DCCBs play a predominant role in agricultural finance through their 722 branches and 4497 Primary Agricultural Co-operative Banks, it has been considered highly relevant for the study. Any fruitful suggestion emanating from the study may bring great relief to the economy as a whole.

1.3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study covers all the 23 DCCBs in Tamilnadu. It focuses on the financial performance of DCCBs, besides making an assessment of the position and growth of NPAs in DCCBs. The impact of NPAs on various performance variables in DCCBs has also been measured. The perception of officials on NPAs in DCCBs has also been studied.

1.4. OBJECTIVES

This research has been undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To study the financial performance and the growth of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu during the study period.
2. To assess the position and growth of Non-performing assets in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.
3. To examine the impact of NPAs on profitability and other performance variables.

4. To study the perception of officials on NPAs and their opinions for reducing NPAs and improving bank performance.

1.5. HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses have been formulated to analyse the officials' opinion regarding reducing NPAs.

1. There is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement "The problems of NPA can be contained to a great extent by maintaining a continuous rapport/relationship with borrower".
2. There is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement "Borrowers have to be made more accountable/responsible to contain NPA problem".
3. There is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement "Involvement of Auditors, Accountants, Regulators, Representative Bodies would help recover bank dues in an effective manner".
4. There is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement "Corporate Governance in Corporate Bodies can help improve the conduct of accounts with banks and bring down level of NPAs".
5. There is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement "Banks will have to educate their employees about NPA and its effect on the Banks' performance."

6. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Improved Credit Appraisal System will help reduce NPAs”.
7. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Continuous monitoring and follow-up action are required for reducing NPAs”.
8. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Improved legal system with increased role of DRT will bring down NPAs”
9. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Improved exchange of Information will reduce NPAs”.
10. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Improved market intelligence system will help reduce NPAs”.
11. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Avoiding political interference will help reduce NPAs”.
12. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “ Involvement of Representative Bodies will reduce NPAs.”
13. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Introduction of Incentive/Reward system to staff engaged in collection process will help reduce NPAs”.
14. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Proper selection of borrower’s project will reduce NPAs”.

15. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Financing only viable projects will bring down NPAs”.
16. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Extending need based financing will help reduce NPAs”.
17. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Ensuring proper end-use will reduce NPAs”.
18. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “ Proper post-sanction follow-up will reduce NPAs”.
19. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Regular contact with borrowers will help reduce NPAs”.
20. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Regular monitoring of the accounts will help reduce NPAs”.
21. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Avoiding overdrawn extraneous debt will help reduce NPAs”.
22. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Holding of recovery camps will reduce NPAs”.
23. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Special incentives for prompt repayment will reduce NPAs”.
24. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Good borrowers are willing to repay”.

25. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Good borrowers are not willing to repay”.

26. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Bad borrowers are willing to repay”.

27. There is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement “Bad borrowers are not willing to repay”.

1.6. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The present study covers a period of seven years of secondary data from 1998-1999 to 2004-2005 for study purpose. Data were available upto 2004-2005 during the field work and accordingly data upto 2004-2005 were alone used for analysis, which may not fully relevant to the later period. Anyhow, latest developments with regard to NPAs have been incorporated in appropriate places. This study mainly depends up on secondary data obtained from the records of all the DCCBs and the TNSC bank both published and unpublished. In this study, the financial performance of all the DCCBs have been analysed with the help of some selected financial indicators. The perception of the officials on NPAs in DCCBs were solicited from selected officials comprising of Special Officer/ Managing Director, General Manager, Executive Officer, Assistant General Managers, Managers and Assistant Managers and from for Senior Assistants,

Junior Assistants and other subordinate staff of the banks. The study does not cover the officials of the Primary Agricultural Co-operative Banks (PACBs).

1.7 PRESENTATION OF THE REPORT

The thesis has been organized into seven chapters, while the first chapter deals with the Introduction and the Design of the Study. The second chapter is concerned with the Review of Literature and Methodology. Chapter Three is devoted to the financial performance of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu. The fourth chapter deals with NPAs - concept and status in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu. An analysis of the impact of NPAs on various performance variables in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu is presented in Chapter Five. Perception of Officials on NPAs in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu is discussed in Chapter Six. Chapter Seven provides the summary of findings, suggestions and conclusions.

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. V.B. Jugale, *Financial Sector Reforms in the World*, Serials Publications, New Delhi, 2006, p.216.
2. Ens Economic Bureau, “Banks’ Bad Loans Other Sticky Assets Touch Rs.2,36,000 Crore”, *The New Indian Express*, Mumbai, January 5, 2006, p.13.
3. Nagesh Pinge, “Risk Management A New Approach Needed”, *Chartered Financial Analyst*, October 2005, p.35.
4. *Annual Report*, Tamil Nadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Ltd., Chennai, 2005.
5. Bhupesh, “Ernst Pegs NPA 50% Higher at \$ 25 Billion”, *The Business Standard*, July 12, 2002.
6. Sardar Narinder Singh Gujral, “The NPA Problem Miles to Go”, *Chartered Financial Analyst*, March 2003, p.73.
7. N.S. Toor, *Non-Performing Advances in Banks*, Skylark Publications, New Delhi, 1998, p.44.
8. K.V. Krishnamurthy, “At No Rate”, *The Business Standard*, June 13, 2002.
9. S. Venkitaramanan, “There is More to NPAs than Poor Credit Appraisal”, *The Business Line*, July 12, 1999.
10. SCBs need \$13 bn to Support Asset Losses, *The Economic Times*, December 20, 2000.
11. G.P. Muniappan, “Confederation of Indian Industry”, *Banking Submit 2002* at Mumbai on April 1, 2002.
12. K.V.Krishnamurthy, *op.cit.*
13. S. Venkitaramanan, *op.cit.*

14. Reserve Bank of India, “Trend and Progress of Banking in India 2000-01”, Supplement to RBI Bulletin, Appendix II 9(B), December 2001, p.194.
15. *Annual Report 2005* (Tamil Nadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Ltd., Chennai).
16. P.S.V. Chari and P.S. Narasimham, “A Prescription of Good Credit Management”, *The Hindu* (Chennai), 3rd January 2002, BS-1.
17. R. Selvaraju, G. Vasanthi and Justin Nelson Michael, “Effect of NPAs on Operational Efficiency of CCBs”, *Indian Economic Panorama*, Vol.16, No.3, October 2006, p.34.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents a review of literature on the past research studies and describes the methodology adopted for the present study. The review has facilitated the researcher to adopt, modify and formulate an improved conceptual frame work for the use of the present study and to draw meaningful conclusions.

2.1 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Banking Regulatory Authorities, policy makers and researchers alike are interested in research on NPAs since prudential norms have also been implemented in co-operative banks from 1996-97. The study of NPAs in DCCBs is a relatively new field of study. Literature available on the subject reveals that both empirical and non-empirical studies have already dealt with the problem of NPAs and their impact on the performance of banks from the angle of profitability, liquidity, equity and change in their approach to business. A brief review of these studies is presented here.

J. Murthy, et al. (1988) have shown that default brings down the return accruing to reduce effective rate of interest and reduces the funds recirculation and increases their dependence on external sources thereby increasing the costs.¹

A study by the Office of the Comptroller of Currency (OCC) of the United States in 1988 found that poor asset quality was a major factor responsible for the failure of 98 per cent of the banks. Hence, reduction in gross NPAs was desirable.²

According to the report of the Agricultural Credit Review Committee (1989) overdues prevented recycling of funds, impaired refinance eligibility and productivity of co-operative banks. Nearly 26 per cent of the resources deployed by the credit agencies for the agriculture sector were locked up in overdues and were not available for recycling. At the institutional level, the clogging of overdues severely impaired the eligibility of the credit agencies for refinance from the NABARD. As a defaulter, the borrower is cut off from any access to credit from institutions. This affects his productive enterprise.³

Kwan, et al., (1994) also concluded that there is a negative relationship between efficiency and the problem of loans.⁴

N.S. Toor (1994) found that poor recovery management led to reduction in yield on advances, reduced productivity, loss in the credibility and put detrimental impact on the policies of the banks.⁵

V.S. Kaveri (1995) also examined the impact of NPAs on profitability by taking profit making and six loss making banks and concluded that loss making

banks maintained higher NPAs in the loan portfolio which led them to show losses.⁶

Ross Gary (1996) in the study 'Risk Happen, focused on the risk and performance relationship in commercial banking. It is not evident that banks never approved a loan with the intent that the loans would become Non-Performing Assets and that an organisation might learn from its prior decisions as banks continue to accumulate non-performing loans in the normal course of business.⁷

Berger, et al., (1997) examined the relationship between problem loan and bank efficiency by employing the Granger-causality technique and found that the high level of problem loans causes banks to increase spending on monitoring, working out and/or selling off these loans and possibly to become more diligent in administering the portion of their existing loan portfolio that is currently performing.⁸

Gupta and Debashish (1997) also concluded that NPAs affect the profitability of banks and lead to liquidity crunch.⁹

Prem Sharma (1998) opined that in the aftermath of the Financial Sector Reforms, the co-operative banks had to meet the challenges of the financial sector reforms by competing with Public Sector Banks and Private Sector Banks in the

mobilisation of deposits, savings and advancing of loans to tone up their functional effectiveness and to attain capital adequacy norms.¹⁰

According to the comparative study of NPA by Satyanarayana (1998), the NPA in Venezuela, Mexico, Thailand, Brazil, Japan, Taiwan, Colombia, Chile, Korea, Argentina, Intonesia, Malaysia, Hongkong, U.S.A. and Singapore indicated that except in Latin America the NPA levels were in single digit (6 per cent to 7 per cent). India was viewed unfavourably in the international arena, as India has the highest proportion of NPAs (14.45 per cent) among the sixteen countries in 1994-1995.¹¹

Sudhakar Patra (1998) showed that the Boudh CCB in Orissa was not successful in making profit due to non-repayment of loans in time.¹²

Abhiman Roy Das (1999) in his paper “Profitability in Public Sector Banks” evaluates inter-bank variability of profit among the Public Sector Banks during 1992-98 and observes that there is a distinct risk aversion among the banks as indicated by their preference for investments over advances.¹³

Das and Abhiman (1999) have compared the various efficiency measures of public sector banks by applying the data envelopment analysis model and concluded that the level of NPAs has a significant negative relationship with efficiency estimates.¹⁴

M.S. Verma, (1999) in the working group concluded that the high level of NPAs leads to the operational failure of the banks.¹⁵

A.P. Pati, (1999) in his study analysed the causes, consequences and cure of large NPAs in Indian banks. Non-linkage of lending with productive investment and recovery with credit-product sale, the author argues, is one of the main causes of large NPAs. Moreover, there is the government directed lending in priority sector leading to NPAs. As a consequence, profitability falls and loan availability shrinks. As a remedy the author suggests improved recovery mechanism and improved credit management targeted to NPA minimisation.¹⁶

P.K. Bhattacharjee (1999) in his paper finds that the Indian banking system has an asset backed loan system supported by collaterals and guarantees. The gross NPAs in India are 17 per cent whereas in China it is 25 per cent to 45 per cent.¹⁷

S.G. Phadnis (1999) justified the Narasimham Committee's observation that asset quality was very poor in directed lending, since around 48 per cent of NPAs were in the priority sector advances group.¹⁸

The Working Committee of the RBI (1999) on NPAs considered write-off, compromise and one-time settlement for recovery of NPAs. It recommended a compromise model for the recovery of NPAs which is the most effective

mechanism. However, both write-off and compromise are steps to be taken with caution and due monitoring.¹⁹

An RBI study (1999) stated that banks were required to closely monitor the operations of the borrowal units. In respect of accounts where the classification of asset worsens, banks were required to take prompt steps to recover the dues and staff accountability was required to be examined. Special emphasis was placed on monitoring of large NPA accounts, also on the reduction of NPAs, through upgradation, recovery and compromise settlements.²⁰

Klingebl and Daniela (2000) discussed the suitability model of asset reconstruction companies to solve the problem of NPAs. Only a few studies have highlighted the impact of NPAs on the performance of banks.²¹

K.G. Selvan and Samwel Kakuko Lopoyetum, (2000) concluded that the management of NPA and improvement of the recovery rates is the need of the hour. The suitable course on NPA management is that it is plainly open to the bankers to coherently ensure that the assets do not become NPAs. But, if they do, then bankers should strive hard and take early steps to recover the amount, failing which the profitability and viability of the bank will get eroded and dwindle from time to time.²²

Katuri Nageswara Rao (2000) in his article highlighted the fact that the recovery of NPAs has become the Critical Performance Area (CPA) for banks in India, consequent on the implementation of the prudential norms in the wake of new economic reforms. There are weak banks and distress zone banks as well clamouring for immediate attention from the government.²³

Sanjay Kumar (2000) in his article views said that since the banking sector reforms, NPAs have become the most critical factor governing the performance of banks. NPAs have various implications on profitability, liquidity and solvency of the Regional Rural Banks.²⁴

K. Satyanarayana and Ganti Subrahmanyam, (2000) in their article presented a comprehensive picture of non-performing advances of commercial banks in India in the post-reform period. Undoubtedly, banks in India carry 15-16 per cent of their gross advances as NPAs, which is very high by international standard, though more than 50 per cent of these impaired assets are covered through provision. In fact, the ratio of net NPAs to tangible net worth of public sector banks is alarmingly 70 per cent which perhaps is coming in the way of better rating of banks in the market. Private sector banks, which have a relatively lower proportion of NPAs, have shown a sudden spurt in the last 2-3 years. The proportion of credit risk among priority sector advances like SSI, agriculture, etc. is almost double (21.62%) when compared to non-priority (11.86%) advances.²⁵

Caprio and Klingebiel (2000) in their working paper point out that the problem of NPAs may be due to bad management by banks. According to their view, in an increasingly competitive financial market, economic factors have evolved as the key influences on banks' non-performing loans. In this context, various studies have underscored, the role of the banks' lending policy in general and the terms of credit defined over, *inter alia*, cost maturity and collaterals in influencing the movement of bank's non-performing loans.²⁶

P. Ganesan (2001) in his study with a bearing on NPAs and banks' dealt with administrative measures to improve the profitability of banks. In an empirical study on the determinants of profitability of the public sector banks in India, it has been observed that credit flow into the economy could not produce any positive impact over banks' profitability due to higher NPA when cost incurred on defaulted and other loan assets is high.²⁷

Westgaard, et.al. (2001) identified different financial variables as well as other firm characteristics affecting the default probability which if identified in advance can help controlling the fresh accretion of NPAs.²⁸

V.S. Kaveri (2001) studied the non-performance assets of the various banks and suggested various strategies to reduce the extent of NPAs. In view of the steep rise in fresh NPA advances, credit should be strengthened. The RBI should use some new policies/strategies to prevent NPAs.²⁹

Indira Rajaraman and Garima Vasistha (2002) in their study on NPL (Non-Performing Loans) of public sector banks observe that for banks operating in regions where there has been marked industrial decline, recapitalisation with operational restructuring amounts to use of public funds with no discernible public purpose and makes the drastic suggestion that closure of banks with liquidation of assets including real estate at market value should prove to be far more cost-effective even with full depositor protection.³⁰

H. Srinivasa Rao (2002) in his thesis suggested that the Andhra Pradesh State Co-operative Bank (APCOB) should initiate certain steps like monitoring the spending pattern of loans (indirectly), implementation of the NABARD guidelines, and designing and implementation of collection policies to solve the problems of NPAs, by issuing necessary guidelines to the DCCBs and PACS at the grass root level.³¹

Monica Soni, (2002) in her paper analyses the NPA position of two major components of Rural Banking viz. the Co-operative Banks and the Regional Rural Banks. The situation with regard to NPA management by different co-operative banks is not at all satisfactory. It shows that a large proportion of total NPAs is contributed by RRBs in the current viability category.³²

D. Satish (2002) in their study concluded that the provisions of the securitization and reconstruction of financial assets ordinance would provide the

teeth for banks and financial institutions to get rid of their NPAs. But the Combo nature of the ordinance, which combines three unrelated issues of securitization, asset reconstruction and enforcement of security interest, might just complicate the scenario.³³

The Tarapore Committee on Capital Account Convertibility (CAC) laid down that the 5 per cent level of NPAs in banks is an important milestone to be reached for full convertibility.³⁴

According to Samal (2002) the NPA problem was due to defects in like the slow-moving legal system and the absence of a proper legal framework.³⁵

Sardar Narinder Singh Gujral (2003) in his article says that the Securitization Act is a fine, comprehensive and extraordinary piece of legislation. It is a giant leap forward in the realm of financial sector reforms. The Act is not a financial TADA. It is a tool and not a weapon in the hands of the banks to shoot the defaulters.³⁶

A study done by Santi Gopal and Soma Dey (2003) showed that it is a paramount task for the banks to manage their NPAs more efficiently so that they can change their character from NPAs to performing assets. This study makes an attempt to analyse the loan amount-wise, age-wise, head-wise and sector-wise classification of NPAs and to identify the factors responsible for the growth of

NPAs of the Khatra People's Co-operative Bank Ltd., UCB, in the district of Bankura in West Bengal.³⁷

P. Srinivas Subbarao (2003) in his paper concluded that the level of NPAs in the Indian PSBs is relatively high by international standards (i.e., 2%). The problem of NPAs should be handled with strict enforcement of prudential norms and requirements of transparency. The legal action, and recovery process should be made effective with improved participation of Debt Recovery Tribunals (DRT), Lok Adalats and Securitisation and Assets Reconstruction Companies.³⁸

R. Singh (2003) analysed the profitability management of banks under the deregulated environment with some financial parameters of the major four bank groups. i.e. public sector banks, old private sector banks, new private sector banks and foreign banks. Profitability has declined in the deregulated environment. He emphasised that the banking sector must be competitive in the deregulated environment. Banks should prefer non-interest income sources.³⁹

A. Das and Ghosh (2003) made an empirical analysis of non-performing loans of India's public sector banks relating to various indicators such as asset size, credit growth and macro economic condition, and operating efficiency indicator. An empirical analysis suggests that besides supporting a policy environment, banks have to devise appropriate lending terms taking into account

the cost of credit, cost of funds, maturity of loans and credit orientation among other to induce borrowers to make prompt repayment.⁴⁰

Arun Yeole, (2004) in her article “The problem of NPAs”, showed that the problem of non-performing assets (NPAs) is more in the public sector banks (PSBs) as compared to the private sector banks and foreign banks. NPAs have a direct impact on a bank’s profitability, liquidity and equity. The NPAs of the Indian PSBs are considered relatively high by international standards. The biggest ever challenge that the banking industry now faces is the management of NPAs.⁴¹

D.K. Chellani and Dr. Rita Raj (2004) concluded that the DCCBs have an undisputedly important role in the present three-tire federal co-operative credit structure. In view thereof it is extremely vital that more focused attention be paid to the long-term viability and sustainability of their operations. The implementation of prudential norms would bring further pressure on the already fragile operations of the DCCBs. The DCCBs in Gujarat, therefore, had to focus on both qualitative and quantitative core banking performance where they are far behind the all India figures.⁴²

K. Rajendran (2004) in his article “Non-performing assets” concluded that increasing NPA exercises a major impact on the DCCBs. DCCBs shall have to educate their employees on NPA and its effect on the bank. Change in NPA norms and credit monitoring and recovery mechanism should be strengthened.⁴³

Carlton Pereira (2004) in his article pointed out that there are certain regulatory and fiscal issues facing investors in the emerging NPA business. These in their current form would deter investors from investing in the business. This article highlights the issues and points the way forward to their effective resolution to facilitate the investment process.⁴⁴

Sanjai Singh Rathore and Alka Singh (2004) in their article found that there is a relationship between non-performing assets and capital adequacy considering the case study of the Avadh Gramin Bank, Lucknow. The study has found that the bank has a very poor receiving ratio. It has a higher percentage of NPAs in its total advances.⁴⁵

Meena Sharma (2005) attempts to study the problem of NPAs in public sector banks and also their impact on the performance of these banks. The Impact of NPAs on the profitability of the banks is analysed by applying the multiple regression model. The impact of NPAs on the productivity, achievement of capital adequacy level, funds mobilisation and deployment policy of the banks are also analysed. NPAs not only affect the performance of the banks but also do irreparable harm to the entire economy. It endangers the very foundation of the credit system. Concerted efforts are required at the RBI, banks and judiciary levels to control the menace of NPAs. Efficient legal framework, improvement in

credit appraisal and monitoring skills of banks and strong political will could enable Indian banks to find a satisfactory solution to the problem.⁴⁶

Rajendra Singh (2005) in his work concluded that with the enactment of The Securitisation Act, it is felt that borrowers would no longer be able to take banks lightly and simply walk away with scarce public money. The threat of taking over of the collateral assets and enforcement of loan recovery has already begun to show positive results. So far NPA recoveries are estimated to be in the range of 20 per cent. During the next 3-4 years, the banks hope to recover 50 to 60 per cent of NPAs through tough measures.⁴⁷

K.C. Chakraborty (2005) in his article pointed out that the banks have to face several challenges in managing NPAs. Besides ensuring better scrutiny of the credit proposals before sanction, banks need to watch closely and monitor the assets from the beginning. In fact, NPA management begins right from the selection of borrowers.⁴⁸

Justin Nelson Michael (2005) in his thesis “A study on Non-Performing Assets in Co-operative Banks with Reference to Cuddalore District Central Co-operative Bank Ltd., Tamil Nadu” has assessed the position of non-performing assets in the Cuddalore District Central Co-operative Bank, the effect of non-performing assets on the financial health of the bank and the recovery of

co-operative credit and examined the factors discriminating default of co-operative credit, which subsequently increases non-performing assets.⁴⁹

N. Ganesan (2006) in his article examined the performance (operational efficiency) of 30 state co-operative banks (SCBs) in India for the financial year 2002-03 to 2003-04. The Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is used to find the efficiency of SCBs. Initially, the individual efficiencies are determined. In the second stage SCBs are grouped region-wise and their efficiencies are traced. He has used DEA for finding the regional efficiency also. In the third stage, he has adopted the approach of cross-efficiency.⁵⁰

S. Khasnobis (2006) in his article concluded that the distribution of NPAs in the system follows 8-20 rules whereby 20 per cent by number of borrowers are responsible for 80 per cent of the value of impaired assets. The large impaired assets comprise industrial assets with good restructuring potential. The ARCIL experience shows that in value terms more than 60 per cent of the impaired assets are amenable to restructuring or to be sold as a going concern. The small assets, however, have to be put through a recovery process, where the collateral based financing system followed in the country offers a fair recovery potential.⁵¹

T. Vanniarajan (2006) focused his paper on the problem of NPAs and found that they were more in public sector banks as compared to other banks. NPAs have a direct impact on a bank's profitability, liquidity and equity.⁵²

R.K. Uppal and Rimpi Kaur (2007) in their article concluded that the poor performance of priority sector advances, persistence of large NPAs and decreasing interest income are the issues that call for careful attention in the subsequent dose of the reforms.⁵³

Gourav Vallabh, et al., (2007) in their paper made an empirical approach to the analysis of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) of public, private and foreign sector banks in India. The important results derived from the analysis include the finding that banks' exposure to priority sector lending reduces NPAs.⁵⁴

C. Lakshmanan and A. Dharmendran (2007) in their article said that the problem of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) is less in the Chennai Central Co-operative Bank as compared to the other CCBs in Tamil Nadu. They also focused on the impact of NPAs on the Net Profit, Investment, Legal Expenses and Spread of the bank. The study concludes that the effective management of NPAs is essential to strengthen the financial position of the bank.⁵⁵

The large number of literature on the problem of NPAs in different types of banks and financial institutions reflects the status of NPAs and their impact on public sector banks. There has been no separate study in this regard to the status and impact of NPAs in all the DCCBs put together in Tamil Nadu along with the perception of the officials. This study is an attempt to fill the gap in the research relating to NPA management in the District Central Co-operative Banks in

Tamilnadu. The parameters used here for analysis may form the basis for future studies in other areas of banking. Similarly, the macro-level study may further lead to unit level studies at the micro-level.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

This part of the study describes the methodology which includes collection of data, sampling design, period of study, geographical coverage, operational definition of concept, construction of tools, tools of analysis, data processing and framework of analysis.

2.2.1 Collection of Data

This study is an empirical one. The proper selection of an appropriate method of data collection is extremely important. This applies to both analytical and empirical data.

The researcher has made use of all available documents and/or records, published and unpublished, in order to gather information. Books, journals, reports, monographs, seminar papers, co-operative audit circulars and reports of committees were also consulted for information. The main documents relied on were the annual reports of all the District Central Co-operative Banks (DCCBs); Reports of Tamil Nadu State Apex Co-operative Bank (TNSCB), Chennai; Reports of the Registrar of Co-operative Societies (RCS), Chennai; Reports of the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), Bombay;

Reports of the Agricultural Credit Department (ACD) and the Reserve Bank of India.

Primary data were collected through field survey. Officials of the DCCBs were contacted in the field. Structured questionnaires were prepared and personally mailed to all the officials by the researcher. Of course the questionnaire was pre-tested before it was administered. It consisted of different types of questions. From Annexure-A, it can be found that the questionnaire includes different types of questions through rating scales.

2.2.2 Sampling Design

The multi-stage purposive sampling is adopted for the study with Tamil Nadu state as the universe, District as the stratum, DCCBs as primary units of the sampling and the banks' officials as ultimate units.

Tamil Nadu state had of 29 Districts during the study period. There were 23 DCCBs. Each bank had eighteen officials with different positions - three officials in the top level management (Special Officer/Managing Director, General Manager and Executive Officer), five in the middle level management (Assistant General Manager of Administration, Banking, Development, Agri-Credit and other Industrial Credit) and ten in the lower level management (Manager and Assistant Manager of Administration, Banking, Development, Agri

credit and other Industrial Credit) have been covered for the study. The total number of officials in all the 23 DCCBs at the time of survey was 414. Of these 414 officials, there is a total of 69 officials in the top level management, 115 in the middle level management and 230 in the lower level management.

The questionnaire was mailed to each official individually in all the 23 DCCBs. A self-addressed stamped envelop was also sent along with it for returning the filled up questionnaire. Two weeks after mailing the questionnaire a reminder was sent. Three hundred and twenty two usable completed questionnaires were received. Accordingly the researcher has made all the respondents (322) sample for the study.

In order to assess the perception of the officials on NPAs 322 officials were purposively selected by adopting the multi-stage sampling method with 56 officials in the top level management, 98 in the middle level management and 168 in the lower level management. The response rate is 81 per cent in the top level management, 85 per cent in the middle level management and 73 per cent in the lower level management. Table 2.1 presents the distribution pattern of the sample bank-wise and position-wise.

TABLE 2.1
DISTRIBUTION PATTERN OF THE SAMPLES BANK-WISE
AND POSITION-WISE

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCB	Position of Officials			Total No. of Officials	No. of Sample Officials
		Top Level Management	Middle Level Management	Lower Level Management		
1.	Chennai	3	5	10	18	15
2.	Coimbatore	3	5	10	18	13
3.	Cuddalore	3	5	10	18	14
4.	Dharmapuri	3	5	10	18	13
5.	Dindigul	3	5	10	18	16
6.	Erode	3	5	10	18	18
7.	Kancheepuram	3	5	10	18	14
8.	Kanyakumari	3	5	10	18	17
9.	Kumbakonam	3	5	10	18	12
10.	Madurai	3	5	10	18	18
11.	Nilgiris	3	5	10	18	11
12.	Pudukkottai	3	5	10	18	15
13.	Ramanathapuram	3	5	10	18	10
14.	Salem	3	5	10	18	14
15.	Sivagangai	3	5	10	18	13
16.	Thanjavur	3	5	10	18	13
17.	Tiruchirapalli	3	5	10	18	14
18.	Tirunelveli	3	5	10	18	15
19.	Tiruvannamalai	3	5	10	18	16
20.	Thoothukudi	3	5	10	18	15
21.	Vellore	3	5	10	18	14
22.	Villupuram	3	5	10	18	10
23.	Virhdungagar	3	5	10	18	12
	Total No.of officials	69	115	230	414	
	No.of Sample officials	56	98	168		322
	Response Rate	81%	85%	73%		

2.2.3 Period of Study

The present study is based on the data collected from primary as well as secondary sources to accomplish the purpose and various objectives of the study. In this study financial data from all the 23 DCCBs located in different corners of Tamil Nadu State covering a period of seven years from 1998-99 to 2004-05 have been used. The questionnaires were sent to all the DCCBs' officials. The completed questionnaires were received from 1st September 2006 to 30th June 2007.

2.2.4 Geographical Coverage

The Tamil Nadu State, predominantly agricultural in nature, also has a long history of co-operation. The state of Tamil Nadu is situated on the South Eastern side of the Indian Peninsula. It is bound on the East by the Bay of Bengal, on the South by the Indian Ocean, on the West by the States of Kerala, Karnataka and on the North by Andhra Pradesh. The total area of Tamil Nadu is 130058 sq.km. The state has been divided into 31 Revenue Districts (Fig. 2.1). The state has eight municipal corporations, viz., Chennai, Madurai, Coimbatore Salem, Trichy, Tirunelveli, Erode and Tirupur. There are 100 municipalities, seven township committees, 16 townships, 385 panchayat unions, 201 taluks and 12,593 village panchayats. The population of the state as on March 2001 was 62.41 million as per the 2000-2001 Census.⁵⁶ The state is well served by a net work of banks both

commercial and co-operatives. Tamil Nadu is one of the states where Co-operative Banks are playing a leading and vital role in the rural credit dispensation and mobilisation of rural deposits. There are 23 DCCBs (as on 31st March 2005) in the state of Tamil Nadu (Table 2.2). The function of the DCCBs and their branches has been spread over in all the districts of Tamil Nadu. The study covers all the 23 DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

Fig: 2.1 Districts of Tamil Nadu State
Source www.tn.gov.in

TABLE 2.2
LIST OF D.C.C. BANKS IN TAMILNADU

Sl.No.	Name of the DCC Bank
1.	Chennai
2.	Coimbatore
3.	Cuddalore
4.	Dharmapuri
5.	Dindigul
6.	Erode
7.	Kancheepuram
8.	Kanyakumari
9.	Kumbakonam
10.	Madurai
11.	Nilgiris
12.	Pudukkottai
13.	Ramanathapuram
14.	Salem
15.	Sivagangai
16.	Thanjavur
17.	Tiruchirapalli
18.	Tirunelveli
19.	Tiruvannamalai
20.	Thoothukudi
21.	Vellore
22.	Villupuram
23.	Virudhunagar

Source: <http://www.tnscbank.com/coopbank>. – DCCB.

2.2.5 Operational Definition of Concepts

2.2.5.1 Bank

Bank refers to the District Central Co-operative Bank in Tamil Nadu.

2.2.5.2 Co-operative Year

The Co-operative year, up to 1991, signifies the year commencing from 1st July and ending with 30th June. From 1991, it commences from 1st April and ends with 31st March.⁵⁷

2.2.5.3. Non-Performing Asset

A credit facility in respect of which interest and/or instalment of principal amount remained 'past due' for two quarters or more. The 'past due' concept has been replaced with the 'overdue' concept from 31 March 2001.⁵⁸ This concept is discussed in detail in the fourth chapter.

2.2.5.4 Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR)

According to the Banking Regulation Act, 1949, under Section 18 "a Co-operative Bank other than a Scheduled State Co-operative Bank or a Primary Co-operative Bank is required to maintain cash reserve with itself or in current account opened with the RBI or the SBI or a Scheduled Commercial Bank of the state concerned or with any other bank notified by the central government of not less than three per cent of demand and time liabilities of the bank on the last Friday of the second preceding fortnight. This is treated as Cash Reserve Ratio of the bank".⁵⁹

2.2.5.5 Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR)

According to the Banking Regulation Act 1949, under section 24, “every Co-operative Bank shall maintain liquid assets like cash, gold and unencumbered securities not less than 25 per cent or such other percentage not exceeding 40 per cent of their demand and time liabilities. This is treated as statutory liquidity ratio of the bank”.⁶⁰

2.2.5.6 Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR)

Capital adequacy ratio is the ratio of capital to risk-weighted assets.⁶¹ Capital adequacy norms need to move in the direction of strengthening the capital base of the co-operative banks and to conform to the applicable norms over a period of time.

2.2.5.7 Spread

Spread refers to the difference between the total interest income earned and received minus the interest amount paid and payable.⁶²

2.2.6 Construction of Tools

The questionnaire for this study was constructed to collect data from the officials of the DCCBs.

Before the construction of the questionnaire, the researcher reviewed previous studies in-depth. Discussions were held with the officials of the DCCBs. In the light of the information gathered, the researcher prepared the questionnaire. Then a pretest was conducted to assess and test its validity in the context of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu. The comments and suggestions expressed by the officials were duly incorporated in the questionnaire. Thus the questionnaire was finalised. Then a pilot study was conducted with twenty-five officials drawn from different cadres. Accordingly the tool was modified to suit the requirements of this study.

The questionnaire was used to collect various data from the officials of the DCCBs. The data relating to their perception of NPAs and their suggestions for reducing NPAs.

To study the perception of officials, 92 questions were asked. Each question had five responses - 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'no opinion', 'disagree' and 'strongly disagree.' The perception of the officials was measured by applying a scaling technique.

2.2.7 Data Processing

After the completion of data collection, the filled up questionnaires were edited properly to make them ready for coding. A master table was prepared to incorporate all the information available in the questionnaire followed by the

construction of classification tables with the help of transcription cards. The classification tables were used for further analysis.

2.2.8 Framework of Analysis

The main aim of the study is to assess the financial performance of the banks, the position of NPAs, the impact of NPAs on performance variables and the perception of officials on NPAs and their suggestions for reducing NPAs in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

Statistical tools have been employed to analyse the data and inferences have been drawn. Statistical tools, such as arithmetic mean, standard deviation, percentage, indices, growth rate, simple and multiple regression tests, partial correlation test and factor analysis have been used. The analysis was done with the help of an SPSS program. The Kolmogorov Smirnov test (KS test), similar to the Chi-square test, has been applied to test the hypotheses.

The growth of DCCBs was assessed in terms of various parameters such as memberships, branches, share capital, reserves, deposits, borrowings, loans and advances, investments, working capital and net profit. Besides, overdues were also analysed in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

The NPAs in DCCBs were analysed in terms of various classification of assets such as standard assets, sub-standard assets, doubtful assets, loss assets,

gross NPAs, provision for NPAs and Net NPAs. The base data relating to all parameters have been provided in Annexure E.

2.2.8.1 Annual Growth Rate

The annual growth rates of the selected parameters have been calculated for all the DCCBs based on the performance variables in the third chapter and the classification of assets in the fourth chapter respectively.

The annual growth rate is calculated through the least square method under time series analysis. The type of function fitted was in the form of

$Y = a + bt$ where 'Y' stands for the above mentioned performance variables and the classification of assets in DCCBs at the state level, 't' is the time period, 'b' is the slope of the time variable and 'a' is the intercept.⁶³

2.2.8.2 Compound Growth Rate

The compound growth rates of the performance variables and the classification of assets were estimated to ascertain the growth performance of the DCCBs with the help of the formula discussed below:

$$Y_t = abt$$

where

Y_t = Value performance variables and classification of assets.

a = intercept

b = parameter

t = years

By employing logarithms of this above equation on both sides, the exponential form gets reduced to a linear form with ' Y_t ' as dependent variable and ' t ' as independent variable. The transformation is given as follows:

$$\ln Y_t = \ln A + \ln B$$

The equation was solved by the ordinary least square method. The parameters ' a ' and ' b ' indicate absolute increment in performance variables and classification of assets. In order to obtain the compound growth rate it is necessary to take anti log of ' b ' and subtract one from it. The value so obtained is multiplied by 100 to get the percentage growth rate.⁶⁴

$$\text{Compound Growth Rate} = (\text{Anti log of } b - 1) \times 100$$

2.2.8.3 Simple Regression Model

To find the relationship between the performance variables and the impact of independent variables on dependent variables, the simple regression model has been used.

$$Y = a + bX + e$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable

X = Independent variable

b = Regression co-efficient of independent variable

e = error term.⁶⁵

This model has been applied to find the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variables in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu separately.

Note: The dependent variable and the independent variables are indicated by signs as shown in the fifth chapter.

2.2.8.4 Multiple Regression Model

The relationship between the performance variables in DCCBs has been analysed with the help of the Karl Pearsons Correlation Co-efficient with 't' statistic. Since the NPAs are one of the various factors that may adversely affect the profitability of banks, an additional attempt has been made to include a few more independent variables such as Overdues, Advances, Legal Expenses and

Spread which have different dimensions in banking activities. Based on the above, the following regression equation was developed.

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + b_5 X_5 + e$$

Where,

Y = Net Profit

X₁ = Gross NPAs

X₂ = Overdues

X₃ = Advances

X₄ = Legal Expenses

X₅ = Spread

b₁..b₅ = Regression Co-efficient

a = Intercept and

e = error term.⁶⁶

This model is applied to find the impact of the independent variables on net profit in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu totally.

2.2.8.5 Factor Analysis

The technique adopted to identify and analyse the officials' opinions on NPAs is the factor analysis. The factor analysis is another multivariate technique. It is an extremely powerful and useful analytic approach to psychological,

behavioural, financial and other types of data. It is a statistical technique for determining the underlying factors or forces among a large number of interdependent variables or measures. It is a method for extracting common factor variances from a set of observations. It groups the number of variables into a smaller set of uncorrelated factors potentially conveying a great deal of information. It tells us what variables belong together – which ones virtually measure the same thing.

The factor analysis is an appropriate technique for cases where the variables have a high degree of intercorrelation. A factor is a construct, a hypothetical entity that is assumed to underlie tests, scales, items or any other measures. The basic concepts relating to factor analysis are factor, factor loading, communality and Eigen value.

Factor: A factor is an underlying dimension of several related variables. There can be one or more factors in a phenomenon depending upon its nature and the number of variables involved in it.

Factor Loadings: These are values that explain how closely the variables are related to each one of the factors discovered. They are factor-variable correlations. It is the absolute size of the loadings that is important in the interpretation of a factor.

Communality (h^2): It shows how much of each variable is accounted for by the underlying factors taken together. The communality of a factor is its common factor variance. The factors with factor loadings of 0.50 or greater are considered significant factors. This limit is chosen because it had been judged that factors with less than 50 per cent common variation with the rotated factor pattern are too weak to report.⁶⁷

Eigen Value (or Latent Root): It is the sum of squared values of factor loadings relating to a factor. It indicates the relative importance of each factor in accounting for the particular set of variables under study.

There are several methods available under Factor Analysis. But the principal components method with Orthogonal Varimax Rotation is mostly used and widely available in the Factor Analytic Computer Programme.

2.2.8.6 KS – Test

For the purpose of the analysis of the opinions of the respondents on specific statements. Null hypotheses were formulated. The formulated hypotheses were tested with the help of the Kolmogorov Smirnov test (KS Test), which has the following form.⁶⁸

$$D = O - E$$

Where

‘D’ refers to calculated value.

‘O’ refers to cumulative observed proportion.

‘E’ refers to cumulative expected proportion.

Cumulative observed proportion is calculated on the basis of observed frequency, that is, observed number. For example the total number of respondents is 322, 84 respondents had given their opinion for gradation 'strongly agree' in the case of the first statement. The observed proportion is calculated by dividing 84 by the total number of respondents, 322. The resultant value (0.26) is the observed proportion. For all the statements, the same method of calculation has been followed. On the basis of observed proportion, the cumulative observed proportion is calculated.

Since there are five gradations, for each gradation 0.20 (i.e. $100/5$) is assigned as expected proportion. On the basis of the expected proportion, the cumulative expected proportion is calculated.

For each gradation, the difference between the cumulative observed proportion and the cumulative expected proportion is calculated. The largest difference is taken as the calculated value. The calculated value is compared with the table value (vide Annexure-B). If the calculated value is greater than the table value, the null hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand if the calculated value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The KS test is used to identify the significant set of officials' opinions for reducing NPAs.

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. J. Murthy, Vishwanatha and A. Bayya Reddy, "Defaults of Financial Institutions at What Cost", *The Chartered Accountant*, Vol.37, No.6, December 1988.
2. Office of the Comptroller of Currency, **Bank Failure: An Evaluation of the Factors Contributing to the Failure of National Banks** (Washington DC: Office of the Comptroller of Currency, June 1988).
3. Reserve Bank of India, *The Report of the Agricultural Credit Review Committee*, RBI, Bombay, 1989.
4. Kwan, Simon Robert and Eisenbies, "*An Analysis of Inefficiencies in Banking: A Stochastic Cost Frontier Approach*", Presented at a Seminar on Productivity Analysis at the University of George, October, 1994.
5. N.S. Toor, "*Non-Performing Advances in Banks*", Skylark Publication, New Delhi, 1994.
6. V.S. Kaveri, "Relationship between Recovery and Profitability of Bank – A Study", *SBI Monthly Review*, Vol.33, 1995.
7. Ross Gary Howard, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Kentucky, 1996, p.126.
8. Berger, Allen N. and Robert De Young, "Problems of Loans and Cost Efficiency in Commercial Banks", *Journal of Banking and Finance*, Vol.21, No.6, June 1997.
9. Gupta and Debashish, "NPA Management: Innovation is the Key", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol.3, No.3, November, 1997.
10. Prem.S. Sarma, "Financial Sector Reforms and the Co-operatives", *The Co-operator*, Vol.36, No.6, December 1998, pp.237-240.
11. K. Satyanarayana, "Feasible NPA Levels of Banks for Capital Account Convertibility", *Prajnan*, Vol.24, No.3, March 1998, pp.325-345.
12. S.N.Tripathy, *Co-operatives for Rural Development*, Edited Books, Discovery Publishing House, New Delhi, 1998, pp.164-183.

13. Abhiman Roy Das, "Profitability in Public Sector Banks", *RBI Occasional Papers*, Vol.20, No.1, Summer 1999, pp. 55-77.
14. Das and Abhiman, "Efficiency of Public Sector Banks: An Application of Data Development Model", *Prajnan*, Vol. 28, No.2, September 1999.
15. Reserve Bank of India, *Report of the Working Group and Restructuring of Public Sector Banks*, RBI, Bombay, (Chairman M.S Verma)1999.
16. A.P. Pati, "NPAs – Causes, Consequences and Cures", *The Management Accountant*, Vol.34, No.11, November 1999, pp. 853-857.
17. P.K. Bhattacharjee, "NPA Management – Perform or Perish", *ICFAI Readers*, Vol.1, No.11, October 1999, pp. 51-52.
18. S.G. Phadhis, "NPA Management Experience of Co-operative Banks", *Urban Credit*, March 1999, p. 29.
19. Reserve Bank of India, *The Report of the Working Committee*, RBI, Bombay,1999.
20. Reserve Bank of India, "Some Aspects and Issues Relating to NPAs in Commercial Banks", *Reserve Bank of India Bulletin*, Vol.50, No.3, July 1999, pp. 913-936.
21. Klingebiel and Daniela, "The Use of Asset Management Companies in the Resolution of Banking Crisis: Cross-Country Experiences", *Working Paper*, No.2284, under Domestic Finance, Saving Financial System, Stock Markets, World Bank, 2000.
22. K.G. Selvan and Samwel Kakuko Lopoyetum, "A Study on Non-performing Assets Management in Dharmapuri Town Co-operative Bank – A Case Study", *Co-operative Perspective*, Vol.34, No.4, January-March 2000, pp.45-55.
23. Katuri Nageswara Rao, "NPAs Ground Realities", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol.V, Issue VIII - April 2000, pp. 43-46.

24. Sanjay Kumar, "NPAs in Regional Rural Banks: Impact and Management", *The Management Accountant*, Vol.35, No.11, November 2000, pp. 855-858.
25. K. Satyanarayana and Ganti Subrahmanyam, "Anatomy of NPAs of Commercial Banks", *The ICAI Journal of Applied Finance*, Vol.6, No.3, July 2000, pp. 14-26.
26. G. Caprio Jr. and D. Klingebiel, "Bank Insolvency Bad Luck, Bad Policy or Bad Banking?", Annual World Bank Conference on Development Economics 1996, *Policy Research Working Paper*, 1620, World Bank, 1996.
27. P. Ganesan, "Determinants of Profit and Profitability of Public Sector Banks in India: A Profit Function Approach", *Journal of Financial Management and Analysis*, Vol.14, No.1, 2001, pp. 27-37.
28. Westgaard, Sjur and Nicovan der wijst, *Default Probabilities in a Corporate Bank Portfolio: A Logistic Model Approach*, Elsevier, 2001.
29. V.S. Kaveri, "Prevention of NPAs – Suggested Strategies", *IBA Bulletin*, Vol. XXIII, No.8, August 2001, pp. 7-9.
30. Indira Rajaraman and Garima Vasistha, "Non-Performing Loans of PSU Banks", *Economic and Political Weekly*, February 2, 2002.
31. H. Srinivas Rao, *Working of the Andhra Pradesh State Co-operative Bank – An Evaluation*, Ph.D. Thesis, Osmania University, Hyderabad in May 2002, Andhra Pradesh, India.
32. Monica Soni, "NPA Management by Rural Banks: A Critical Appraisal", *Indian Journal of Accounting*, Vol.XXXIII, December 2002, pp.67-71.
33. D. Satish, "The Securitization Bill 2002 will it Perform?", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol. VIII, Issue 9, September 2002, pp.16-18.
34. Reserve Bank of India, Tarapore Committee, *The Report of the Committee on Capital Account Convertibility* RBI Bombay.

35. B. Samal, "The NPA Overhang: Magnitude, Solution and Legal Reforms", *Vinimaya*, Vol.23, No.2, October-December 2002, pp.12-17.
36. Sardar Narinder Sing Gujral, "The NPA Problem Miles to Go", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol. IX, Issue 3, March 2003, pp. 73-78.
37. Santi Gopal Maji and Soma Dey, "Management of NPAs in UCB: A Case Study of the Khatra People's Co-operative Bank Ltd", *The Management Account*, Vol.38, No.3, March 2003, p.195.
38. P. Srinivas Subbarao, "Is Securitisation Ordinance Minimising NPAs or is Improving the Profits of PSBs by Reducing NPAs", *The Management Account*, Vol.38, No. 3, March 2003, pp.208-210.
39. R. Singh, "Profitability Management in Banks under Deregulated Environment", *IBA Bulletin*, Vol.XXV, No.7, July 2003, pp. 19-26.
40. A. Das and S. Ghosh, "Determination of Credit Risk", Paper presented at the Conference of *Money, Risk and Investments* held at Nottingham Trent University in November, 2003.
41. Arun Yeole, "The Problem of NPAs", *Yojana*, Vol.48, November 2004, pp. 35-38.
42. D.K. Chellani and Rita Rai, "The Performance of District Central Co-operative Banks in Gujarat", *Indian Co-operative Review*, Vol.41, No.4, April 2004, pp. 289-296.
43. K. Rajendran, "Non-Performing Assets", *Tamil Nadu Journal of Co-operation*, Vol.4, No.4, February 2004, pp.14-20.
44. Carlton Pereira, "Investing in NPAs will Investors Bite?", *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. XXXIX, No.42, October 16, 2004, pp. 4602-4604.
45. Sanjai Singh Rathore and Alka Singh, "Non-Performing Assets and Capital Adequacy", *Indian Journal of Accounting*, Vol.XXXV, No.1, December 2004, pp.78-81.
46. Meena Sharma, "Problem of NPAs and Its Impact on Strategic Banking Variables", *Finance India*, Vol.XIX, No.3, September 2005, pp.953-967.

47. Rajendra Singh, "Empowering Banks for Recovery of NPAs", *The Journal of Indian Institute of Banking & Finance*, January-March 2005, pp.5-13.
48. K.C. Chakraborty, "Management of NPAs Trends and Challenges", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, October 2005, pp. 30-33.
49. Justin Nelson Michael, *A Study on Non-Performing Assets in Co-operative Banks with Reference to Cuddalore District Central Co-operative Bank Ltd., Tamilnadu*, Ph.D. thesis submitted to Annamalai University, Chidambaram, May 2005.
50. N. Ganesan, "A Study on the Performance Analysis of the State Co-operative Banks in India", *Prajnan*, Vol.XXXIV, No.4, 2005-06, pp.311-321.
51. S. Khasnobis, "NPAs: Emerging Challenges", *The Indian Banker*, Vol. I, No.11, November 2006, pp.17-20.
52. T. Vanniarajan, "Correlates of NPAs and Performance of Banks", *Indian Journal of Accounting*, Vol.XXXVI, No.2, June 2006, pp.72-77.
53. R.K. Uppal and Rimpi Kaur, "Banking Sector Reform: Rational, Efficacy and Agenda for Third Reforms", *Indian Journal of Marketing*, Vol.XXXVII, No.6, June 2007, pp.12-22.
54. Gourav Vallabh, Anoop Bhatia and Saurabh Mishra, "Non-Performing Assets of Indian Public, Private and Foreign Sector Banks" An Empirical Assessment", *The ICAI Journal of Bank Management*, Vol.VI, No.3, August 2007, pp.7-28.
55. C. Lakshmanan and A. Dharmendran, "Impact of NPAs on the Performance Variables in Chennai Central Co-operative Bank", *Indian Co-operative Review*, Vol.44, No.4, April 2007, pp. 291-297.
56. *Annual Report*, The Tamilnadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Ltd., Chennai, 2003-2004, pp.125-129.
57. *Reserve Bank of India Bulletin*, Supplement to Annual Report 1991-92, RBI, Bombay, October 1992, p.117.

58. NABARD, Prudential Norms on Income Recognition Asset Classification and Provisioning – SCBs and DCCBs, *Master Circular*, No.193/Dos-21/2002, 17th August 2002.
59. Manual on Deposits, The Tamilnadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Limited, Chennai, January 1997, p.A.7.
60. *Ibid.*
61. K.K. Ammannaya, “Banking Reforms and New Challenges for Banks”, *Southern Economist*, 15th July 1997, p.4.
62. The National Federation of State Co-operative Bank Limited Publication, “Concept and Computation of Prime Lending Rate”, *The Co-operator*, Vol.XXXVII, No.3, September 1999, p.109.
63. B. Chinnappa and Keshava Reddy, “An Empirical Analysis of Growth and Instability in Sugar Industry”, *Agricultural Bankers*, Vol.23, No.2, April-June 1999, pp.27-32.
64. G.M. Hiremath, K.N.R. Sastry and A.D. Naik, “Deteriorating Potentiality of Tank Irrigation in Karnataka”, *Agricultural Bankers*, Vol.22, No.4, October-December, 1998, pp. 36-40.
65. C. Lakshmanan and A. Dharmendran, *op.cit.*, pp291-297
66. T. Vanniarajan, *op.cit.*, pp. 72-77.
67. Fed N. Kerlinger, *Methods of Factor Analysis: Foundations of Behavioural Research*, New York: Holt Reinhart and Winston Inc., 1973, p.470.
68. John Neter, William Wasserman and G.A. Whitmore, *Applied Statistics*, Quoted in Library of Congress Cataloging Publications, Second Edition, p.739.

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CHAPTER III

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF DCC BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

3.1. INTRODUCTION

A Co-operative Bank has been defined by Divideas as “a mutual society formed, composed and governed by working people themselves for encouraging regular savings and granting small loans on liberal terms of rate of interest and repayment”.¹ A co-operative bank must be essentially co-operative in character and must deal in credit which satisfies the requirements of an ideal credit.

Co-operative banks, like commercial banks, are involved in activities such as receiving deposits, lending money, transfer of money, etc. They have a network of branches in urban and rural areas and mainly cater to the needs of middle and poor classes of society. They assist agriculture and small industries, which are the backbone of Indian economy.

By the end of the Nineteenth century the condition of rural masses in India was quite deplorable. The countryside was studded with the problem of poverty, ignorance, and ancestral debt. The outcome of all these factors resulted in rural indebtedness. With a view to save the peasants from the clutches of money-lenders, provincial governments enacted several legislations such as the Deccan Agriculture Relief Act (1879), the Land Improvement Loan Act (1883) and the

Agriculturist Loan Act 1884. These measures could not relieve the burden of the peasants due to stringent and cumbersome official procedures. Later on, after a series of measures on the recommendation of Committees, the First Co-operative Societies Act (1904) came into existence.²

The passage of this act was the first milestone in the co-operative movement in India. It aimed at encouraging thrift habits among poor peasants and artisans by setting up Co-operative Societies which were classified as 'rural' and 'urban'. The Act of 1904 was amended in 1912 to facilitate the establishment of Central Co-operative Banks at the district level, thereby giving it a three tier federal character. After the independence of the country, in the recommendation of the A.D Gorwala Committee (1954) one Central Co-operative Bank for each district became a dictum, particularly in the bigger states. The main purpose was to provide stability and facilitate the emergence of a strong and powerful co-operative credit structure for the development of all co-operative activities at the district level. The establishment of District Central Co-operative Bank (DCCB) at the district level was to serve as a link between the ultimate credit disbursing outlets, viz., Primary Agricultural Co-operative Credit Societies (PACS) at the village level and State Co-operative Banks (SCB/Apex Bank) at the state level.³

3.1.1. Origin and Growth of DCC Banks in India

Even before the enactment of the Co-operative Societies Act, 1912, the Madras Central Urban Bank was established on September 19, 1905. “In Bombay the Bombay Central Co-operative Bank was started in the year 1906”.⁴ The objects of these two banks were to find money for financing the societies in all parts of the presidencies. “In 1906, another Central Co-operative Bank was formed at Bargarh in the Banda District of Uttar Pradesh state.”⁵

The period from 1906 to 1918 witnessed the beginning and spread of the Central Co-operative Banks in various parts of the country. During the period from 1919 to 1930, the number of Central Co-operative Banks increased from 233 to 588. This period was roughly between the end of the First World War and the beginning of the world depression which required more financial assistance to agriculturists in India.

The period of depression between 1929-30 and 1936-37 adversely affected the working of the Central Co-operative Banks by a steep increase in the overdues. Even during this period, the number of Central Co-operative Banks increased to 611. This was due to the formation of new Central Co-operative Banks in the states of Uttar Pradesh and Bihar.⁶

3.1.2. Origin and Growth of DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu

Even though there was no provision to start a Central Co-operative Bank in the Co-operative Credit Societies Act of 1904, the Madras Central Urban Co-operative Bank was registered in October 1905 to finance the co-operatives throughout the Presidency.⁷

In 1909, the Salem District Central Co-operative Bank was registered. Before the end of 1910 another Central Co-operative Bank at Coimbatore was formed. After the enactment of the Co-operative Societies Act, 1912, more Central Co-operative Banks were registered in Tamil Nadu.

Ordinarily it was that there should be only one Central Co-operative Bank for each district in order that the working of the bank may be economical. However, if two or more Central Co-operative Banks already existed in the same district, they should not be disturbed provided they had approached or attained viability.⁸ In Tamil Nadu, there are 23 Central Co-operative Banks. Due to bifurcation of districts in recent years the area of operation of five Central Co-operative Banks extends to more than a district.

Among the DCC banks in Tamil Nadu there were 12 largest and oldest Central Co-operative Banks. The banks have rendered more than 75 years of

commendable service to the people of both rural and urban areas in Tamilnadu state.

3.2. GROWTH AND PERFORMANCE OF DCC BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

The District Central Co-operative Banks have 722 Branches spread over 31 district in Tamilnadu state. The trend and growth rate in the Memberships, Branches, Share Capital, Reserves, Deposits, Borrowings, Loans and Advances Outstanding, Investments, Working capital, Net Profit and Overdues is an indication of the financial performance of the DCC Banks. This has been analysed district-wise during the study period by using the annual and compound growth rate.

3.2.1. Growth of Membership

The membership of the DCCBs generally consists of Primary Societies registered within the area of operation of the banks and individuals. The desirability of individual membership has been a subject of debate among experts. The Maclagan Committee favoured central banks of the pure type without individual membership while the Central Banking Enquiry Committee did not recommend the exclusion of individual members. The Madras Committee recommended the elimination of individual shareholders from the constitution of central banks. The Rural Credit Survey Committee approved the admission of

individual agriculturists as members as a purely transitional arrangement pending the establishment of co-operative societies in the area concerned. The Mehta Committee on Co-operative Credit did not recommend any 'special attempts' for enrolling more individual members. The latest trend is to have only a small number of individual members along with primary societies in the central co-operative banks⁹

The growth rate of memberships of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu has been analysed with the help of the annual and compound growth rates. The annual growth rate is measured by the linear equation whereas the compound growth rate is drawn from the exponential function. The computed annual and compound growth rates of membership in the 23 DCCBs from 1998-99 to 2004-05 are shown in Table 3.1.

TABLE 3.1
TREND AND GROWTH OF MEMBERSHIPS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	526.71	-1.36*	0.7428	14.44*	-0.26
2.	Coimbatore	1010.86	9.25*	0.6101	7.88*	0.89
3.	Cuddalore	561.57	0.57*	0.7111	12.31*	0.10
4.	Dharmapuri	547.29	6.21*	0.8589	30.45*	1.10
5.	Dindigul	616.43	0.29*	0.6154	8.00*	0.05
6.	Erode	1393.71	-13.18	0.3981	3.31	-1.01
7.	Kancheepuram	774.00	0.14	0.0047	0.024	0.02
8.	Kanyakumari	522.00	-1.07*	0.7759	17.31*	-0.21
9.	Kumbakonam	576.29	2.39*	0.9065	48.48*	0.41
10.	Madurai	970.29	-8.18	0.3382	2.56	-0.85
11.	Nilgiris	293.86	0.86*	0.8781	36.00*	0.29
12.	Pudukkottai	258.00	-1.36*	0.7849	18.23*	-0.54
13.	Ramanathapuram	438.29	1.96*	0.7894	18.74*	0.44
14.	Salem	1956.86	2.00	0.3851	3.13	0.10
15.	Sivagangai	365.29	-0.50	0.1008	0.56	-0.14
16.	Thanjavur	489.57	0.79*	0.8897	40.33*	0.16
17.	Thiruchirapalli	976.29	3.36*	0.6029	7.59*	0.34
18.	Tirunelveli	834.29	3.68*	0.9064	48.44*	0.44
19.	Tiruvannamalai	436.71	32.00	0.4346	3.84	5.11
20.	Thoothukudi	580.00	-0.11	0.0865	0.47	-0.02
21.	Vellore	669.00	-3.71	0.1482	0.87	-0.58
22.	Villupuram	700.00	2.43*	0.7458	14.67*	0.34
23.	Virudhunagar	539.14	-6.96*	0.9422	81.42*	-1.35

* Significant at five per cent level.

The annual growth rates of memberships in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu are positive in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kancheepuram, Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Ramanathapuram, Salem, Thanjavur. Thiruchirapalli, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai and Villupuram banks with trend coefficients of

9.25, 0.57, 6.21, 0.29, 0.14, 2.39, 0.86, 1.96, 2.00, 0.79, 3.36, 3.68 32.00 and 2.46 respectively during the period of study. The growth rates are significant at the five per cent level except in the case of the Kancheepuram, Salem and Tiruvannamalai banks where it is statistically insignificant. The fitted regression model for the case is also insignificant since its F value is 0.024, 3.13 and 3.84 respectively. The co-efficient of determination in the various trend equations reflects a maximum of 0.9422. It shows that the independent variable “time” explains the dependent variable of membership only to the maximum extent of 94.22 per cent. Negative annual growth rates are noticed in the Chennai, Erode, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Sivagangai, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks with -1.36, -13.18, -1.07, -8.18, -1.36, -0.50, -0.11, -3.17, -6.96 respectively.

The compound growth rates are negative for these nine banks with compound growth rates of -0.26, -1.01, -0.21, -0.85, -0.54, -0.14, -0.02, -0.58 and -1.35 respectively. In the other 14 banks positive compound growth rates have been witnessed.

3.2.2. Growth of Branches

The action programme prepared in 1964 by the Ministry of Food and Agriculture suggested that every DCC Bank should open branches at the Taluk head quarters and if possible in smaller towns also.¹⁰ The All India Rural Credit

Survey Committee has stated that a co-operative financing agency should have branches at some intermediate level between the village and the district headquarters, such branches being sought to be established at least at sub-divisional centres to start with and thereafter at other suitable places.¹¹ The purpose of opening branches at sub-divisional levels is two fold: to mobilise more deposits and to render effective services to member societies at proximate points. It would be economical for member societies to deal with the nearest branch of the DCCB in drawing loans and making remittances. Accordingly a number of branches were established in various places. Table 3.2 presents the trend and growth of branches of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

TABLE 3.2
TREND AND GROWTH OF BRANCHES IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		A	B			
1.	Chennai	60.14	0.39*	0.7961	19.52*	0.64
2.	Coimbatore	22.00	0.61*	0.8811	37.05*	2.49
3.	Cuddalore	-	-	-	-	-
4.	Dharmapuri	36.00	0.64*	0.8438	27.00*	1.68
5.	Dindigul	25.86	0.57*	0.6154	8.00*	2.12
6.	Erode	32.86	-0.61*	0.8811	37.05*	-1.98
7.	Kancheepuram	42.86	0.43*	0.6667	10.00*	0.97
8.	Kanyakumari	13.43	0.54*	0.8272	23.94*	3.54
9.	Kumbakonam	33.14	-0.71	0.1667	1.00	-0.22
10.	Madurai	-	-	-	-	--
11.	Nilgiris	18.57	-0.93	0.5633	6.45	-6.67
12.	Pudukkottai	-	-	-	-	-
13.	Ramanathapuram	25.29	0.11	0.2250	1.45	0.42
14.	Salem	61.57	-0.18	0.0530	0.28	-0.30
15.	Sivagangai	28.86	-0.07	0.0833	0.45	-0.25
16.	Thanjavur	-	-	-	-	-
17.	Thiruchirapalli	48.71	1.36*	0.8474	27.77*	2.55
18.	Tirunelveli	26.43	-0.11	0.0402	0.21	-0.44
19.	Tiruvannamalai	28.00	-0.39	0.5602	6.37	-1.52
20.	Thoothukudi	14.43	0.43*	0.7500	15.00	2.72
21.	Vellore	35.43	-0.18*	0.6250	8.33*	-0.52
22.	Villupuram	21.29	-0.11	0.3750	3.00	-0.52
23.	Virudhunagar	33.29	-0.36	0.3290	2.45	-1.15

* Significant at five per cent level.

It is seen from Table 3.2 that the annual growth rates of branches in the DCC banks in Tamilnadu are positive in the Chennai, Coimbatore, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Ramanathapuram, Thiruchirapalli and Thoothukudi banks with 0.39 times, 0.61 times, 0.64 times, 0.57 times, 0.43 times, 0.54 times, 0.11 times, 1.36 times, and 0.43 times respectively. The fitted regression models are also significant in all these banks except in the Ramanathapuram bank. Negative annual growth rates were noticed in the Erode,

Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Salem, Sivagangai, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore Villupuram and Virudhunagar banks with trend coefficients of -0.61 , -0.71 , -0.93 , -0.18 , -0.07 , -0.11 , -0.39 , -0.18 , -0.11 and -0.36 respectively and they were significant at the five per cent level at the Erode and Vellore banks. In the Cuddalore, Madurai, Pudukkottai and Thanjavur banks, the annual growth rate was very negligible and hence it is left out of the analysis. The compound growth rates were negative in the Erode, Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Salem, Sivagangai, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore, Villupuram, and Virudhunagar banks with compound growth rates of -1.98 , -0.22 , -6.67 , -0.30 , -0.25 , -0.44 , -0.52 , -0.52 and -1.15 respectively, whereas in all the other banks positive compound growth rates have been recorded.

3.2.3 Growth of Share Capital

The share capital in the DCCB is contributed by individual members, affiliated societies and the Government of Tamilnadu. Generally the Government of Tamilnadu contributes a lump sum to all the DCC Banks in Tamilnadu to encourage the co-operative system. Table 3.3 shows the growth rates regarding the total paid up share capital of the DCC banks during the study period.

TABLE 3.3
TREND AND GROWTH OF TOTAL PAID UP SHARE CAPITAL IN DCC
BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	28.43	10.84*	0.9527	100.63*	17.95
2.	Coimbatore	12.16	1.39*	0.7140	12.48*	8.56
3.	Cuddalore	5.93	1.51*	0.9583	114.96*	13.37
4.	Dharmapuri	14.66	2.71*	0.9074	49.00*	11.35
5.	Dindigul	6.75	0.91*	0.9932	731.87*	9.26
6.	Erode	9.60	0.96*	0.9723	175.61*	7.40
7.	Kancheepuram	10.71	2.52*	0.9609	122.81*	13.69
8.	Kanyakumari	6.56	0.69*	0.9808	254.95*	7.87
9.	Kumbakonam	10.69	0.72*	0.9577	113.18*	5.41
10.	Madurai	11.19	0.91*	0.9165	54.88*	6.59
11.	Nilgiris	2.99	0.72*	0.6373	8.79*	13.27
12.	Pudukkottai	6.82	0.53*	0.9740	187.31*	6.10
13.	Ramanathapuram	5.93	0.35*	0.9277	64.13*	4.85
14.	Salem	12.53	1.35*	0.8692	33.23*	7.55
15.	Sivagangai	6.23	0.89*	0.9507	96.45*	10.02
16.	Thanjavur	9.24	0.88*	0.9696	159.41*	7.21
17.	Thiruchirapalli	9.55	1.47*	0.9388	76.63*	9.80
18.	Tirunelveli	5.76	0.55*	0.9403	78.81*	7.26
19.	Tiruvannamalai	10.60	1.39*	0.9134	52.73*	9.09
20.	Thoothukudi	6.12	0.13*	0.8177	22.42*	2.04
21.	Vellore	6.43	1.13*	0.9454	86.64*	10.83
22.	Villupuram	8.58	1.70*	0.9480	91.12*	11.55
23.	Virudhunagar	6.58	0.37*	0.9672	147.63*	4.68

* Significant at five per cent level.

It is understood from Table 3.3 that the annual growth rates of the total share capital in the DCC Banks in Tamilnadu are positive in all the banks and they are statistically significant at the five per cent level. The fitted regression models are also significant in all the banks. The co-efficient of determination in various trend equations the Dindigul bank has reached a maximum of 0.9932. It

shows that the independent variable time explains the dependent variable of share capital to the maximum extent of 99.32 per cent in the Dindigul bank.

The compound growth rates of share capital in all banks in Tamilnadu are positive. The total share capital picture shows that there is an increased trend in all the banks in Tamil Nadu state.

3.2.4 Growth of Reserves

The DCC banks maintain three kinds of reserves: (i) statutory reserves, (ii) bad debt reserves and (iii) other reserves. In view of the liberalised policy of the government, the DCC banks provided lavish credit facilities to the affiliated societies. The importance of the reserves has increased over the years. More reserves mean more credits for banks. At the time of profit distribution, the money allocated for reserves makes the financial position of the bank sound. The reserves are created out of profits according to the provisions of the Reserve Bank of India and are invested as per the guidelines and they become the reserve fund. Table 3.4 shows the trend and growth of total reserve in all the DCCBs during the study period.

TABLE 3.4
TREND AND GROWTH OF RESERVES IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	B			
1.	Chennai	73.78	23.13*	0.9666	144.48*	15.16
2.	Coimbatore	16.06	3.63	0.2049	1.29	4.64
3.	Cuddalore	8.65	1.87	0.1909	1.18	3.94
4.	Dharmapuri	-8.62	11.62*	0.9187	56.47*	41.54
5.	Dindigul	-8.21	10.47*	0.8259	23.72*	36.87
6.	Erode	2.13	4.48*	0.9306	67.05*	25.65
7.	Kancheepuram	7.47	11.97*	0.9549	105.83*	27.72
8.	Kanyakumari	6.02	1.81*	0.9241	60.86*	15.13
9.	Kumbakonam	11.29	6.83	0.5520	6.16	20.01
10.	Madurai	7.29	12.42*	0.8256	23.67*	28.61
11.	Nilgiris	1.98	2.21*	0.6514	9.34*	22.92
12.	Pudukkottai	1.83	3.35*	0.9344	71.21*	26.13
13.	Ramanathapuram	7.14	6.50*	0.8554	29.57*	23.39
14.	Salem	8.41	9.99*	0.8788	36.24*	22.17
15.	Sivagangai	5.55	6.16*	0.6845	10.85*	26.31
16.	Thanjavur	9.37	2.80	0.1799	1.10	7.18
17.	Thiruchirapalli	14.93	12.59*	0.9373	74.76*	23.78
18.	Tirunelveli	-7.29	7.65*	0.6769	10.47*	47.82
19.	Tiruvannamalai	7.63	5.59*	0.8737	34.59*	19.95
20.	Thoothukudi	1.84	6.22	0.3228	2.38	9.13
21.	Vellore	3.20	3.41*	0.9670	146.57*	24.85
22.	Villupuram	11.36	7.03*	0.9385	76.29*	19.93
23.	Virudhunagar	3.71	3.83*	0.7765	17.37*	25.31

* Significant at five per cent level.

It is evident from Table 3.4 that the annual growth rates of total reserves in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu show a positive growth. It was statistically significant at the five per cent level in all the banks except in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Kumbakonam, Thanjavur and Thoothukudi banks. It indicates that there is a decline in the amount of reserves during the study period whereas the fitted regression equation in these cases are insignificant since the F values are

only 1.29, 1.18, 6.16, 1.10, and 2.38 respectively. The co-efficient of determination in the Vellore bank was the highest of 96.70 per cent while the lowest of 17.99 per cent was found in the Thanjavur bank. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks with the highest of 47.82 percent recorded in the Tirunelveli and the lowest of 3.94 per cent in the Cuddalore bank.

3.2.5 Growth of Deposits

The Central Co-operative Banks accept various kinds of deposits from individuals, co-operatives and other institutions. The reserve funds and surplus funds of the Co-operative Societies are deposited with the concerned central co-operative banks. Voluntary agencies like local bodies, societies incorporated under the Societies Registration Act, Universities and Technical Institutions, Government Corporations, Companies wholly owned by the Government, Religious and Charitable Institutions, Educational Institutions, Court, Electricity Board, Regulated Markets etc. have been directed by the State Government to keep their funds with the Central Co-operative Bank.¹² Table 3.5 shows the trend and growth rates of deposits over the study period.

TABLE 3.5
TREND AND GROWTH OF DEPOSITS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	577.66	87.87*	0.9207	58.03*	10.73
2.	Coimbatore	295.58	11.01*	0.6319	8.58*	3.47
3.	Cuddalore	90.81	43.68*	0.6977	11.54*	37.00
4.	Dharmapuri	196.36	11.36*	0.6247	8.32*	5.27
5.	Dindigul	179.02	10.84*	0.8164	22.24*	5.21
6.	Erode	262.69	10.88*	0.7056	11.98*	3.78
7.	Kancheepuram	271.69	12.70*	0.5899	7.19*	4.22
8.	Kanyakumari	76.38	13.78*	0.7826	18.00*	11.86
9.	Kumbakonam	214.41	8.26	0.4029	3.37	3.65
10.	Madurai	382.56	1.56	0.0045	0.023	0.51
11.	Nilgiris	90.73	1.25	0.0924	0.51	1.45
12.	Pudukkottai	107.17	10.07*	0.8363	25.55*	7.49
13.	Ramanathapuram	121.98	9.12*	0.8497	28.27*	6.23
14.	Salem	650.28	30.13	0.5174	5.36	4.29
15.	Sivagangai	119.05	6.77	0.4186	3.60	5.32
16.	Thanjavur	119.82	4.51*	0.5849	7.05*	3.54
17.	Thiruchirapalli	338.11	20.84*	0.8395	26.14*	5.28
18.	Tirunelveli	190.71	-0.94	0.0094	0.05	-0.38
19.	Tiruvannamalai	101.40	13.98*	0.9256	62.18*	9.95
20.	Thoothukudi	126.47	1.04	0.0283	0.15	0.87
21.	Vellore	215.87	12.39*	0.7425	14.42*	5.09
22.	Villupuram	151.25	26.07*	0.9341	70.84*	11.73
23.	Virudhunagar	178.54	8.74*	0.6655	9.95*	4.38

* Significant at five per cent level.

It could be seen from Table 3.5 that the annual growth rate of deposits in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu is positive in all the banks except in the Tirunelveli bank where the annual growth rate was -0.94 times while is statistically insignificant. It indicates that there is a decline in the amount of deposit in this bank during the study period but the decline is not statistically

significant. The fitted regression model for the case is also insignificant since its F value is 0.05. The co-efficient of determination in the case indicates that the change in the amount of deposits is only to the extent of 0.94 per cent. Insignificant annual growth rates are seen in the Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Salem, Sivagangai and Thoothukudi banks with 8.26, 1.56, 1.25, 30.13, 6.77 and 1.04 times respectively. The fitted trend equations in these cases are insignificant at the five per cent level since the F values are 3.37, 0.023, 0.51, 5.36, 3.60 and 0.15 respectively. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Tirunelveli bank which has a negative growth rate of -0.38 per cent.

3.2.6 Growth of Borrowings

The District Central Co-operative Banks also borrow from the State Co-operative Banks, the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) through the State Co-operative Bank, the State Bank of India and the State Government. The NABARD grants financial accommodations at a concessional rate of interest. The maximum borrowing power of a Central Co-operative Bank is fixed at 15 times the paid up share capital plus its reserve fund.¹³ Table 3.6 shows the trend and growth rates of the total borrowings by the banks.

TABLE 3.6
TREND AND GROWTH OF BORROWINGS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	-5.10	4.76	0.4592	4.24	73.69
2.	Coimbatore	6.22	12.84*	0.7475	14.80*	25.08
3.	Cuddalore	2.14	10.35*	0.8304	24.49*	27.32
4.	Dharmapuri	234.32	9.13	0.1257	0.7190	4.34
5.	Dindigul	-4.96	13.24*	0.8836	37.95*	32.15
6.	Erode	50.93	3.84	0.2752	1.90	5.90
7.	Kancheepuram	61.41	-0.86	0.0179	0.092	-1.54
8.	Kanyakumari	27.37	7.38	0.4345	3.84	14.37
9.	Kumbakonam	53.94	9.76*	0.6674	10.03*	10.68
10.	Madurai	5.70	15.35	0.4935	4.87	22.19
11.	Nilgiris	4.19	5.43*	0.9355	72.51*	23.57
12.	Pudukkottai	19.54	9.23*	0.8790	36.63*	17.20
13.	Ramanathapuram	5.90	6.10*	0.5849	7.05*	18.61
14.	Salem	27.21	20.46*	0.6715	10.22*	20.62
15.	Sivagangai	20.03	11.11*	0.8799	36.66*	18.55
16.	Thanjavur	51.38	10.91*	0.8631	31.53*	12.08
17.	Thiruchirapalli	-3.50	13.93*	0.8799	36.62*	31.66
18.	Tirunelveli	-10.57	10.52*	0.8463	27.53*	42.47
19.	Tiruvannamalai	61.94	6.79*	0.8939	42.11*	7.92
20.	Thoothukudi	2.25	2.33	0.5241	5.51	24.40
21.	Vellore	14.97	16.09*	0.7261	13.25*	28.32
22.	Villupuram	49.59	12.55*	0.5699	6.63*	12.09
23.	Virudhunagar	14.75	3.26*	0.7335	13.76*	11.64

* Significant at five per cent level.

Table 3.6 shows that the annual growth rates of borrowings in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu are positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram bank which recorded a negative growth rate of -0.86 times but the co-efficient is insignificant. It indicates that there is a decline in the amount of borrowings during the study period. The fitted regression model for trend equation in the

Kancheepuram bank is also insignificant since its F values is only 0.092. The co-efficient of determination shows that the change in the time variable explains the change in borrowings to the extent of only 1.79 per cent in the Kancheepuram bank. In all the other DCC banks the annual growth rates are statistically significant except in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Erode, Kanyakumari, Madurai and Thoothukudi banks with trend values of 4.76, 9.13, 3.84, 7.38, 15.35 and 2.33 respectively. The fitted trend equations in these cases are insignificant at the five per cent level with F values of 4.24, 0.719, 1.90, 3.84, 4.87 and 5.51 respectively. The compound growth rates are positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram bank with a negative record of -1.54 per cent.

3.2.7 Growth of Loans and Advances

The position of loans and advances in respect of short-term loans, cash credits and overdraft and bills purchased and discounted, medium-term loans conversion, rephasesments/recheduled loans and jewel loans to individuals are presented in Table 3.7 showing the trend and growth rates of the loans and advances during the study period.

TABLE 3.7
TREND AND GROWTH OF LOANS AND ADVANCES IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	294.40	96.66*	0.9535	102.45*	16.48
2.	Coimbatore	165.42	30.34*	0.9612	123.93*	11.98
3.	Cuddalore	118.97	33.16*	0.9791	234.62*	14.43
4.	Dharmapuri	386.40	24.92	0.4446	4.00	5.99
5.	Dindigul	129.16	26.74*	0.9944	892.36*	12.35
6.	Erode	153.05	20.66*	0.9856	341.73*	9.40
7.	Kancheepuram	242.76	23.26*	0.9350	71.86*	7.41
8.	Kanyakumari	90.82	19.71*	0.9424	81.81*	12.17
9.	Kumbakonam	215.92	14.89*	0.9040	47.10*	5.52
10.	Madurai	295.30	25.69*	0.9810	258.17*	6.69
11.	Nilgiris	57.96	8.73*	0.9179	55.86*	10.66
12.	Pudukkottai	100.17	20.69*	0.9821	274.48*	12.17
13.	Ramanathapuram	98.98	16.02*	0.9442	84.66*	10.20
14.	Salem	261.54	53.57*	0.9858	384.69*	12.19
15.	Sivagangai	118.44	15.76*	0.9727	178.37*	9.32
16.	Thanjavur	132.55	15.21*	0.9516	98.36*	8.13
17.	Thiruchirapalli	212.55	51.34*	0.9919	608.83*	13.67
18.	Tirunelveli	94.21	12.61*	0.8929	41.69*	9.49
19.	Tiruvannamalai	151.16	22.83*	0.9850	329.37*	9.99
20.	Thoothukudi	80.52	8.55*	0.8456	27.39*	8.04
21.	Vellore	146.04	36.92*	0.9427	82.23*	14.73
22.	Villupuram	211.98	32.09*	0.9163	54.75*	9.70
23.	Virudhunagar	97.63	14.97*	0.9483	91.76*	9.91

* Significant at five per cent level.

It could be seen from Table 3.7 that the annual growth rates of loans and advances outstanding in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu are positive in all the banks. The growth rates are statistically significant in all the banks except in the Dharmapuri bank. It indicates that there is an increase in the amount of loans and advances outstanding during the study period. The fitted regression model for the

trend equation in the Dharmapuri bank is insignificant since its F value is only 4.00. The co-efficients of determination in all the banks are higher than 0.90 except in the Dharmapuri, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks with 0.44, 0.89 and 0.84 times respectively which indicate that changes in loans and advances vary to the maximum extent of 99.44 per cent in the Dindigul bank. The compound growth rates are positive in all the banks with the highest of 16.48 per cent recorded in the Chennai and the lowest of 5.52 per cent found in Kumbakonam.

3.2.8 Growth of Investments

Investments are made by the DCC banks in various types of securities viz. Government Securities, debentures of land development banks, other trustee securities, fixed deposits with institutions other than banks. The DCC banks accept deposits and are, therefore, responsible for investing their funds in such a way as to safeguard the interest of the depositors. The same considerations of safety, liquidity and profitability in the employment of funds are essential as in the case of the other banks. It is therefore, highly desirable that the DCC banks should take all the necessary care and precaution while investing their funds. Table 3.8 shows the trend and growth rates of investment by the banks.

TABLE 3.8
TREND AND GROWTH OF INVESTMENTS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	369.94	33.99*	0.6504	9.30*	7.58
2.	Coimbatore	161.30	-0.05	0.00003	0.00016	-0.13
3.	Cuddalore	81.16	6.69	0.1146	0.65	7.17
4.	Dharmapuri	48.54	6.30*	0.7859	18.36*	10.16
5.	Dindigul	69.01	0.56	0.03417	0.177	0.99
6.	Erode	172.83	1.96	0.0535	0.28	1.25
7.	Kancheepuram	101.29	6.95	0.4564	4.20	6.11
8.	Kanyakumari	21.71	3.56*	0.8556	29.61*	11.61
9.	Kumbakonam	62.36	2.45	0.3719	2.96	3.80
10.	Madurai	111.42	1.66	0.0522	0.02752	1.67
11.	Nilgiris	21.42	1.27	0.0845	0.4615	11.86
12.	Pudukkottai	29.56	2.71*	0.6571	9.58*	7.68
13.	Ramanathapuram	33.41	2.29*	0.5797	6.89*	6.27
14.	Salem	428.18	13.48	0.0974	0.539	4.02
15.	Sivagangai	34.42	1.75	0.4027	3.37	4.76
16.	Thanjavur	35.21	1.34	0.4519	4.12	3.63
17.	Thiruchirapalli	149.76	-1.70	0.0484	0.254	-1.12
18.	Tirunelveli	77.19	-4.62	0.2859	2.00	-6.97
19.	Tiruvannamalai	27.56	5.05*	0.8527	28.94*	12.61
20.	Thoothukudi	56.91	-2.99	0.3736	2.98	-6.31
21.	Vellore	86.64	0.99	0.0859	0.469	1.13
22.	Villupuram	46.49	7.10	0.2380	1.56	8.54
23.	Virudhunagar	96.85	-2.48	0.0745	0.402	-2.80

* Significant at five per cent level.

The annual growth rate of total investments is analysed with the help of the simple linear equation. It shows that trend coefficients in the DCC banks in the Coimbatore, Thiruchirappalli, Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Virudhunagar in Tamil Nadu are negative with values of -0.05, -1.70, -4.62, -2.99 and -2.48 respectively. The annual growth rate in the above banks is statistically

insignificant. In all the other DCC banks, positive growth rates have been recorded and they were statistically significant at the five per cent level in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kanyakumari, Pudukkottai, Ramanathapuram and Tiruvannamalai banks with trend values of 33.99, 6.30, 3.56, 2.71, 2.29, and 5.05 respectively. The fitted regression under trend equation in these banks are also significant at the five per cent level since the F values are 9.30, 18.36, 29.61, 9.58, 6.89 and 28.94 respectively. There has been negative compound growth rates of investments in the Coimbatore, Thiruchirapalli, Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Virudhunagar banks with -0.13 , -1.12 , -6.97 , -6.31 and -2.80 per cent respectively whereas in all the other banks, positive compound growth rates are seen during the study period.

3.2.9 Growth of Working Capital

Working capital is defined as the difference between current assets and current liabilities. Working capital determines the liquidity position of the bank. The sources of working capital for Central Co-Operative Banks consist of the following. 1) Share capital, 2) reserves and other funds, 3) deposits from members and non-members 4) borrowing from: a) State Co-operative banks, b) the Reserve Bank of India, and c) the Government and 5) Government Grants.

Table 3.9 shows the trend and growth of working capital in the banks during the study period.

TABLE 3.9
TREND AND GROWTH OF WORKING CAPITAL IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	728.58	136.01*	0.9629	129.89*	12.02
2.	Coimbatore	349.12	22.75*	0.6619	9.79*	5.72
3.	Cuddalore	234.88	39.57*	0.9499	94.80*	10.80
4.	Dharmapuri	438.22	26.73	0.4738	4.50	5.75
5.	Dindigul	214.29	33.53*	0.9705	164.65*	10.36
6.	Erode	359.22	22.24*	0.8913	41.00*	5.26
7.	Kancheepuram	377.10	31.86*	0.8777	35.88*	6.85
8.	Kanyakumari	129.21	25.59*	0.9679	150.52*	11.71
9.	Kumbakonam	327.24	24.77*	0.8976	43.81*	6.14
10.	Madurai	428.29	35.35*	0.8367	25.61*	6.57
11.	Nilgiris	99.83	10.99*	0.8689	33.15*	8.45
12.	Pudukkottai	147.37	25.08*	0.9841	309.69*	11.02
13.	Ramanathapuram	136.19	27.80*	0.9084	49.58	12.19
14.	Salem	647.62	68.82*	0.9402	78.65*	8.00
15.	Sivagangai	218.73	13.38*	0.7371	14.02*	5.16
16.	Thanjavur	178.02	27.98*	0.7067	12.05*	9.74
17.	Thiruchirapalli	400.38	54.76*	0.9897	482.14*	9.55
18.	Tirunelveli	221.07	14.84*	0.6246	8.32*	5.81
19.	Tiruvannamalai	199.97	29.85*	0.9174	55.52*	10.23
20.	Thoothukudi	142.93	13.46*	0.6140	7.95*	7.13
21.	Vellore	245.40	39.98*	0.8928	41.65*	11.22
22.	Villupuram	279.32	43.90*	0.9699	160.82*	10.32
23.	Virudhunagar	216.67	18.01*	0.7993	19.92*	6.77

* Significant at five per cent level.

It is seen from Table 3.9 that the annual growth rates of working capital in DCC banks in Tamilnadu in all the banks were positive. The fitted regression models also prove significant growth rates in all the banks except in the Dharmapuri bank with 26.73 times. The co-efficient of determination in the trend equation of the Dharmapuri bank indicates that the changes in time variable

influences the changes in the amount of working capital to the extent of 47.38 per cent. The table also shows a positive compound growth rate in all the DCC banks during the study period with the highest of 12.19 per cent recorded in the Ramanathapuram and the lowest of 5.26 per cent found in the Erode bank.

3.2.10 Growth of Net Profit

The excess of assets over liabilities should be the same as the net profit balance in the profit and loss appropriation account. Similarly excess of liabilities over assets should be the same as the net loss balance in the profit and loss appropriation account.

Table 3.10 gives the net profit/loss position of the DCC banks under study over the study period.

TABLE 3.10
TREND AND GROWTH OF NET PROFIT IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	22.61	4.63*	0.7602	15.85*	12.90
2.	Coimbatore	-1.74	0.81	0.3712	2.95	--
3.	Cuddalore	-1.89	0.57	0.3623	2.84	--
4.	Dharmapuri	-12.23	0.56	0.0007	0.004	--
5.	Dindigul	-2.46	0.24	0.0016	0.008	--
6.	Erode	0.019	0.38*	0.9315	67.98*	31.49
7.	Kancheepuram	0.511	0.12	0.1948	1.21	10.03
8.	Kanyakumari	-1.50	0.63	0.4664	4.37	--
9.	Kumbakonam	-9.62	1.28	0.0236	0.1208	--
10.	Madurai	-4.53	0.59	0.0825	0.449	--
11.	Nilgiris	-2.98	1.08	0.4700	4.43	--
12.	Pudukkottai	-1.72	0.78	0.4530	4.14	--
13.	Ramanathapuram	-0.90	-1.77	0.0329	0.169	--
14.	Salem	2.73	0.32*	0.9460	87.61*	8.43
15.	Sivagangai	-13.00	2.92	0.2112	1.34	--
16.	Thanjavur	-16.96	4.24	0.2160	1.38	--
17.	Thiruchirapalli	-5.93	2.36	0.3628	2.85	--
18.	Tirunelveli	-0.969	-0.82	0.0097	0.049	--
19.	Tiruvannamalai	-6.31	2.06*	0.7841	18.16*	--
20.	Thoothukudi	-3.77	-0.61	0.0088	0.044	--
21.	Vellore	-2.27	0.95	0.3556	2.76	--
22.	Villupuram	2.29	0.11	0.0328	0.169	8.65
23.	Virudhunagar	-11.09	2.40	0.2765	1.91	--

* Significant at five per cent level.

The annual growth rate of net profit is analysed with the help of a simple linear equation. It shows that the growth rates of net profit in the DCC banks in Tamilnadu are negative in the Ramanathapuram, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks with -1.77 , -0.82 and -0.61 times respectively. It shows that the amount of net profit in these banks have declined during the study period. But the decline is

not statistically significant, whereas all the other banks show positive growth rates and the growth rates are significant at the five per cent level in the Chennai, Erode, Salem and Tiruvannamalai banks with 4.63, 0.38, 0.32 and 2.06 times respectively. The co-efficient of determination in various trend equations under the Salem bank is a maximum of 0.9460. It shows that the independent variable time explains the dependent variable of net profit only to the maximum extent of 94.60 per cent in the Salem bank. Positive compound growth rates were noticed in the Chennai, Erode, Kancheepuram, Salem and Villupuram banks with 12.90, 31.49, 10.03, 8.43 and 8.65 per cent respectively, whereas in all the other banks these were noticed in 0 per cent.

3.2.11 Growth of Overdue Position

Overdues have been a major problem at the primary society level as member cultivators of agricultural credit societies do not repay the loans taken from the societies on the due date owing to various reasons such as diversion of funds, crop failures, etc. Primary societies in turn fail to promptly repay their loans to the Central Co-operative Banks, causing heavy overdues. The trend and growth of the overdue position is presented in Table 3.11

TABLE 3.11
TREND AND GROWTH OF OVERDUES IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Coefficients		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	8.49	0.91*	0.6211	8.19*	7.60
2.	Coimbatore	16.59	9.34	0.3669	2.90	19.45
3.	Cuddalore	8.61	4.55	0.2892	2.03	16.38
4.	Dharmapuri	-18.89	29.72	0.3336	2.50	91.22
5.	Dindigul	23.33	4.28	0.3230	2.39	10.06
6.	Erode	-0.80	8.36	0.2999	2.14	39.25
7.	Kancheepuram	24.72	7.62*	0.8306	24.52*	16.29
8.	Kanyakumari	9.98	0.63	0.0708	0.38	6.89
9.	Kumbakonam	46.08	3.58	0.0905	0.49	3.26
10.	Madurai	32.23	4.76	0.4356	3.86	9.70
11.	Nilgiris	28.93	-0.76	0.0292	0.15	-1.58
12.	Pudukkottai	33.07	3.12	0.1074	0.60	4.29
13.	Ramanathapuram	23.38	4.04*	0.7486	14.89*	10.18
14.	Salem	3.34	8.21*	0.7399	14.23*	29.15
15.	Sivagangai	38.92	-0.11	0.0003	0.0013	-2.97
16.	Thanjavur	62.32	-0.17	0.0004	0.0019	-2.19
17.	Thiruchirapalli	8.35	6.92*	0.7017	11.76*	24.05
18.	Tirunelveli	13.63	0.24	0.0633	0.34	1.39
19.	Tiruvannamalai	40.81	2.06	0.1982	1.23	4.75
20.	Thoothukudi	10.83	0.52	0.1224	0.70	3.56
21.	Vellore	-5.05	11.64	0.4842	4.69	36.14
22.	Villupuram	24.07	3.25	0.5525	6.17	9.33
23.	Virudhunagar	18.58	-0.30	0.0262	0.13	-3.34

* Significant at five per cent level.

It is understood from Table 3.11 that overdues of the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu show negative annual growth rates in the Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur and Virudhunagar banks with -0.76, -0.11, -0.17 and -0.30 times respectively. It shows that the overdues in the above banks have declined during the study period. But the decline is not statistically significant. There are positive annual growth

rates in all the other banks but they are statistically significant at the five per cent level only in the Chennai, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Ramanathapuram, Salem and Thiruchirapalli banks with 0.91, 7.62, 4.04, 8.21 and 6.92 times respectively. The fitted regressions under trend equations in the above cases are also significant at the five per cent level since the F values are 8.19, 24.52, 14.89, 14.23 and 11.76 respectively. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur and Virudhunagar banks where there are negative compound growth rates of -1.58, -2.97, -2.19 and -3.34 per cent respectively. This speaks of the acute problem of overdues in a majority of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

3.3. CONCLUSION

The annual growth rates of memberships were negative in the Chennai, Erode, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Sivagangai, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks whereas in all the other banks positive annual growth rates were noticed. The compound growth was higher at 5.11 per cent in the Tiruvannamalai bank.

The annual growth rates of branches in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed negative annual growth rates in the Erode, Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Salem, Sivagangai, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore, Villupuram and Virudhunagar banks whereas in all the other banks positive annual growth rates were noticed.

The growth rates varied from 3.54 per cent in the Kanyakumari bank to –6.67 per cent in Nilgiris bank.

The annual growth rates of the total share capital in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive in all the banks and they were statistically significant at the five per cent level. Positive compound growth rates were noticed in all the banks.

The annual growth rates of the total reserves in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive in all the banks. Insignificant annual growth rates were noticed in Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Kumbakonam, Thanjavur and Thoothukudi banks. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks.

The annual growth rates of deposits in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive in all the banks except in the Tirunelveli bank where the annual growth rate was –0.94 times. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Tirunelveli bank with –0.38 per cent.

The annual growth rates of the borrowings in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram bank. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram bank with a negative growth rate of –1.54 per cent.

The annual growth rates of loans and advances in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive and significant in all the banks except in the Dharmapuri bank. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks.

The investments of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed a negative and insignificant growth rates in the Coimbatore, Thiruchirappalli, Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Virudhunagar banks. In all the other banks there were positive growth rates and it was significant in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kanyakumari, Pudukkottai, Ramanathapuram and Tiruvannamalai banks. The compound growth rates varied between 12.61 per cent in the Tiruvannamalai bank and -6.97 per cent in the Tirunelveli bank.

The annual growth rates of the working capital in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive. But the growth rates were significant in all the banks except in the Dharmapuri bank. The results were positive with regard to compound growth rates in all the banks during the study period.

The growth rates of the net profit in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were negative and insignificant in the Ramanathapuram, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks, while all the other banks showed positive growth rates and the growth rates were significant in the Chennai, Erode, Salem and Tiruvannamalai banks.

The growth rates of overdues of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were negative and insignificant in the Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur and Virudhunagar banks. The amount of overdues in these banks has declined during the study period. The positive annual growth rates were recorded in all the other banks and they were significant in Chennai, Kancheepuram, Ramanathapuram, Salem and Thiruchirapalli banks. The amount of overdues in these banks showed an increasing trend. The compound growth rate varied from 91.22 per cent in the Dharmapuri bank to -3.34 per cent in the Virudhunagar bank.

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. B. S. Mathur, *Co-operation in India*, Sahitya Bhavan Publishers & Distributors (P) Ltd., Agra, 2001, p.287.
2. K.S. Pathania, *Management of Co-operative Finance in India*, Anmol Publications (P) Ltd., New Delhi, 1998, p.45.
3. D.K. Chellani and Rita Rai, "The Performance of DCCBs in Gujarat", *Indian Co-operative Review*, Vol.41, No.4, April 2004, p.289.
4. Sami Uddin and Mahfoozur Rahman, **Co-operative Sector in India**, S.Chand & Company (P) Lte., New Delhi, 1983,p. 97.
5. C.B. Mamoria, **Rural Credit and Agricultural Co-operative in India**, Kitab Mahal, Allahabad, 1983,p.129.
6. B.S Mathur, **Co-operation in India**, Sahitya Bhawan Publishers & Distributors (P) Lts., Agra, 2001,p.175.
7. The Madras Co-operative Manual Government of Madras, 1952,p. 94.
8. Sivaprakasam, **Personnel Management in CCBs in India - Policies and Practies**, Kanishka Publishers & Distributors, New Delhi, 1993,p.38.
9. B.S. Mathur, *op.cit.*, p. 180.
10. R.Thanikodi, CCBs in India: Problems and Remedies, *The Co-operator*, Vol.42, No.12, June 2005, P.523.
11. P. Sivaprakasam, *op.cit.*, p.47.
12. Circular of the Registrar of Co-operative Societies, Tamil Nadu, No. 500057/73, Dated 27.04.1973.
13. Circular of the Registrar of Co-operative Societies, Tamil Nadu, No. 200031/8/A1 (2), Dated 24.08.1982.

CHAPTER IV

NON-PERFORMING ASSETS - CONCEPT AND STATUS IN

DCC BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The present chapter aims at examining the Non- performing Assets – concept and status in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu. This chapter analyses the meaning of NPAs, scope of NPAs, prudential accounting norms relating to capital adequacy, income recognition, assets classification, provisioning standards, investment portfolio and the latest development. The position of standard assets, sub-standard assets, doubtful assets, loss assets, gross NPAs, provision for NPAs and net NPAs at the state level and the district level are discussed with the help of trend analysis and compound growth rates for all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

4.2 NON-PERFORMING ASSETS: CONCEPT

The Indian Banking System has several outstanding achievements to its credit, the most striking of which is its reach. An extensive banking network has been established in the last thirty years. The Co-operative Banks are now spread out even into the remote corners of our country. Indian's co-operative banking system is one of the largest in the nation in terms of the branch network of the banks.

Non-performing assets, popularly known as “NPAs”, have become a worrying issue in all the public sector banks. NPA is a new phenomenon with regard to the DCC Banks. The issue of NPA came into limelight only when the RBI introduced the concept of asset classification, income recognition and provisioning norms to assess the credit risk of the DCC Banks in their balance sheets on 31.03.1997.

With the view to enhance operational efficiency, productivity, profitability and to accomplish the objective of implementing the best international practices in the DCC Banks especially with regard to revenue recognition, asset classification, provisioning, capital adequacy and Investments Portfolio, the RBI introduced a new set of prudential norms during the year 1996. Accordingly, a new definition was introduced for indicating NPAs. Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) represent those assets which cease to generate income and remain irregular for more than 180 days due to non-payment of interest and instalments. Such accounts were considered to carry more than normal risks attached to the business and the threat of loss due to their doubtful nature of recoverability. Presently, any borrowed account other than agricultural borrowal account is treated as non-performing if either interest or principal is not paid for three months (90 days). The RBI has laid down detailed guidelines for the identification of accounts as NPAs, which are discussed in this chapter.

Banks were advised to implement the instructions from the accounting year 1996-97. Each branch was directed to undertake the exercise of the classification of assets making provisions and these should be verified by competent officials from the internal inspection departments/controlling offices. The banks should also get the classification, etc., verified by Auditors and a certification to this effect obtained from the Auditors. The Balance Sheet for the year ended 31.3.1997 should reflect the financial position of the banks as arrived at on the basis of instructions now issued to banks.¹

With a view to preparing the Profit and Loss account and the Balance Sheet, reflecting the bank's actual financial health, a proper system for recognition of income, classification of assets and provisioning on a prudential basis have been made necessary. Regarding provision requirement, provisions should be made on the basis of classification of assets into four different categories - standard, sub-standard, doubtful and loss assets.

4.2.1. Non-Performing Asset (NPA) - Meaning

An asset becomes non-performing when it ceases to generate income for the bank. A non-performing asset (NPA) is defined generally as a credit facility in respect of which interest and/or instalment of principal has remained "past due" for two quarters or more. An amount due under any credit facility is treated as "past due" when it has not been paid within 30 days from the due date. It was,

however, decided to dispense with the “past due” concept with effect from 31 March 2001.

4.2.2 Scope of NPAs

A Non-Performing Asset (NPA) is an advance where.

- Interest and/or installment of principal remains overdue for a period of more than 180 days in respect of a term loan,
- The account remains out of order for a period of more than 180 days in respect of an overdraft/cash credit (OD/CC),
- The bill remains overdue for a period of more than 180 days in the case of bills purchased and discounted,
- Interest and/or instalment of principal remains overdue for two harvest seasons or for a period not exceeding two half years in the case of an advance granted for agricultural purposes.
- Any amount to be received remains overdue for a period of more than 180 days in respect of any other accounts.

In respect of advances granted for agricultural purposes where interest payment is on half-yearly basis synchronizing with harvest, banks should adopt

the agricultural season as the basis. In other words, if interest has not been paid during the last two seasons of harvest (covering two half years) after the principal has become overdue then such an advance should be treated as NPA. This norm is applicable to all direct agricultural advances listed in Annexure-D. In respect of agricultural advances other than those specified in Annexure-D, identification of NPA would be done on the same basis as non-agricultural advances which of present is the 180 days delinquency norm. Crop loan for each season, viz., Rabi and Kharif, has to be treated as separate accounts and the IRAC norms have to be applied accordingly.

Credit facilities granted for other allied agricultural activities as well as for non-farm sector activities should be treated as NPA if amounts of instalments of principal and/or interest remain outstanding for a period of two quarters from the due date.

In the case of project loan and housing loan, the loan becomes overdue if instalment is not paid on the due date. Similarly, where interest is payable after recovery of principal, such loans should be classified as NPA when there is a default in repayment of principal on the due date and the overdue criterion will be the basis for classification of assets.

In respect of consortium advances, each bank is required to classify the borrowal accounts according to its own recovery, and the banks participating in

the consortium should arrange to get their share of recovery transferred from the lead bank of the consortium.

In respect of short term agricultural advances as well as advances for other purposes, if any, granted under the on-lending system, only that particular facility which became irregular should be treated as NPA. In respect of all other direct loans and advances granted to a borrower, all such loans will become NPA even if one loan account becomes NPA.

In respect of cash credit/over draft facility, an account should be treated as out of order if the outstanding balance remains continuously in excess of the sanctioned limit/drawing power. In cases where the outstanding balance in the principal operating account is less than the sanctioned limit/drawing power, but there are no credits continuously for six months as on the date of balance sheet, or credits are not enough to cover the interest debited during the same period, these accounts should be treated as out of order.

Any amount due to the bank under any credit facility is 'overdue' if it is not paid on due date fixed by the bank.

The performance of the account as on the date of Balance Sheet only has to be taken into account for the purpose of NPA. Subsequent developments should not be considered for determining NPAs. If an interest and/or instalment of

principal has remained unpaid for any two quarters out of the four quarters ending 31 March of the year concerned, the credit facility should be treated as NPA although the default may not be continuously for two quarters during the year.²

4.3 PRUDENTIAL ACCOUNTING NORMS

Prudential norms were initially introduced for commercial banks and extended later to the co-operative banks functioning under the regulations of the RBI. However, co-operative banks differ structurally and operationally from commercial banks. Since commercial banks have more potential in all spheres, the co-operative banks face various obstacles to their existence. Commercial banks have flexibility in operations while the co-operative banks are not only denied flexibility, but are also bound to comply with the rigid rules and regulations of the Registrar of Co-operative Societies (RCS).

As far as the lending policies are concerned, the Manager of a commercial bank has got discretionary power either to sanction or reject a loan proposal whereas the manager of a Central Co-operative Bank is controlled by certain rules in granting some loans even if they are not viable.

The DCCBs were advised by the RBI to implement the prudential norms for income recognition, assets classification and provisioning from the accounting year 1996-97.³

Prudential accounting norms have special significance in the new banking system with its focus on efficiency, profitability, protection of investors' and depositors' interest. Its main elements are: (1) capital adequacy, (2) income recognition, (3) assets classification, (4) provisioning standards, (5) investment portfolio and (6) latest developments.

A format at Annexure-C shown in the Appendix forms the format of the provide prudential norms for co-operative banks.

4.3.1 Capital Adequacy Norms

The RBI introduced the risk assets ratio system for banking in India as a capital adequacy measure. Under the system, the balance sheet assets, non-funded items and other off-balance sheet exposure were assigned risk weight according to the prescribed percentage.

The weighted aggregate of the degree of credit risk is expressed as percentage of the funded and non-funded item. The aggregate is used to determine the minimum capital ratio. The risk-weighted assets ratio approach to capital adequacy is more equitable as institutions with a high risk assets profile have to maintain a higher level of capital. The integration of the on-balance sheet and the off-balance sheet exposures into the capital ratio would promote risk sensitivity and skills to manage the risk and structure balance sheet in a prudent manner.

Thus, capital adequacy is the ratio of capital to risk-weighted assets. According to the Bank of International Settlement (BIS) norms, co-operative banks were required to maintain a minimum capital to risk asset ratio of eight per cent.⁴ Adoption of this norm will be advantageous in many ways. It does not distinguish between small or big, commercial or co-operative, banks.

However, co-operative banks are different from commercial banks and as such capital adequacy norms as applied to commercial banks cannot be made applicable to co-operative banks. It is felt that the RBI should help co-operative banks in getting restrictive provisions of the State Co-operative Act removed and then prescribe a time schedule for attaining capital adequacy norms.⁵

As per the RBI guidelines, the minimum capital adequacy ratio of nine per cent should be maintained by the Indian Banks since March 2000 according to the Basle Committee Recommendations.⁶ Commercial banks are required to achieve nine per cent Capital Risk Weighted Assets Ratio (CRWAR) by 31st March, 2000.⁷ It should be noted that the Narasimham Committee has suggested an increase in capital adequacy ratio to 10 per cent to be achieved by 2002.⁸

The Narasimham Committee has also suggested that there should be no further recapitalisation of banks from the Government budget. However, the Committee is silent on recapitalising the co-operatives which must be strengthened for ensuring adequate flow of credit to the rural sector.

4.3.2. Income Recognition Norms

The policy of income recognition is based on the record of recovery and the unrealized income should be taken to the Profit and Loss Account by the SCBs/CCBs. However, in the case of certain states where the State Co-operative Act/Rules and Audit Manual provide for taking such unrealized interest to the income head in the P&L A/C, it is necessary for those SCBs/CCBs to make full provisioning for an equivalent amount by charging of the P & L A/C.

(i) Fee, commission and other income may be treated as income only when the account is classified as standard. Besides, a matching provision should be created to the extent such items were treated as income in the previous year but not realized in the subsequent year.

(ii) Fees and commission earned by banks as a result of renegotiation or rescheduling of outstanding debts should be recognized on an accrual basis over the period of time covered by the renegotiated or rescheduled extension of credit.

(iii) Even in the case of credit facilities backed by Government guarantee, overdue interest can be taken to P & L account only if matching provision is made.

(iv) The bills purchased/discounted should be treated as overdue if they remain unpaid. Interest may be charged to such bills and may be taken to P & L Account provided matching provision has been made.

(v) Accrued interest on investments may be taken to P & L Account till maturity. However, it has to be provided for fully, if interest is not realized on the due date/the date of maturity.

If any advance, including bills purchased and discounted, becomes NPA as at the close of any year, interest accrued and credited to income account in the corresponding previous year, should be reversed or provided for, if it is not realized. This will apply to Government guaranteed loan accounts also. In respect of fees, commission and similar incomes that have accrued and credited to the income account in the corresponding previous year should be reversed or provided for with respect to past periods, if uncollected.

Interest realized on NPAs may be taken to the income account provided the credits in the accounts towards interest are not out of fresh/additional credit facilities sanctioned to the borrowers concerned. In the absence of a clear agreement between the bank and the borrower for the purpose of appropriation of recoveries in NPAs (i.e. towards principal or interest due) banks should adopt the accounting principle and exercise the right of appropriation of recoveries in a uniform and consistent manner.

4.3.3 Norms for Asset Classification

The main elements of prudential norm relate to asset classification. Earlier Commercial banks classified their advances into eight health codes. i.e. Satisfactory, Irregular, Sick : Viable/under nursing, Sick : Non-viable/sticky, Advances recalled, Suit filed account, Decreed debts and Debts classified by the bank as Bad/Doubtful. Now, assets are classified into the following four categories (Chart 4.1).

(i) Standard Assets

Standard asset is one which does not disclose any problem and which does not carry more than normal risk attached to business. Thus in general all the current loans, agricultural and non-agricultural loans, which have not become NPA may be treated as standard assets.

(ii) Sub-Standard Assets

A Non-performing asset may be classified as sub-standard on the basis of the following criteria.

- a) An asset which has remained overdue for a period not exceeding three years in respect of both agricultural and non-agricultural loans should be treated as substandard.
- b) In the case of all types of term loans, where instalments are overdue for a period not exceeding three years, the entire outstanding in term loan should be treated as sub-standard.
- c) An asset, where the terms and conditions of the loans regarding payment of interest and repayment of principal have been renegotiated or rescheduled, after commencement of production, should be classified as sub-standard and should remain so in such category for at least two years of satisfactory performance under the renegotiated or rescheduled terms. In other words, the classification of an asset should not be upgraded merely as a result of rescheduling unless there is satisfactory compliance with the conditions.

(iii) Doubtful Asset

A non-performing asset may be classified as doubtful on the basis of following criteria.

As asset which has remained overdue for a period exceeding three years in respect of both agricultural and non-agricultural loans should be treated as doubtful. In the case of all types of term loans, where instalments are overdue for more than three years, the entire outstanding in term loan should be treated as doubtful. As in the case of substandard assets, rescheduling does not entitle a bank to upgrade the quality of advance automatically. A loan classified as doubtful has all the weakness inherent as that of a sub-standard account. There is also a problem of weakness in the collection or liquidation of the outstanding dues in such an account in full.

(iv) Loss Asset

Loss assets are those where loss is identified by the bank/auditor/RBI/NABARD inspectors but the amount has not been written off wholly or partly. In other words, an asset which is considered unrealizable and/or of such little value that its continuance as a doubtful asset is not worthwhile, should be treated as a loss asset. Such loss assets will include overdue loans in cases (a) where decrees or execution petitions have been time barred or documents are lost which are legal

proof to claim the debt, (b) where the members and their sureties are declared insolvent or have died leaving no tangible assets, (c) where the members have left the area of operation of the society (refers to the borrower in whose name the respective loan account with SCB/CCB) leaving no property and their sureties have also no means to pay the dues (d) where the loan is fictitious or when gross misutilisation is noticed, and (e) amounts which cannot be recovered in case of liquidated societies.

Broadly speaking, the classification of assets into these categories should be done taking into account the degree of well-defined credit weakness and the extent of dependence on collateral security for realization of dues. Banks should establish appropriate internal systems to eliminate the tendency to delay or postpone the identification of NPAs, especially in respect of high value accounts.

Where the account indicates inherent weakness on the basis of the data available, the account should be deemed NPA. In other genuine cases, the banks must furnish satisfactory evidence to the statutory auditors/inspecting officers about the manner of regularization of the account to eliminate doubts on their performing status. Thus, if these accounts of the borrowers have been regularized by repayment of all overdue amounts, such accounts need not be treated as NPA and straightaway they may be upgraded to standard category. The status of NPA

account in the doubtful category cannot be changed on account of the part payment of dues.

It is difficult to envisage a situation when only one facility to a borrower becomes a problem credit and not others. Therefore, all the facilities granted by a bank to a borrower have to be treated as NPA and not the particular facility or part thereof which has become irregular.

The NPA need not go through the various stages of classification in cases of serious credit impairment and such assets should be straightaway classified as doubtful or loss asset as appropriate. Erosion in the value of security can be reckoned as significant when the realizable value of the security is less than 50 per cent of the value assessed by the bank or accepted by the RBI/NABARD at the time of the last inspection, as the case may be. Such NPAs may be straightaway classified under the doubtful category and provisioning should be made as applicable to doubtful assets.

If the realizable value of the security, as assessed by the bank/approved valuers /RBI/NABARD is less than 10 per cent of the outstanding in the borrowal accounts, the existence of the security should be ignored and the asset should be straightaway classified as loss asset. It may be either written off or fully provided for by the bank.

Advances against term deposits, NSCs, IVPs, KVPs and life policies need not be treated as NPAs. But advances against gold ornaments, government securities and all other securities are not covered by this exemption.

In the case of bank finance given for industrial projects or for agricultural plantations, etc., where moratorium is available for payment of interest, payment of interest becomes due only after the moratorium or gestation period is over. Therefore, such amounts of interest do not become overdue or NPA with reference to the date of debit of interest. They become overdue after the due date for repayment of instalment of principal or after the due date for payment of interest, if uncollected.

In the case of housing loan or similar advances granted to staff members where interest is payable after recovery of principal, interest need not be considered overdue from the first quarter onwards. Such loans/advances should be classified as NPA only when there is a default in repayment of instalment of principal or payment of interest on the respective due dates.

In respect of advances granted for agricultural purposes where interest and/or instalment of principal remains unpaid after it has become overdue for two harvest seasons but for a period not exceeding two half-years, such an advance should be treated as NPA. These norms should be made applicable to all direct agricultural advances listed in the Annexure-D. In respect of other agricultural

advances including allied activities, assessment of NPA would be done as in the case of non-agricultural advances.

In the case of conversion or re-schedulement, the term loan as well as fresh short-term loan may be treated as current dues and need not be classified as NPA. The asset classification of these loans would thereafter be governed by the revised terms and conditions and would be treated as NPA if interest and/or instalment of the principal remains unpaid, after it has become overdue, for two harvest seasons but for a period not exceeding two half years. However, term loans, which have been rephrased/rescheduled after they have become NPA, should continue to be classified in the same category. (Rescheduling/Rephasing will not change the NPA status).

With effect from 1st April 2000, advances sanctioned against State Government guarantees should be classified as NPA and should be fully provided for in that year, if the guarantee is invoked and remains in default for more than 180 days. As regards advances guaranteed by the State Government which stood invoked as on 31 March 2000 but were not honoured by the State Government and continued to be in default for more than 180 days, was to provisioning be made with a minimum of 25 per cent each year during the period ending 31 March 2000 to 2003.

The availability of security or net worth of borrower/guarantor should not be taken into account for the purpose of classifying an advance as NPA or otherwise, as income recognition and classification of assets are based on recovery.

The amount involved in frauds should be classified as Sub-standard Assets, Doubtful Assets and Loss Assets depending upon the prospects of recovery within a reasonable time frame, say two years, in each case on the basis of availability of insurance cover, court decree, security deposit/fidelity guarantee (in the case of employees).

The amount outstanding in the Cadre Fund has to be considered loss asset and should be provided for fully, if no firm commitment from the State Government is forthcoming supported by suitable provision in the State budget.

Asset classification has to be done at branch level as the branches of the bank do the lending and relevant records are maintained at their level. However, provisioning is to be done at the bank level (HO) as preparation of financial statements for the entire bank is done at the HO level.

4.3.4 Provisioning Norms on the basis of Asset Classification

Provisioning is necessary considering the erosion in the value of security charged with the banks over a period of time. Therefore, after the assets of

CCBs/SCBs are classified into various categories (viz. standard, sub-standard doubtful and loss assets) necessary provision has to be made for them. The details of provisioning requirements in respect of the various categories of assets are mentioned below. A chart indicating briefly the criteria for classifying the loan accounts under four assets code categories and the basis of provisioning under each category are given at Chart 4.2.

4.3.4.1. Provision for Standard Asset

Banks are required to make provision on standard assets at a minimum of 0.25 per cent of the total outstanding in this category. The provision made on standard assets may not be reckoned as erosion in the value of assets and will form part of owned funds of the bank. The advances granted against term deposits, National Savings Certificates (NSC) eligible for surrender, Kisan Vikas Patras (KVP), Indira Vikas Patras (IVP), Life policies, staff loans would attract provision of 0.25 per cent prescribed for standard assets. The provision towards standard assets need not be netted from gross advances and should be shown separately as “Contingent provision against standard assets” under “other liabilities and other provisions”.

4.3.4.2. Provision for Sub-standard Asset

Since it is probable that a bank incurs some loss in such accounts, a general provision of 10 per cent is required to be made on the total outstanding amount in the case of all loan accounts categorised as sub-standard.

4.3.4.3 Provision for Doubtful Assets

(a) A provision of 100 per cent of the advances is to be made to the extent to which the advance is not covered by realizable value of securities to which the bank has valid recourse and the realizable value is estimated on a realistic basis.

(b) Over and above the provision on the unsecured portion, a provision of 20 per cent, 30 per cent and 50 per cent of the secured portion has to be made depending upon the period for which an asset has remained overdue (Chart 4.3).

CHART 4.3

CRITERIA FOR PROVISION FOR DOUBTFUL ASSETS

Criterion	% Provision
Overdue above 3 years and up to 4 years	20
Overdue over 4 years, but not exceeding 6 years	30
Overdue exceeding 6 years	50

4.3.4.4. Provision for Loss Asset

The entire loss assets should be written off. If the assets are permitted to be retained in the books for any reason, 100 per cent of the outstandings thereof should be fully provided for.

4.3.4.5. Guidelines for Classification and Provisioning for Assets

All agricultural loans may be treated as fully secured as they are disbursed against charge on land as provided in the respective State Cooperative Societies/Acts/Rules.

Liabilities towards PF and gratuity should be estimated on actuarial basis and fully provided for.

Advances against gold ornaments, government securities and all other kinds of securities are not exempted from provisioning requirements.

The investment portfolio of a bank would normally consist of both approved securities (predominantly Government Securities) and 'Other securities' (shares, debentures and bonds of cooperative and other institutions). Investments in approved securities should be bifurcated into permanent and current investments. Permanent investments are those which banks intend to hold till maturity and current investments are those which banks intend to deal in i.e. buy

and sell on a day-to-day basis. There is, however, no minimum percentage stipulated for bifurcation of investments into permanent and current categories.

As regards current investments and other securities, they should be valued at lower of cost price or market value. Investments in shares of cooperative institutions may be valued at carrying cost price.

With a view to ensuring full disclosure on the profitability and net worth of the bank, Items not provided for or items of liabilities where inadequate provisions have been made (e.g. Gratuity, Provident Fund, Income Tax, Interest accrued on deposits/borrowings, etc), Inspecting Officers should specify them to arrive at the unprovided for expenditure and treat them as actual expenditure for the purpose of arriving at the net worth.

Banks are permitted to take the loan outstanding under the Back-end Subsidy-Scheme net of subsidy amount and make provision only on the balance amount. This relaxation is for the purpose of making provisions only and not for other purposes, such as for the computation of gross loans and advances, asset classification, etc.

In order to give adequate time to co-operative banks to adjust themselves to the new system, phasing of provision was permitted as indicated below:

The banks were required to make 100 per cent provision in respect of loss assets from 1996-97 onwards. The provision of 30 per cent, 20 per cent, 20 per cent and 30 per cent of the sub-standard and doubtful assets were made compulsory during 1996-97, 1997-98, 1998-99 and 1999-2000 respectively. 100 per cent provision have to be made for sub-standard and doubtful assets from 2000-2001 onwards.⁹

4.3.5 Investments Portfolio

The investment policy of the Central Co-operative Banks should be based on the principle of safety and productivity. The planning of resource utilization is an important task for every co-operative bank. Judicious and profitable deployment of the resource mobilized has to be done in accordance with the requirements of constituent members of the bank and it should be always done with social awareness. The RBI regulates the liquidity of the banking system through two complementary methods. One is the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) and the other is the Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR).

According to Section 18 of the Banking Regulation Act 1949, a Co-operative Bank is required to maintain cash reserve with itself or in current account opened with the SBI or with any other bank notified by the Central Government of not less than three per cent demand and time liabilities of the last Friday of the second preceding fortnight. The maintenance of CRR in excess of

three per cent is a mere loss to the bank. The banks are to utilise the funds in profit making areas under Section 24 of the Banking Regulation Act 1949. Every co-operative bank should maintain liquid assets equal to not less than 25 per cent or such other percentage not exceeding 40 per cent of their total demand and time liabilities.¹⁰ Thus, the surplus funds of the banks are invested for maintaining the CRR and the SLR.

However, during the time of the growth of deposits, the co-operative banks have more surplus funds which are deployed in the form of investment in the secondary market. The Central Government securities, State Government securities and other approved securities are available with the maximum interest rates which are more than the deposit rates allowed by the apex bank.¹¹

With effect from May 16, 1994, the RBI permitted the Central Co-operative Banks to invest 10 per cent of their deposits in bonds of public sector undertakings with certain conditions.¹² They are:

- i) The investments already made in the bonds of Public Sector Undertaking and fresh investments should not exceed 10 per cent of their deposits.
- ii) Permission should be obtained from the concerned Registrar of Co-operative Societies.

4.3.6 Latest Developments

The mid-term review of the Monetary and Credit Policy of the Reserve Bank of India for the year 2002-03 announced a 90-day-norm for the recognition for loan impairment which has been extended to the SCBs/DCCBs from the year ending 31.03.2006. With effect from March 31, 2006, NPAs include amounts.

1. Interest and/or instalment of principal remaining overdue for a period of more than 90 days in respect of a term loan.
2. The amount remains out of order for a period of more than 90 days in respect of a Overdraft/Cash Credit (OD/CC).
3. The bill remains overdue for a period of more than 90 days in the case of bills purchased and discounted.
4. In respect of direct agricultural loans the existing norms of classification of NPA will continue. (All direct agricultural advances will be classified as NPA if the interest and/or instalments of principal remains overdue for two harvest seasons but for a period not exceeding two half years). But, in respect of other agricultural loans for allied agricultural activities, 90 days norms will apply.
5. Any amount to be received remains overdue for a period of more than 90 days in respect of all other accounts.

To strengthen the bank balance sheets and ensure smooth transition to the 90-day-norms, the banks should also commence making additional provisions for loans where the interest and/or instalment of principal has remained overdue for more than 90 days but less than 180 days as indicated below:

- a. 25 per cent of the additional provisioning to be provided by 31st March 2004.
- b. 50 per cent of the additional provisioning to be provided by 31st March 2005.
- c. 100 per cent of the additional provisioning to be provided by 31st March 2006.

In terms of prudential regulations, have to be made provisions in respect of various categories of assets as discussed above (Chart 4.2)

The RBI has been constantly reviewing the regulatory requirements in respect of prudential provisions and it is proposed to gradually enhance provisioning requirements in future.¹³

4.4 STATUS OF NPAs IN TERMS OF VARIOUS CATEGORIES OF ASSETS IN DCCBs IN TAMIL NADU

An attempt has been made to study the position and growth of standard assets, sub-standard assets, doubtful assets, loss assets, gross NPAs, provision for NPAs and Net NPAs of all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu. The position has been analysed with the help of mean and standard deviations. The annual and

compound growth rates have been calculated for analysing the trend and growth of various assets in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

4.4.1 Position of Standard Assets

Standard assets are the benchmark of a bank's health, since they do not carry more than the normal risk attached to the loan. A higher proportion of standard assets not only indicates a lower proportion of delinquency, but also denotes the efficiency of lending. The primary concern of banking business is to maintain the quality of assets as standard. The position of the standard assets of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu is presented in Table 4.1.

It is seen from Table 4.1 that the total standard assets of all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were Rs.3,83,311 lakhs in 1998-99 which increased to Rs. 5,63,327 lakhs by 2002-03. Though it decreased to Rs. 5,61,360 lakhs in 2003-04, it increased to Rs. 6,83,679 lakhs in the year 2004-05 due to increased disbursement of loans over the years except in the year of 2003-04. The average level of standard asset during the period was the highest in the Chennai CCB at 12.56 per cent. While the proportion of standard assets had been 10.13 per cent in 1998-99 in Chennai CCB, it increased to 13.16 per cent in 2004-05. However there is variation in the level of standard assets as shown by the standard deviation at 2.10 during the study period. The Salem DCCB also has a very high average level of standard assets during the period which stood at 8.22 per cent. The Nilgiris DCCB has the lowest average level of standard assets at 1.22 per cent during the study period. Among the rest of the DCCBs the Thoothukudi DCCB has the lowest average level of standard assets at 1.56 per cent.

4.4.2 Growth of Standard Assets

The growth rates of standard assets in the DCC banks in Tamil Nadu have been studied with the help of the simple linear regression model. The trend equations have been fitted separately for each district in Tamil Nadu. The calculated trend co-efficients and their statistical significance for different DCC banks are presented in Table 4.2.

TABLE 4.2
TREND AND GROWTH OF STANDARD ASSETS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Co-efficients		R ²	F	CGR
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	27450.57	9741.75*	0.9564	109.66*	17.10
2.	Coimbatore	15512.57	2261.86*	0.8899	40.41*	10.49
3.	Cuddalore	11728.71	2617.07*	0.8684	32.99*	12.16
4.	Dhampuri	36619.57	469.00	0.0082	0.041	0.004
5.	Dindigul	26925.29	2286.68	0.1143	0.645	9.25
6.	Erode	15649.00	1449.04*	0.9580	113.98*	7.11
7.	Kancheepuram	20950.29	1466.18*	0.7845	18.21*	5.91
8.	Kanyakumari	8537.86	1745.25*	0.9183	56.18*	11.62
9.	Kumbakonam	18209.43	926.54	0.4262	3.713	4.03
10.	Madurai	26635.29	-158.86	0.0199	0.101	-0.70
11.	Nilgiris	3954.43	607.00*	0.8147	21.99*	10.38
12.	Pudukkottai	8134.43	1534.68*	0.9511	97.21*	11.30
13.	Ramanathapuram	7202.29	835.14	0.4215	3.644	7.04
14.	Salem	26483.43	4051.54*	0.9725	176.47*	10.16
15.	Sivagangai	8059.00	1228.61*	0.8319	24.74*	9.62
16.	Thanjavur	8249.00	821.25	0.2084	1.317	5.91
17.	Thiruchirapalli	18575.14	3343.25*	0.9409	79.64*	11.43
18.	Tirunelveli	6740.14	968.75*	0.7647	16.25*	10.12
19.	Tiruvannamalai	12035.43	1419.18	0.4352	3.852	8.06
20.	Thoothukudi	7217.71	169.46	0.2963	2.105	2.21
21.	Vellore	13997.43	3028.50*	0.9317	68.24*	13.44
22.	Villupuram	17688.14	2986.93*	0.8837	37.98*	10.33
23.	Virudhunagar	8940.86	955.18*	0.7856	18.32*	7.42

* Significant at five per cent level.

It could be seen from Table 4.2 that the annual growth rates of standard assets in the DCC banks in Tamil Nadu were positive in all the banks except in

the Madurai bank. The annual growth rate of the standard assets in the Madurai bank is -158.86 times and it is statistically insignificant. It indicates that there is a decline in the amount of the standard assets in this bank during the study period but the decline is not statistically significant. The fitted regression model for the case is also insignificant since its F value is 0.10. The co-efficient of determination in the case indicates that the change in the amount of standard assets is only to the extent of 1.99 per cent. Positive and insignificant annual growth rates are seen in the Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Thanjavur, Tiruvannamalai and Thoothukudi banks with 469, 2286.68, 926.54, 835.14, 821.25, 1419.18 and 169.46 times respectively. The fitted trend equations in these cases are insignificant at the five per cent level since the F values were 0.04, 0.64, 3.71, 3.64, 1.31, 3.85 and 2.10 respectively. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Madurai bank, which has a negative growth rate of -0.70 per cent.

4.4.3 Position of Sub-standard Assets

An asset that has become overdue slips into the sub-standard category. Sub-standard assets ring alarm bells urging the bank to ensure effective monitoring and recovery. Table 4.3 shows the position of the sub-standard assets in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

If could be seen from Table 4.3 that the amount of total sub-standard assets which had been Rs. 34739 lakhs in 1998-99 increased to Rs. 95,062 lakhs in 2003-04. But it decreased to Rs. 38,268 lakhs in 2004-05 due to increase in the recovery of loans in this year. The Madurai DCCB has the highest level of sub-standard assets with an average of 13.98 per cent of sub-standard assets in the total sub-standard assets of all the DCCBs. It suffered an unprecedented increase of 24.60 per cent of the total sub-standard assets during 2004-05. The Dharmapuri DCCB, which has the highest amount of sub-standard assets however, has 10.72 per cent of the total sub-standard assets of all the DCCBs. The Kanyakumari DCCB has the lowest average among all the DCCBs with 0.86 per cent of total substandard assets. The standard deviation of standard assets were the highest in the Thanjavur DCCB at 2.77 and lowest in the Kanyakumari DCCB at 0.37.

4.4.4 Growth of Sub-Standard Assets

The details of the value of sub-standard assets in the 23 DCC banks from 1998-99 to 2004-05 were considered for growth analysis. The results are presented in Table 4.4.

TABLE 4.4
TREND AND GROWTH OF SUB-STANDARD ASSETS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Co-efficients		R ²	F	CGR
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	1115.00	-142.11*	0.7360	13.94*	-23.92
2.	Coimbatore	530.14	396.18	0.4970	4.939	21.99
3.	Cuddalore	604.86	57.43	0.0324	0.1674	3.11
4.	Dharmapuri	991.57	1558.50	0.1890	1.165	14.23
5.	Dindigul	1829.57	185.11	0.1376	0.7980	5.17
6.	Erode	66.71	145.61	0.4556	4.184	37.32
7.	Kancheepuram	2660.43	-84.79	0.0653	0.3492	-2.91
8.	Kanyakumari	254.86	57.18	0.1839	1.127	21.32
9.	Kumbakonam	2504.71	46.14	0.0085	0.0429	-1.10
10.	Madurai	1715.14	1460.93*	0.7297	13.50*	25.14
11.	Nilgiris	1059.43	119.50	0.1843	1.129	8.53
12.	Pudukkottai	1967.43	91.46	0.0602	0.320	2.37
13.	Ramanathapuram	1271.71	52.14	0.0315	0.162	2.94
14.	Salem	-72.00	634.21*	0.6445	9.063*	35.28
15.	Sivagangai	2539.43	-58.93	0.0321	0.166	-3.78
16.	Thanjavur	4184.43	-129.32	0.0479	0.252	-3.80
17.	Thiruchirapalli	2204.71	288.18	0.0839	0.458	4.67
18.	Tirunelveli	2500.00	-113.43	0.0797	0.433	-2.98
19.	Tiruvannamalai	1495.00	228.25	0.1183	0.671	6.33
20.	Thoothukudi	368.71	167.32*	0.8836	37.96*	17.96
21.	Vellore	541.57	247.57	0.1730	1.046	10.41
22.	Villupuram	2626.00	-197.93	0.3457	2.642	-13.14
23.	Virudhunagar	829.86	108.93	0.1838	0.909	15.97

* Significant at five per cent level.

It is evident from Table 4.4 that sub-standard assets of the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu show negative annual growth rates in the Chennai, Kancheepuram,

Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Villupuram with -142.11 , -84.79 , -58.93 , -129.32 , -113.43 and -197.93 times respectively. It shows that the amount of sub-standard assets in these have declined during the study period. But the decline is not statistically significant in the banks except in Chennai. There are positive annual growth rates in all the other banks but they were statistically significant at the five per cent level only in the Madurai, Salem and Thoothukudi banks with 1460.93 , 634.21 and 167.32 times respectively. The fitted regressions under trend equation in these cases are also significant at the five per cent level since F values were 13.50 , 9.06 and 37.96 respectively. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Chennai, Kancheepuram, Kumbakonam, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks where there are negative compound growth rates of -23.92 , -2.91 , -1.10 , -3.78 , -3.80 , -2.98 and -13.14 per cent respectively. This reflects that the problem of NPAs due to sub-standard assets is more in the Madurai, Salem and Thoothukudi banks.

4.4.5 Position of Doubtful Assets

The doubtful assets of the bank are the risk assets representing loans which have not been recovered even after three years. The doubtful assets in the loan portfolio of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu are shown in Table 4.5.

It is evident from Table 4.5 that the total doubtful assets of all the DCCBs had been Rs. 20892 lakhs at the beginning of the study period. They have tripled to Rs. 67975 lakhs in 2003-04. However, they have declined to Rs. 49,788 lakhs at the end of the period due to increase in the recovery of loans in this period. The Madurai DCCB has the highest amount of doubtful assets with an average of 12.59 per cent of the total doubtful assets of all the DCCBs. Its position had been 10.30 per cent in 1998-99, which increased to 15.26 per cent in 2004-05. However there are variations in the position of doubtful assets as shown by the standard deviation of 2.16 during the period. The Madurai DCCB is followed by the Thiruchirapalli DCCB, which has average doubtful assets of 12.43 per cent of the total. The Kanyakumari DCCB has the lowest average level of doubtful assets at 0.47 per cent and the standard deviation is 0.27.

4.4.6 Growth of Doubtful Assets

The annual and compound growth rates of doubtful assets are shown in Table 4.6.

TABLE 4.6
TREND AND GROWTH OF DOUBTFUL ASSETS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Co-efficients		R ²	F	CGR
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	807.14	44.18	0.0422	0.220	14.40
2.	Coimbatore	174.86	436.54*	0.6297	8.503*	22.04
3.	Cuddalore	-130.14	208.79	0.3972	3.294	65.79
4.	Dharmapuri	-422.29	336.04	0.3036	2.179	56.61
5.	Dindigul	242.71	311.54*	0.6881	11.03*	23.45
6.	Erode	-19.71	139.64*	0.7323	13.67*	32.36
7.	Kancheepuram	1704.86	-223.21	0.4233	3.67	-25.87
8.	Kanyakumari	27.43	38.82	0.4461	4.026	20.12
9.	Kumbakonam	305.86	482.68*	0.6344	8.674*	27.70
10.	Madurai	1517.14	899.18*	0.8788	36.24*	21.14
11.	Nilgiris	1066.00	-18.86	0.0172	0.088	-2.38
12.	Pudukkottai	92.71	175.54*	0.7489	14.91*	39.11
13.	Ramanathapuram	1563.29	286.32	0.2705	1.854	14.70
14.	Salem	485.43	47.36	0.0508	0.268	2.52
15.	Sivagangai	1698.00	73.18	0.1005	0.559	3.46
16.	Thanjavur	1031.29	295.57	0.2934	2.076	16.40
17.	Thiruchirapalli	352.57	1211.00*	0.8732	34.43*	34.87
18.	Tirunelveli	378.29	282.93	0.3925	3.230	20.86
19.	Tiruvannamalai	1129.00	399.29	0.1035	0.577	15.94
20.	Thoothukudi	777.00	336.00	0.2898	2.039	30.62
21.	Vellore	93.29	382.00*	0.8930	41.71*	27.24
22.	Villupuram	1491.14	184.39	0.1588	0.944	6.35
23.	Virudhunagar	168.71	215.46*	0.7995	19.93*	31.19

*Significant at five per cent level.

The annual growth rate of the total doubtful assets is analysed with the help of a simple linear equation. Table 4.6 shows that the DCCBs of Kancheepuram

and the Nilgiris banks have negative growth rates of -223.21 and -18.86 times respectively. The annual growth rates in these two banks are statistically insignificant. All the other DCCBs registered positive growth rates and it was statistically significant at the five per cent level in Coimbatore, Dindigul, Erode, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Thiruchirapalli, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks with 436.54, 311.54, 139.64, 482.68, 899.18, 175.54, 1211, 382 and 215.46 times respectively. The fitted regressions under trend equation in these banks are also significant at the five per cent level since the F values are 8.50, 11.03, 13.67, 8.67, 36.24, 14.91, 34.43, 41.71 and 19.93 respectively. The negative compound growth rates of the doubtful assets in Kancheepuram and the Nilgiris banks were -25.87 and -2.38 per cent respectively, while in all the other banks, positive compound growth rates are seen during the study period. This speaks of the fact that the problem of NPAs is comparatively less in the Kancheepuram and the Nilgiris banks.

4.4.7 Position of Loss Assets

The loss assets are those loans declared as non-recoverable. They highlight the discrepancies in the credit risk management practices of the bank. Table 4.7 depicts the position of the loss assets of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

Table 4.7 shows that out of the total outstanding loans and advances of all the DCCBs, Rs. 7404 lakhs had been declared as total loss assets in 1998-99. The total loss assets have increased to Rs. 41,609 lakhs in 2004-05. The proportion of the total loss assets portfolio of all the DCCBs has been consistently increasing throughout the period due to lack of a realizable value of security. The Kancheepuram DCCB has the highest amount of loss assets as indicated by the average mean value of 14.42 per cent of total loss assets of all the DCCBs. While its position was 7.52 per cent in 1998-99, which increased to 15.54 per cent in 2004-05. However, there is variation in the position of loss assets as shown by the standard deviation at 3.33 during the period. The Dharmapuri DCCB also has a very high average level of loss assets during the period with 11.10 per cent. The Vellore DCCB has the lowest amount of loss assets with an average of 0.46 per cent of the total and the standard deviation is 0.13.

4.4.8 Growth of Loss Assets

The growth rate in the loss assets in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu was analysed district-wise. The trend co-efficients and their statistical significance in different DCC banks are shown in Table 4.8.

TABLE 4.8
TREND AND GROWTH OF LOSS ASSETS IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Co-efficients		R ²	F	CGR
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	68.29	22.50	0.1964	1.222	13.45
2.	Coimbatore	453.00	-48.32*	0.7724	16.97*	-21.98
3.	Cuddalore	-281.14	233.07	0.5130	5.266	63.65
4.	Dharmapuri	1450.57	129.03	0.1011	0.563	8.24
5.	Dindigul	-677.43	334.39*	0.6517	9.356*	68.01
6.	Erode	-391.14	331.39*	0.9693	157.63*	107.01
7.	Kancheepuram	-1074.29	1185.57*	0.9301	66.56*	55.04
8.	Kanyakumari	33.43	172.64*	0.8632	31.56*	51.75
9.	Kumbakonam	571.57	33.25	0.4187	3.602	4.40
10.	Madurai	-337.29	367.64*	0.7304	13.55*	56.21
11.	Nilgiris	-341.57	185.54*	0.7595	15.79*	157.74
12.	Pudukkottai	-180.71	269.46*	0.8916	41.10*	36.15
13.	Ramanathapuram	-183.29	448.89*	0.6360	8.736*	35.08
14.	Salem	-743.00	624.00*	0.9013	45.65*	49.59
15.	Sivagangai	-453.43	333.39*	0.7516	15.13*	--
16.	Thanjavur	-451.86	625.43	0.4907	4.817	111.40
17.	Thiruchirapalli	122.57	291.82*	0.9539	103.55*	28.11
18.	Tirunelveli	-197.57	122.68*	0.7567	15.55*	--
19.	Tiruvannamalai	456.86	235.82*	0.6113	7.862	103.96
20.	Thoothukudi	-311.14	182.32	0.3433	2.614	33.44
21.	Vellore	-28.29	34.29*	0.8154	22.09*	39.87
22.	Villupuram	-606.57	235.39	0.4141	3.534	94.96
23.	Virudhunagar	-176.71	217.18*	0.5818	6.957*	50.27

* Significant at five per cent level.

Table 4.8 shows that the annual growth rates of loss assets in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu are positive in all the banks except in the Coimbatore bank.

The annual growth rate of loss assets in the Coimbatore bank is -48.32 times while the co-efficient is significant. It indicates that there is a decline in the amount of loss assets during the study period and the decline is statistically significant. The fitted regression model for the trend equation in the Coimbatore bank is also significant at the five per cent level since its F value is only 16.67. The co-efficient of determination shows that the change in the time variable explains the change in the loss assets to the extent of only 77.24 per cent. In all the other DCC banks, the annual growth rates are statistically significant except in the Chennai, Cuddalore, Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Thanjavur, Thoothukudi and Villupuram which recorded growth rates of 22.50, 233.07, 129.03, 33.25, 625.43, 182.32 and 235.39 times respectively. The fitted trend equations in these cases are insignificant since their F values are 1.22, 5.26, 0.56, 3.60, 4.81, 2.61 and 3.53 respectively. The compound growth rates are positive in all the banks except in the Coimbatore bank with a negative rate -21.98 per cent. It shows that the Coimbatore bank has performed well in keeping the loss assets under control.

4.4.9 Position of Gross NPAs

The gross NPAs are the difference between the total gross advances and the standard assets and they include the following assets viz., sub-standard assets, doubtful assets and loss assets. The gross NPAs position of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu is presented in Table 4.9.

It is evident from Table 4.9 that the position of NPAs of individual DCCBs to total gross NPAs of all DCCBs has been computed. This table shows the relative position of all DCCBs. The total gross NPAs of all DCCBs had been Rs. 63035 lakhs in the beginning of the period. They have tripled to Rs. 2,02,445 lakhs in 2003-04. They decreased to Rs. 1,29,665 lakhs in 2004-05 due to increase in the effective recovery of outstanding loans. Since the Chennai DCCB does not prioritize agricultural lending, the share of all the other DCCBs in the total NPAs amounts to 98.33 per cent. The Madurai DCCB has the highest level of NPAs with an average of 11.55 per cent of NPAs in the total NPAs of all the DCCBs which further increased to 15.40 per cent of the total NPAs during 2004-05. The Thiruchirapalli DCCB, which has the highest amount of NPAs, however, has only 8.33 per cent of the total NPAs of all the DCCBs. The Dharmapuri DCCB has a mean of 7.54 per cent of the total NPAs of all the DCCBs. The Kanyakumari DCCB has the lowest average among all other DCCBs with 1.24 per cent.

4.4.10 Growth of Gross NPAs

The resultant annual and composite growth rates of gross NPAs along with trend coefficients and F values are shown in Table 4.10.

TABLE 4.10
TREND AND GROWTH OF TOTAL GROSS NPAs IN DCC BANKS
IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Co-efficients		R ²	F	CGR
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	1990.43	-75.39	0.3713	2.953	-4.99
2.	Coimbatore	926.57	822.96*	0.8921	41.35*	21.70
3.	Cuddalore	176.43	502.14*	0.7941	19.29*	35.03
4.	Dharmapuri	-6506.00	4961.46*	0.9110	51.18*	95.22
5.	Dindigul	1394.86	831.04*	0.5698	6.623*	18.77
6.	Erode	-344.14	616.64*	0.9818	269.47*	47.56
7.	Kancheepuram	3286.29	878.21*	0.7609	15.92*	13.44
8.	Kanyakumari	544.29	225.79*	0.8660	32.32*	19.45
9.	Kumbakonam	3382.14	562.07	0.3270	2.429	9.45
10.	Madurai	2895.00	2727.75*	0.9269	63.43*	24.83
11.	Nilgiris	1807.00	283.29	0.4463	4.029	10.77
12.	Pudukkottai	1879.43	536.46*	0.6441	9.048*	14.99
13.	Ramanathapuram	2656.86	786.39*	0.6116	7.872*	16.72
14.	Salem	-329.57	1305.57*	0.7829	18.04*	33.72
15.	Sivagangai	3784.00	347.64	0.2358	1.543	7.39
16.	Thanjavur	4995.29	704.93	0.2278	1.475	11.71
17.	Thiruchirapalli	2679.86	1791.00*	0.8973	43.66*	21.39
18.	Tirunelveli	2680.71	292.18	0.3825	3.097	10.10
19.	Tiruvannamalai	3080.86	863.36	0.2241	1.444	10.94
20.	Thoothukudi	834.57	685.64*	0.8624	31.33*	26.83
21.	Vellore	606.57	663.86	0.5621	6.418	24.94
22.	Villupuram	3510.57	221.86	0.2568	1.728	5.27
23.	Virudhunagar	821.86	541.57*	0.7147	12.53*	25.85

* Significant at five per cent level.

It is understood from Table 4.10 that the annual growth rates of total gross NPAs in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu are positive in all the banks except in the

Chennai bank where the annual growth rate recorded a negative growth of -75.39 times which is statistically insignificant. It indicates that there is a decline in the amount of gross NPAs in this bank during the study period but the decline is insignificant. The fitted regression model for the Chennai bank is also insignificant since its F value is 2.95. The co-efficient of determination in this case indicates that the change in the amount of gross NPAs is to the extent of only 37.13 per cent. Insignificant annual growth rates are found in the Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore and Villupuram banks with 562.07, 283.29, 347.64, 704.93, 292.18, 863.36, 663.86 and 221.86 times respectively. The fitted trend equations in these cases are insignificant at the 5 per cent level since the F values are 2.42, 4.02, 1.54, 1.47, 3.09, 1.44, 6.41 and 1.72 respectively. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Chennai bank with a negative growth rate of -4.99 per cent.

4.4.11 Position of Provision for NPAs

Tamil Nadu prioritized agricultural lending . 90 per cent of the loans by DCCBs have been directed towards the agricultural sector. DCCBs are not able to recover agriculture loans fully or even partly in some cases. Therefore, provision against such assets must be made in their balance sheet. The position of provision made for NPAs of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu is presented in Table 4.11.

It is evident from the Table 4.11 that the DCCBs have been compelled to shoulder a heavy burden for making additional provision for NPAs year after year. The level of provision for NPAs which had been Rs. 19132 lakhs in 1998-99 increased to Rs. 79418 lakhs in 2003-04. But it decreased to Rs. 74271 lakhs in 2004-05. The Kancheepuram DCCB has provided the highest amount of provision for NPAs as indicated by the average mean during the period which stands at 9.86 per cent of the total provision for NPAs of all DCCBs. While its position had been 7.19 per cent in 1998-99 in increased to 9.82 per cent in 2004-05. However, there are variation in the position of provision for NPAs as shown by the standard deviation at 1.32 during the period. The Kancheepuram DCCB is followed by the Madurai DCCB which has an average provision for NPAs of 9.13 per cent of the total. The Kanyakumari DCCB has the lowest amount of provision for NPAs with an average of 1.84 per cent of the total and the standard deviation is 0.58.

4.4.12 Growth of Provision for NPAs

Apart from the rate of growth, the annual and compound growth rates in the provision for NPAs during the study period were calculated. The resultant growth rates in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu are presented in Table 4.12.

TABLE 4.12
TREND AND GROWTH OF TOTAL PROVISION FOR NPAs IN
DCC BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Co-efficients		R ²	F	CGR
		a	b			
1.	Chennai	665.71	117.46	0.4719	4.467	14.77
2.	Coimbatore	-125.00	519.71*	0.7577	15.63*	31.81
3.	Cuddalore	-406.14	576.04*	0.6445	9.063*	54.35
4.	Dharmapuri	806.43	569.54	0.3062	2.207	22.67
5.	Dindigul	1015.00	155.57	0.0797	0.433	1.72
6.	Erode	-688.86	483.86*	0.8791	36.34*	60.71
7.	Kancheepuram	308.71	1061.89*	0.9656	141.00*	31.27
8.	Kanyakumari	371.14	90.21	0.4706	4.444	11.69
9.	Kumbakonam	562.57	429.00*	0.6960	11.45*	20.41
10.	Madurai	16.14	1062.61*	0.9956	559.85*	34.20
11.	Nilgiris	102.57	194.96*	0.7257	13.23*	29.44
12.	Pudukkottai	-60.43	328.79*	0.9328	69.41*	33.12
13.	Ramanathapuram	-1328.71	861.36*	0.7367	13.99*	54.49
14.	Salem	-217.14	620.54*	0.7865	18.42*	30.32
15.	Sivagangai	430.86	414.07*	0.7182	12.74*	26.93
16.	Thanjavur	-169.57	571.00	0.5422	5.922	36.79
17.	Thiruchirapalli	2243.57	-152.18	0.1515	0.893	-5.41
18.	Tirunelveli	-278.43	316.32*	0.7684	16.59*	35.56
19.	Tiruvannamalai	1159.43	268.82*	0.9628	129.50*	13.15
20.	Thoothukudi	-552.57	591.07*	0.8637	31.68*	49.05
21.	Vellore	-41.57	423.04*	0.8897	40.34*	29.25
22.	Villupuram	-72.57	722.68*	0.6179	8.084*	24.38
23.	Virudhunagar	-151.29	343.14*	0.7496	14.97*	43.13

*Significant at five per cent level.

Table 4.12 shows that provision for NPAs in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu shows negative annual growth rates in the Thiruchirapalli bank with -152.18

times. It shows that the amount of provision for NPAs in this bank has declined during the study period. But the decline is not statistically significant. There are positive annual growth rates in all the other banks and they were statistically significant at the five per cent level in all the banks except in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kanyakumari and Thanjavur banks where growth rates were 117.46, 569.54, 155.57, 90.21 and 571 times respectively. The fitted trend equation in these cases are insignificant since its F values are 4.46, 2.20, 0.43, 4.44 and 5.92 respectively. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Thiruchirapalli bank which recorded a negative growth rate of -5.41 per cent. The positive growth rate in most of the banks shows the lock up of working capital in an unproduction way.

4.4.13 Position of Net NPAs

Net NPAs are the difference between the gross NPAs and the provision for NPAs. Any increase in the gross NPAs will lead to increase in the Net NPAs and vice versa. On the other hand any increase in the provision for NPAs will lead to a decrease in the Net NPAs, and vice versa. Table 4.13 shows the Net NPAs position in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu individually and collectively.

It is understood from Table 4.13 that the total amount of net NPAs of all the DCCBs has Rs. 43903 lakhs in 1998-99 which increased to Rs. 1,33,027 lakhs in 2003-04. But it decreased to Rs. 98769 lakhs in 2004-05 due to increased recovery of overdues. The Madurai DCCB has the highest level of net NPAs as reflected by an average of 11.94 per cent of net NPAs to the total net NPAs of all DCCBs. While its position had been 10.65 per cent in 1998-99, it increased to 12.51 per cent in 2004-05. However, there are variations in the position of net NPAs, the standard deviation was 1.95 during the study period. The Thiruchirapalli DCCB, which has the highest amount of net NPAs, however, has 9.72 per cent of total net NPAs of all the DCCBs. The Cuddalore DCCB has the lowest amount of net NPAs with an average of 0.48 per cent of the total and the standard deviation is 0.73.

4.4.14 Growth of Net NPAs

The growth rates of the total net NPAs in the DCC Banks in Tamilnadu were analysed with the help of the annual and composite growth rates. They are presented in Table 4.14.

TABLE 4.14
TREND AND GROWTH OF TOTAL NET NPAs IN DCC BANKS IN
TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Trend Co-efficients		R ²	F	CGR
		a	B			
1.	Chennai	1325.14	-192.93*	0.9352	72.12*	--
2.	Coimbatore	-7437.86	3486.79	0.4395	3.921	49.46
3.	Cuddalore	582.57	-73.89	0.0313	0.161	--
4.	Dharmapuri	522.43	1583.61	0.2133	1.356	44.18
5.	Dindigul	379.86	675.46*	0.8289	24.22*	24.78
6.	Erode	344.71	132.79	0.3070	2.215	39.82
7.	Kancheepuram	2982.71	-184.32	0.2129	1.353	-6.47
8.	Kanyakumari	173.14	135.57	0.4327	3.813	25.14
9.	Kumbakonam	2819.57	133.07	0.0532	0.281	1.61
10.	Madurai	2878.86	1665.14*	0.8076	20.98*	21.34
11.	Nilgiris	1704.43	88.32	0.1213	0.690	3.78
12.	Pudukkottai	1939.86	207.68	0.2437	1.611	7.53
13.	Ramanathapuram	3985.57	-74.96	0.0052	0.026	-21.90
14.	Salem	-112.43	685.04*	0.5796	6.893*	36.09
15.	Sivagangai	3348.86	-66.43	0.0247	0.127	-3.95
16.	Thanjavur	5164.86	133.93	0.0128	0.065	3.14
17.	Thiruchirapalli	436.29	1943.18*	0.9019	45.96*	32.71
18.	Tirunelveli	2959.14	-24.14	0.0026	0.013	-0.48
19.	Tiruvannamalai	492.86	1308.82	0.1479	0.868	13.44
20.	Thoothukudi	1387.14	94.57	0.0728	0.392	9.05
21.	Vellore	-3255.29	1704.61*	0.6173	8.065*	61.98
22.	Villupuram	3583.14	-500.82	0.2500	1.667	--
23.	Virudhunagar	973.14	198.43	0.3435	2.616	17.82

*Significant at five per cent level.

Table 4.14 shows that the growth rates of the net NPAs in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu are negative in the Chennai, Cuddalore, Kancheepuram,

Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks with -192.93, -73.89, -184.32, -74.96, -66.43, -24.14 and -500.82 times respectively. It indicates that the amount of net NPAs in these banks have declined during the study period. But the decline is not statistically significant in these banks except in the Chennai bank. In all the other banks there has been positive growth rates and the growth rates are significant at the 5 per cent level in the Dindigul, Madurai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli and Vellore banks with 675.46, 1665.14, 685.04, 1943.18 and 1704.61 times respectively. The co-efficient of determination in the Thiruchirapalli bank is the maximum at 0.9019. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai and Tirunelveli banks where there are negative compound growth rates of -6.47, -21.90, -3.95 and -0.48 per cent respectively. The banks in Chennai, Cuddalore and Villupuram recorded zero per cent growth.

4.5 CONCLUSION

The total standard assets of all the DCCBs have increased over the years except in the year of 2003-04. The average level of standard assets is the highest in the Chennai bank and the lowest in the Nilgiris bank. A negative and insignificant growth rates of standard assets are seen in the Madurai bank with the annual growth rates of -158.86 times. Positive growth rates were found in all the other DCCBs. It is statistically insignificant in the Dharmapuri, Dindigul,

Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Thanjavur, Tiruvannamalai and Thoothukudi banks. The compound growth rates varied from 17.10 per cent in the Chennai bank to -0.70 per cent in the Madurai bank.

The sub-standard assets in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu increased from 1998-99 to 2003-04. But it decreased in 2004-05. The Madurai bank has the highest average level of sub-standard assets while the lowest was found in the Kanyakumari bank. Negative growth rates of sub-standard assets were found in the Chennai, Kancheepuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli, and Villupuram banks. It is statistically significant only in the Chennai bank. There are positive annual and compound growth rates in all the other DCCBs but they were significant only in the Madurai, Salem and Thoothukudi banks. The compound growth rates varied from 37.32 per cent in the Erode bank to -23.92 per cent in the Chennai bank.

The total doubtful assets of all the DCCBs increased three-fold from 1998-99 to 2003-04, but they declined slightly during 2004-05. The Madurai bank has recorded the highest average level of doubtful assets while the lowest level was recorded in the Kanyakumari bank. The annual growth rates of doubtful assets were negative and insignificant in the Kancheepuram and the Nilgiris banks. In all the other DCCBs positive growth rates were found and it was significant at the five per cent level in the Coimbatore, Dindigul, Erode,

Kumbakonam, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Thiruchirapalli, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram and the Nilgiris banks.

The total loss assets of all the DCCBs have consistently increased over the period of study. The Kancheepuram bank has the highest average level of loss assets and the lowest was found in the Vellore bank. The annual growth rates of loss assets in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive in all the banks except in the Coimbatore bank. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Coimbatore bank.

The gross NPAs of the DCCBs have tripled during 1998-99 and 2003-04. But it decreased during 2004-05. The Madurai bank has the highest level of gross NPAs and the lowest was found in the Kanyakumari bank. The total gross NPAs in the DCCBs showed a positive growth in all the banks except in the Chennai bank with -75.39 times, but it is statistically not significant. Positive and insignificant annual growth rates were found in the Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore and Villupuram banks. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Chennai bank.

The provision for NPAs increased during 1998-99 to 2003-04. But it decreased in 2004-05. The Kancheepuram bank has the highest level of provision

for NPAs and the lowest provision was found in the Nilgiris bank. The annual growth rates of provision for NPAs were negative and insignificant in the Thiruchirapalli bank. There are positive annual growth rates in all the other banks but they were statistically significant in all the banks except in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kanyakumari and Thanjavur banks. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in the Thiruchirapalli bank.

The amount of net NPAs of all the DCCBs increased during 1998-99 to 2003-04, though it decreased in the year 2004-05. The Madurai bank has the highest average level of net NPAs while it was the lowest in the Cuddalore bank. The annual growth rates of net NPAs in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were negative in the Chennai, Cuddalore, Kancheepuram, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks. But they are not statistically significant except in the Chennai bank. There have been positive growth rates in all the banks, but the rates were statistically significant only in the Dindigul, Madurai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli and Vellore banks. The compound growth rates varied from 49.46 per cent in the Coimbatore bank to zero per cent in the Chennai, Cuddalore and Villupuram banks respectively.

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. Circular of the RBI, Letter No. RPCD; No. BC-155/07-37-02/95-96, Dated 22nd June 1996.
2. Master Circular of the NABARD N.B . BOS. HO/BOL/1577/B.57.2002.03 Dated 17.08.2002.pp.1-4
3. RBI Circular to CCBs, RPCD. No.BC155/07.37.02/1995-96, RBI Bombay, June 1996, pp. 1-8.
4. ***RBI Bulletin Supplement to Annual Report 1993-94***, RBI Bombay, August 1994, p. 142.
5. ***Manual on Deposits***, The Tamil Nadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Ltd., Chennai, January 1997, p. A-8.
6. B. Ramachandra Reddy, ***Management of Non-Performing Assets in Banking and Financial Institutions***, Edited Book, Serials Publications, New Delhi, 2004, pp. 316-317.
7. M.L. Tannan, ***Banking Law and Practice in India***, Indian Law House, New Delhi, 2004, p. 962.
8. B. Ramachandra Reddy, ***op.cit.***, p. 20.
9. Master Circular of the NABARD, ***op.cit.***, p. 5-15.
10. ***RBI Bulletin***, Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India 1995-96, RBI, Bombay, December 1996, p.108.
11. ***Ibid.***, p. 71.
12. ***RBI Bulletin***, Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India 1999-2000, RBI, Bombay, December 2000, p.128.
13. Circular of the NABARD Letter No.(TN) 972/DOS/1/2003-04 Dated 2.05.2003, pp. 1-2.

94-106,108-115,117-124,126-128,130-132,134-136,138-140,142-144,146-148,150-156

TABLE 4.1**POSITION OF STANDARD ASSETS OF DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU
(Rs in lakhs)**

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCBs	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	Mean^a	S.D.
1.	Chennai	38818 (10.13)	41380 (9.71)	54547 (11.15)	71929 (13.84)	79913 (14.19)	88391 (15.75)	89945 (13.16)	12.56	2.10
2.	Coimbatore	15702 (4.10)	19846 (4.66)	23491 (4.80)	26350 (5.07)	28794 (5.11)	27844 (4.96)	29713 (4.35)	4.72	0.35
3.	Cuddalore	15477 (4.03)	18039 (4.23)	19256 (3.94)	20681 (3.98)	26078 (4.63)	29379 (5.23)	31869 (4.66)	4.39	0.44
4.	Dharmapuri	30172 (7.87)	39511 (9.27)	51286 (10.49)	40167 (7.73)	35084 (6.23)	20875 (3.72)	52374 (7.66)	7.57	2.00
5.	Dindigul	13207 (3.45)	14282 (3.35)	18132 (3.71)	20350 (3.91)	20606 (3.66)	19744 (3.52)	25946 (3.79)	3.63	0.18
6.	Erode	17057 (4.45)	17909 (4.20)	20477 (4.19)	22424 (4.31)	22621 (4.02)	23466 (4.18)	26162 (3.83)	4.17	0.19
7.	Kancheepuram	21106 (5.51)	22893 (5.37)	25939 (5.30)	29518 (5.68)	29397 (5.22)	29857 (5.32)	28995 (4.24)	5.23	0.43
8.	Kanyakumari	11830 (3.09)	11850 (2.78)	13003 (2.66)	14055 (2.70)	16348 (2.90)	19926 (3.55)	21620 (3.16)	2.98	0.29
9.	Kumbakonam	19806 (5.17)	19883 (4.67)	20574 (4.21)	21449 (4.13)	25031 (4.44)	19328 (3.44)	27338 (3.99)	4.29	0.51
10.	Madurai	26463 (6.90)	26077 (6.12)	28840 (5.90)	26042 (5.00)	21723 (3.86)	24350 (4.34)	28504 (4.17)	5.18	1.06
11.	Nilgiris	4125 (1.08)	5335 (1.25)	6190 (1.27)	6944 (1.33)	6759 (1.20)	6500 (1.16)	8824 (1.29)	1.22	0.08

Table contd.

12.	Pudukkottai	10402 (2.71)	11400 (2.68)	11648 (2.38)	14177 (2.73)	15831 (2.81)	16568 (2.95)	19886 (2.91)	2.74	0.17
13.	Ramanathapuram	8804 (2.30)	9972 (2.34)	10439 (2.13)	8277 (1.59)	8889 (1.58)	10967 (1.95)	16452 (2.41)	2.04	0.32
14.	Salem	3011 (7.86)	34822 (8.17)	40342 (8.25)	41375 (7.96)	47124 (8.36)	48521 (8.64)	56532 (8.27)	8.22	0.24
15.	Sivagangai	10266 (2.68)	10761 (2.53)	10457 (2.14)	12447 (2.39)	14836 (2.63)	13799 (2.46)	18248 (2.67)	2.50	0.18
16.	Thanjavur	11470 (2.99)	12148 (2.85)	8618 (1.76)	6269 (1.21)	12867 (2.28)	10664 (1.90)	18708 (2.74)	2.25	0.61
17.	Thiruchirapalli	21359 (5.57)	24237 (5.69)	31313 (6.40)	32692 (6.29)	34272 (6.08)	36089 (6.43)	43675 (6.39)	6.12	0.33
18.	Tirunelveli	9091 (2.37)	6271 (1.50)	9749 (2.00)	11080 (2.13)	12223 (2.17)	12710 (2.26)	13082 (1.91)	2.05	0.27
19.	Tiruvannamalai	11786 (3.07)	15492 (3.64)	18234 (3.73)	18765 (3.61)	20663 (3.67)	13485 (2.40)	25560 (3.74)	3.41	0.46
20.	Thoothukudi	7784 (2.03)	6755 (1.59)	7635 (1.56)	8222 (1.58)	8867 (1.57)	7643 (1.36)	8363 (1.22)	1.56	0.23
21.	Vellore	15469 (4.03)	19220 (4.51)	24064 (4.92)	28526 (5.49)	31182 (5.54)	30430 (5.42)	33889 (4.96)	4.98	0.52
22.	Villupuram	21925 (5.72)	26406 (6.20)	24238 (4.96)	26819 (5.16)	30933 (5.49)	35864 (6.39)	41266 (6.03)	5.71	0.50
23.	Virudhunagar	11081 (2.89)	11439 (2.69)	10524 (2.15)	11313 (2.18)	13286 (2.36)	14960 (2.67)	16728 (2.45)	2.48	0.26
	Total	383311 (100.00)	426028 (100.00)	488996 (100.00)	519871 (100.00)	563327 (100.00)	561360 (100.00)	683679 (100.00)		

Source: Annual Reports of all D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Note : Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total ^aMean percentage.

TABLE 4.3**POSITION OF SUB-STANDARD ASSETS OF DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU****(Rs. in lakhs)**

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCBs	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	Mean ^a	S.D.
1.	Chennai	1244 (3.58)	677 (1.71)	628 (1.46)	318 (0.51)	335 (0.51)	472 (0.50)	152 (0.40)	1.24	1.07
2.	Coimbatore	788 (2.27)	1069 (2.70)	1585 (3.68)	2109 (3.37)	1638 (2.48)	4603 (4.84)	2472 (6.46)	3.69	1.39
3.	Cuddalore	358 (1.03)	412 (1.04)	433 (1.00)	1960 (3.13)	1603 (2.43)	892 (0.94)	184 (0.48)	1.44	0.89
4.	Dharmapuri	1427 (4.11)	3607 (9.10)	1564 (3.63)	10792 (17.25)	10468 (15.86)	21934 (23.07)	787 (2.06)	10.72	7.49
5.	Dindigul	2010 (5.79)	2085 (5.26)	1934 (4.48)	2236 (3.57)	3692 (5.59)	4474 (4.71)	1559 (4.07)	4.78	0.75
6.	Erode	90 (0.26)	360 (0.91)	826 (1.91)	410 (0.66)	568 (0.86)	1545 (1.63)	745 (1.95)	1.17	0.61
7.	Kancheepuram	3089 (8.89)	3087 (7.78)	1655 (3.84)	1381 (2.21)	1774 (2.69)	2841 (2.99)	2422 (6.33)	4.96	2.48
8.	Kanyakumari	112 (0.32)	212 (0.53)	522 (1.21)	832 (1.33)	829 (1.26)	580 (0.61)	298 (0.78)	0.86	0.37
9.	Kumbakonam	2447 (7.04)	2904 (7.32)	1989 (4.61)	2968 (4.74)	2135 (3.24)	4851 (5.10)	1531 (4.00)	5.15	1.40
10.	Madurai	3311 (9.53)	4044 (10.20)	4099 (9.51)	8594 (13.74)	12116 (18.36)	11334 (11.92)	9414 (24.60)	13.98	5.21
11.	Nilgiris	841 (2.42)	1024 (2.58)	1590 (3.69)	2074 (3.32)	2170 (3.29)	2176 (2.29)	968 (2.53)	2.87	0.51

Table contd.

12.	Pudukkottai	2014 (5.80)	1693 (4.27)	2685 (6.23)	2219 (3.55)	2279 (3.45)	3934 (4.14)	1509 (3.94)	4.48	1.01
13.	Ramanathapuram	743 (2.14)	1360 (3.43)	1378 (3.20)	2424 (3.88)	1866 (2.83)	1096 (2.01)	694 (1.81)	2.76	0.73
14.	Salem	971 (2.80)	674 (1.70)	1599 (3.71)	1597 (2.55)	4252 (6.44)	5107 (5.37)	3049 (7.97)	4.36	2.12
15.	Sivagangai	1778 (5.12)	2082 (5.25)	3417 (7.92)	2470 (3.95)	2679 (4.06)	2514 (2.64)	1186 (3.10)	4.58	1.63
16.	Thanjavur	2766 (7.96)	3244 (8.18)	5403 (12.53)	5526 (8.84)	3184 (4.82)	3257 (3.43)	2290 (5.98)	7.39	2.77
17.	Thiruchirapalli	3508 (10.10)	1381 (3.48)	2185 (5.07)	3221 (5.15)	4258 (6.45)	7565 (7.96)	1384 (3.62)	5.98	2.22
18.	Tirunelveli	1047 (3.01)	3538 (8.92)	2359 (5.47)	2710 (4.33)	1604 (2.43)	1402 (1.47)	1664 (4.35)	4.28	2.26
19.	Tiruvannamalai	1630 (4.69)	2517 (6.35)	1957 (4.54)	1970 (3.15)	1266 (1.92)	5542 (5.83)	1974 (5.16)	4.52	1.42
20.	Thoothukudi	543 (1.56)	881 (2.22)	791 (1.83)	811 (1.30)	1255 (1.90)	1343 (1.41)	1642 (4.29)	2.07	0.95
21.	Vellore	440 (1.27)	1043 (2.63)	1012 (2.35)	1621 (2.59)	2210 (3.35)	4051 (4.26)	346 (0.90)	2.48	1.06
22.	Villupuram	2789 (8.03)	1469 (3.70)	1711 (3.97)	2200 (3.52)	2515 (3.81)	1509 (1.59)	647 (1.69)	3.76	1.98
23.	Virudhunagar	793 (2.28)	292 (0.74)	1796 (4.16)	2101 (3.36)	1296 (1.97)	1230 (1.29)	1351 (3.53)	2.48	1.16
	Total	34739 (100.00)	39655 (100.00)	43118 (100.00)	62544 (100.00)	65992 (100.00)	95062 (100.00)	38268 (100.00)	100.00	

Source: Annual Reports of all D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Note : Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total ^aMean percentage.

TABLE 4.5
POSITION OF DOUBTFUL ASSETS OF DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU
(Rs. in lakhs)

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCBs	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	Mean ^a	S.D.
1.	Chennai	174 (0.83)	1103 (4.15)	1134 (3.22)	1610 (4.34)	1311 (2.81)	877 (1.29)	678 (1.36)	2.57	1.32
2.	Coimbatore	1050 (5.03)	1157 (4.35)	1463 (4.15)	1502 (4.05)	1917 (4.12)	1841 (2.71)	4517 (9.07)	4.78	1.86
3.	Cuddalore	11 (0.05)	566 (2.13)	582 (1.65)	985 (2.66)	150 (0.32)	480 (0.71)	2161 (4.34)	1.70	1.40
4.	Dharmapuri	120 (0.57)	233 (0.88)	107 (0.30)	940 (2.53)	497 (1.07)	3823 (5.62)	733 (1.47)	1.78	1.71
5.	Dindigul	832 (3.98)	930 (3.50)	735 (2.08)	1124 (3.03)	1828 (3.92)	2933 (4.31)	2040 (4.10)	3.56	0.72
6.	Erode	229 (1.10)	239 (0.90)	190 (0.54)	614 (1.66)	852 (1.83)	531 (0.78)	1117 (2.24)	1.29	0.58
7.	Kancheepuram	938 (4.49)	1854 (6.98)	1802 (5.11)	191 (0.52)	183 (0.39)	257 (0.38)	459 (0.92)	2.68	2.56
8.	Kanyakumari	185 (0.89)	66 (0.25)	103 (0.29)	141 (0.38)	140 (0.30)	195 (0.29)	449 (0.90)	0.47	0.27
9.	Kumbakonam	1241 (5.94)	616 (2.32)	1866 (5.29)	1699 (4.58)	2887 (6.20)	4592 (6.76)	2755 (5.53)	5.23	1.35
10.	Madurai	2152 (10.30)	4231 (15.92)	4121 (11.69)	3826 (10.31)	6316 (13.56)	7553 (11.11)	7598 (15.26)	12.59	2.16
11.	Nilgiris	996 (4.77)	995 (3.74)	1431 (4.06)	621 (1.67)	714 (1.53)	1364 (2.00)	813 (1.63)	2.77	1.27

Table contd.

12.	Pudukkottai	125 (0.60)	374 (1.41)	612 (1.74)	1007 (2.71)	1185 (2.54)	1318 (1.94)	943 (1.90)	1.83	0.65
13.	Ramanathapuram	1292 (6.18)	1292 (4.86)	2757 (7.82)	4352 (11.73)	3453 (7.41)	3661 (5.39)	2153 (4.33)	6.82	2.33
14.	Salem	583 (2.79)	625 (2.35)	816 (2.31)	238 (0.64)	319 (0.68)	1607 (2.36)	536 (1.08)	1.75	0.84
15.	Sivagangai	1389 (6.65)	1714 (6.45)	2259 (6.41)	2143 (5.78)	2354 (5.05)	2679 (3.94)	1397 (2.81)	5.30	1.35
16.	Thanjavur	1111 (5.32)	1017 (3.83)	3108 (8.81)	1639 (4.42)	2395 (5.14)	4319 (6.35)	1096 (2.20)	5.15	1.92
17.	Thiruchirapalli	939 (4.49)	4020 (15.13)	4182 (11.86)	4972 (13.40)	5761 (12.37)	6320 (9.30)	10182 (20.45)	12.43	4.56
18.	Tirunelveli	742 (3.55)	869 (3.27)	947 (2.69)	882 (2.38)	2742 (5.89)	3073 (4.52)	1315 (2.64)	3.56	1.16
19.	Tiruvannamalai	3984 (19.07)	685 (2.58)	899 (2.55)	989 (2.67)	1974 (4.24)	8229 (12.11)	2323 (4.67)	6.84	5.89
20.	Thoothukudi	187 (0.89)	1291 (4.86)	2147 (6.09)	2592 (6.99)	3699 (7.94)	3794 (5.58)	1137 (2.28)	4.95	2.34
21.	Vellore	766 (3.67)	828 (3.11)	1144 (3.24)	1307 (3.52)	1659 (3.56)	2800 (4.12)	2845 (5.72)	3.85	0.82
22.	Villupuram	1491 (7.14)	1540 (5.79)	1970 (5.59)	2471 (6.66)	2798 (6.01)	4105 (6.04)	1226 (2.46)	5.67	1.40
23.	Virudhunagar	355 (1.70)	332 (1.25)	884 (2.51)	1251 (3.37)	1453 (3.12)	1624 (2.39)	1315 (2.64)	2.43	0.69
	Total	20892 (100.00)	26577 (100.00)	35259 (100.00)	37096 (100.00)	46587 (100.00)	67975 (100.00)	49788 (100.00)	100.00	

Source: Annual Reports of all D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Note : Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total ^aMean percentage.

TABLE 4.7

**POSITION LOSS OF ASSETS OF DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU
(Rs. in lakhs)**

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCBs	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	Mean ^a	S.D.
1.	Chennai	230 (3.11)	86 (0.99)	87 (0.78)	2 (0.01)	148 (0.50)	234 (0.59)	321 (0.77)	0.96	0.92
2.	Coimbatore	380 (5.13)	328 (3.79)	323 (2.89)	288 (1.24)	318 (1.07)	95 (0.24)	86 (0.21)	2.08	1.75
3.	Cuddalore	197 (2.66)	155 (1.79)	14 (0.13)	173 (0.74)	1423 (4.78)	1770 (4.49)	826 (1.99)	2.37	1.63
4.	Dharmapuri	1143 (15.44)	986 (11.38)	2124 (18.99)	3020 (12.96)	3122 (10.49)	2100 (5.33)	1272 (3.06)	11.10	5.11
5.	Dindigul	118 (1.59)	124 (1.43)	113 (1.01)	135 (0.58)	193 (0.65)	1929 (4.90)	2009 (4.83)	2.14	1.76
6.	Erode	11 (0.15)	261 (3.01)	366 (3.27)	1024 (4.39)	1420 (4.77)	1597 (4.05)	1862 (4.47)	3.44	1.47
7.	Kancheepuram	557 (7.52)	1121 (12.94)	1463 (13.08)	3929 (16.86)	5113 (17.18)	7029 (17.84)	6467 (15.54)	14.42	3.33
8.	Kanyakumari	444 (5.99)	510 (5.89)	631 (5.64)	752 (3.23)	751 (2.52)	1274 (3.23)	1106 (2.66)	4.17	1.47
9.	Kumbakonam	660 (8.91)	671 (7.75)	649 (5.80)	646 (2.77)	583 (1.96)	850 (2.16)	873 (2.10)	4.50	2.74
10.	Madurai	360 (4.86)	59 (0.68)	1053 (9.41)	1201 (5.15)	930 (3.12)	1375 (3.49)	2955 (7.10)	4.83	2.62
11.	Nilgiris	9 (0.12)	8 (0.09)	30 (0.27)	86 (0.37)	950 (3.19)	845 (2.14)	876 (2.11)	1.18	1.17

Table contd.

12.	Pudukkottai	350 (4.73)	379 (4.38)	466 (4.17)	656 (2.82)	1004 (3.37)	1460 (3.71)	1965 (4.72)	3.99	0.67
13.	Ramanathapuram	1231 (16.63)	615 (7.10)	198 (1.77)	687 (2.95)	2690 (9.04)	2595 (6.59)	3270 (7.86)	7.42	4.48
14.	Salem	494 (6.67)	488 (5.63)	608 (5.44)	1379 (5.92)	1980 (6.65)	3408 (8.65)	3914 (9.41)	6.91	1.42
15.	Sivagangai	-- --	152 (1.75)	361 (3.23)	834 (3.58)	1027 (3.45)	2388 (6.06)	1399 (3.36)	3.06	1.72
16.	Thanjavur	76 (1.03)	79 (0.91)	193 (1.73)	4658 (19.98)	3067 (10.30)	3804 (9.65)	2472 (5.94)	7.08	6.41
17.	Thiruchirapalli	550 (7.43)	659 (7.61)	827 (7.39)	1225 (5.26)	1624 (5.46)	2090 (5.30)	2054 (4.94)	6.20	1.12
18.	Tirunelveli	89 (1.20)	-- --	-- --	354 (1.52)	381 (1.28)	363 (0.92)	865 (2.08)	1.00	0.71
19.	Tiruvannamalai	3 (0.04)	1289 (14.88)	1508 (13.48)	1649 (7.08)	1893 (6.36)	1572 (3.99)	1887 (4.52)	7.19	4.90
20.	Thoothukudi	330 (4.46)	231 (2.67)	7 (0.06)	7 (0.03)	36 (0.12)	420 (1.07)	1896 (4.56)	1.85	1.89
21.	Vellore	42 (0.57)	41 (0.47)	44 (0.39)	49 (0.21)	182 (0.61)	182 (0.46)	222 (0.53)	0.46	0.13
22.	Villupuram	17 (0.23)	18 (0.21)	11 (0.10)	11 (0.05)	10 (0.03)	155 (0.39)	2123 (5.10)	0.87	1.73
23.	Virudhunagar	113 (1.53)	403 (4.65)	108 (0.97)	537 (2.30)	921 (3.10)	1873 (4.75)	889 (2.14)	2.78	1.36
	Total	7404 (100.00)	8663 (100.00)	11184 (100.00)	23302 (100.00)	29766 (100.00)	39408 (100.00)	41609 (100.00)	100.00	

Source: Annual Reports of all D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Note : Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total ^aMean percentage.

TABLE 4.9**POSITION OF GROSS NPAs OF DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU
(Rs. in lakhs)**

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCBs	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	Mean ^a	S.D.
1.	Chennai	1648 (2.61)	1866 (2.49)	1849 (2.07)	1930 (1.57)	1795 (1.26)	1583 (0.78)	1151 (0.89)	1.67	0.69
2.	Coimbatore	2218 (3.52)	2554 (3.41)	3371 (3.76)	3899 (3.17)	3873 (2.72)	6539 (3.23)	7075 (5.46)	3.61	0.81
3.	Cuddalore	566 (0.90)	1093 (1.46)	1029 (1.15)	3118 (2.54)	3176 (2.23)	3142 (1.55)	3171 (2.45)	1.75	0.60
4.	Dharmapuri	2690 (4.27)	4827 (6.45)	3795 (4.24)	14752 (12.00)	14087 (9.90)	27857 (13.76)	2792 (2.15)	7.54	4.07
5.	Dindigul	2960 (4.70)	3139 (4.19)	2782 (3.11)	3495 (2.84)	5713 (4.01)	9336 (4.61)	5608 (4.32)	3.97	0.67
6.	Erode	330 (0.52)	860 (1.15)	1382 (1.54)	2048 (1.67)	2840 (1.99)	3673 (1.81)	3724 (2.87)	1.65	0.67
7.	Kancheepuram	4584 (7.27)	6062 (8.10)	4902 (5.47)	5501 (4.48)	7070 (4.97)	10127 (5.00)	9348 (7.21)	6.07	1.31
8.	Kanyakumari	741 (1.18)	788 (1.05)	1256 (1.40)	1725 (1.40)	1720 (1.21)	2049 (1.01)	1853 (1.43)	1.24	0.16
9.	Kumbakonam	4348 (6.90)	4191 (5.60)	4504 (5.03)	5313 (4.32)	5605 (3.94)	10293 (5.08)	5159 (3.98)	4.98	0.97
10.	Madurai	5823 (9.24)	8334 (11.13)	9273 (10.36)	13621 (11.08)	19362 (13.60)	20262 (10.01)	19967 (15.40)	11.55	2.02
11.	Nilgiris	1846 (2.93)	2027 (2.71)	3051 (3.41)	2781 (2.26)	3834 (2.69)	4385 (2.17)	2657 (2.05)	2.60	0.44

Table contd.

12.	Pudukkottai	2489 (3.95)	2446 (3.27)	3763 (4.20)	3882 (3.16)	4468 (3.14)	6712 (3.32)	4417 (3.41)	3.49	0.38
13.	Ramanathapuram	3266 (5.18)	3267 (4.36)	4333 (4.84)	7463 (6.07)	8009 (5.63)	8162 (4.03)	6117 (4.72)	4.98	0.66
14.	Salem	2048 (3.25)	1787 (2.39)	3023 (3.38)	3214 (2.61)	6556 (4.60)	10122 (5.00)	7499 (5.78)	3.86	1.19
15.	Sivagangai	3167 (5.02)	3948 (5.27)	6037 (6.74)	5447 (4.43)	6060 (4.26)	7581 (3.75)	3982 (3.07)	4.65	1.10
16.	Thanjavur	3953 (6.27)	4340 (5.80)	8704 (9.72)	11823 (9.62)	8647 (6.07)	11380 (5.62)	5858 (4.52)	6.80	1.89
17.	Thiruchirapalli	4997 (7.92)	6060 (8.10)	7194 (8.04)	9418 (7.66)	11643 (8.18)	15975 (7.89)	13620 (10.50)	8.33	0.90
18.	Tirunelveli	1878 (2.98)	4407 (5.89)	3306 (3.69)	3946 (3.21)	4727 (3.32)	4838 (2.39)	3844 (2.96)	3.49	1.05
19.	Tiruvannamalai	5617 (8.91)	4491 (6.00)	4364 (4.87)	4608 (3.75)	5133 (3.61)	15343 (7.58)	6184 (4.77)	5.64	1.84
20.	Thoothukudi	1060 (1.68)	2403 (3.21)	2945 (3.29)	3410 (2.77)	4990 (3.50)	5557 (2.75)	4675 (3.61)	2.97	0.61
21.	Vellore	1248 (1.98)	1912 (2.55)	2200 (2.46)	2977 (2.42)	4051 (2.85)	7033 (3.47)	3413 (2.63)	2.62	0.42
22.	Villupuram	4297 (6.82)	3027 (4.05)	3692 (4.12)	4682 (3.81)	5323 (3.74)	5769 (2.85)	3996 (3.08)	4.07	1.21
23.	Virudhunagar	1261 (2.00)	1027 (1.37)	2788 (3.11)	3889 (3.16)	3670 (2.58)	4727 (2.34)	3555 (2.74)	2.47	0.59
	Total	63035 (100.00)	74856 (100.00)	89543 (100.00)	122942 (100.00)	142352 (100.00)	202445 (100.00)	129665 (100.00)	100.00	

Source: Annual Reports of all D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Note : Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total ^aMean percentage.

TABLE 4.11**POSITION OF PROVISION FOR NPAs IN DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU
(Rs. in lakhs)**

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCBs	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	Mean ^a	S.D.
1.	Chennai	467 (2.44)	802 (3.01)	1289 (4.52)	1456 (3.66)	1459 (2.73)	1304 (1.64)	1172 (1.58)	2.80	0.98
2.	Coimbatore	569 (2.97)	1192 (4.48)	1569 (5.51)	1510 (3.80)	2078 (3.89)	2143 (2.70)	4616 (6.22)	4.22	1.19
3.	Cuddalore	235 (1.23)	670 (2.52)	814 (2.86)	1241 (3.12)	4274 (8.01)	3442 (4.33)	2610 (3.51)	3.65	1.98
4.	Dharmapuri	1342 (7.01)	1649 (6.20)	808 (2.84)	4558 (11.46)	4378 (8.20)	6870 (8.65)	1987 (2.68)	6.72	2.93
5.	Dindigul	1244 (6.50)	1278 (4.80)	1210 (4.25)	1346 (3.38)	1518 (2.84)	4259 (5.36)	606 (0.82)	4.00	1.72
6.	Erode	272 (1.42)	391 (1.47)	129 (0.45)	958 (2.41)	1777 (3.33)	2099 (2.64)	3100 (4.17)	2.27	1.17
7.	Kancheepuram	1376 (7.19)	2587 (9.73)	3396 (11.92)	4240 (10.66)	5452 (10.21)	7550 (9.51)	7293 (9.82)	9.86	1.32
8.	Kanyakumari	482 (2.52)	515 (1.94)	674 (2.37)	834 (2.10)	839 (1.57)	503 (0.63)	1277 (1.72)	1.84	0.58
9.	Kumbakonam	1433 (7.49)	1299 (4.88)	1567 (5.50)	1697 (4.27)	2537 (4.75)	4312 (5.43)	3105 (4.18)	5.22	1.04
10.	Madurai	1147 (6.00)	2257 (8.48)	3323 (11.66)	3871 (9.73)	5114 (9.58)	6545 (8.24)	7609 (10.24)	9.13	1.66
11.	Nilgiris	320 (1.67)	384 (1.44)	855 (3.00)	498 (1.25)	1430 (2.68)	1458 (1.84)	1232 (1.66)	1.93	0.60

Table contd.

12.	Pudukkottai	489 (2.56)	585 (2.20)	643 (2.26)	1145 (2.88)	1547 (2.90)	2183 (2.75)	2191 (2.95)	2.64	0.29
13.	Ramanathapuram	627 (3.28)	1023 (3.85)	131 (0.46)	1091 (2.74)	1671 (3.13)	4317 (5.44)	5957 (8.02)	3.85	2.19
14.	Salem	1016 (5.31)	1133 (4.26)	1472 (5.17)	1485 (3.73)	1870 (3.50)	4346 (5.47)	4533 (6.10)	4.79	0.90
15.	Sivagangai	644 (3.37)	1239 (4.66)	1769 (6.21)	2103 (5.29)	2414 (4.52)	3964 (5.00)	2477 (3.34)	4.63	0.95
16.	Thanjavur	580 (3.03)	721 (2.71)	1671 (5.86)	1425 (3.58)	2421 (4.54)	5529 (6.96)	2454 (3.30)	4.28	1.47
17.	Thiruchirapalli	2024 (10.58)	3243 (12.19)	555 (1.95)	1083 (2.72)	1611 (3.02)	1543 (1.94)	1385 (1.86)	4.90	4.15
18.	Tirunelveli	402 (2.10)	469 (1.76)	574 (2.01)	329 (0.83)	1032 (1.93)	1763 (2.22)	2339 (3.15)	2.00	0.63
19.	Tiruvannamalai	1453 (7.60)	1711 (6.43)	1961 (6.88)	2126 (5.35)	2453 (4.60)	3001 (3.78)	2938 (3.95)	5.51	1.38
20.	Thoothukudi	431 (2.25)	495 (1.86)	739 (2.59)	1917 (4.82)	1918 (3.59)	3892 (4.90)	3290 (4.43)	3.49	1.17
21.	Vellore	747 (3.90)	850 (3.20)	1054 (3.70)	1287 (3.24)	1667 (3.12)	2674 (3.37)	3275 (4.41)	3.56	0.43
22.	Villupuram	1572 (8.22)	1595 (6.00)	1801 (6.32)	2209 (5.55)	2325 (4.36)	3058 (3.85)	7167 (9.65)	6.28	1.90
23.	Virudhunagar	260 (1.36)	513 (1.93)	488 (1.71)	1365 (3.43)	1602 (3.00)	2663 (3.35)	1658 (2.23)	2.43	0.77
	Total	19132 (100.00)	26601 (100.00)	28492 (100.00)	39774 (100.00)	53387 (100.00)	79418 (100.00)	74271 (100.00)	100.00	

Source: Annual Reports of all D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Note : Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total ^aMean percentage.

TABLE 4.13

POSITION OF NET NPAS OF DISTRICT CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN TAMIL NADU
(Rs. in lakhs)

Sl. No.	Name of the DCCBs	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	Mean ^a	S.D.
1.	Chennai	1181 (2.69)	1065 (2.21)	560 (0.92)	474 (0.57)	336 (0.38)	279 (0.21)	-21 (-0.02)	0.99	0.97
2.	Coimbatore	1649 (3.76)	1362 (2.82)	1802 (2.95)	2389 (2.87)	1795 (2.02)	4396 (3.30)	32172 (32.57)	7.18	10.38
3.	Cuddalore	331 (0.75)	423 (0.88)	215 (0.35)	1877 (2.26)	-1098 (-1.23)	-300 (-0.23)	561 (0.57)	0.48	0.73
4.	Dharmapuri	1348 (3.07)	3178 (6.59)	2987 (4.89)	10194 (12.26)	9709 (10.91)	20987 (15.78)	805 (0.82)	7.76	4.99
5.	Dindigul	1716 (3.91)	1861 (3.86)	1572 (2.57)	2149 (2.58)	4195 (4.72)	5077 (3.82)	5002 (5.07)	3.79	0.88
6.	Erode	58 (0.13)	469 (0.97)	1253 (2.05)	1090 (1.31)	1063 (1.19)	1574 (1.18)	624 (0.63)	1.07	0.55
7.	Kancheepuram	3208 (7.31)	3475 (7.20)	1524 (2.50)	1261 (1.52)	1618 (1.82)	2577 (1.94)	2055 (2.08)	3.48	2.40
8.	Kanyakumari	259 (0.59)	273 (0.57)	582 (0.95)	891 (1.07)	881 (0.99)	1546 (1.16)	576 (0.58)	0.84	0.24
9.	Kumbakonam	2915 (6.64)	2892 (5.99)	2937 (4.81)	3616 (4.35)	3068 (3.45)	5981 (4.50)	2054 (2.08)	4.55	1.41
10.	Madurai	4676 (10.65)	6077 (12.59)	5950 (9.74)	9750 (11.73)	14248 (16.02)	13717 (10.31)	12358 (12.51)	11.94	1.95
11.	Nilgiris	1526 (3.48)	1643 (3.40)	2196 (3.60)	2283 (2.75)	2404 (2.70)	2927 (2.20)	1425 (1.44)	2.80	0.73

Table contd.

12.	Pudukkottai	2000 (4.56)	1861 (3.86)	3120 (5.11)	2737 (3.29)	2921 (3.28)	4529 (3.40)	2226 (2.25)	3.68	0.87
13.	Ramanathapuram	2639 (6.01)	2244 (4.65)	4202 (6.88)	6372 (7.66)	6338 (7.12)	3845 (2.89)	160 (0.16)	5.05	2.51
14.	Salem	1032 (2.35)	654 (1.36)	1551 (2.54)	1729 (2.08)	4686 (5.27)	5776 (4.34)	2966 (3.00)	3.00	1.26
15.	Sivagangai	2523 (5.75)	2709 (5.61)	4268 (6.99)	3314 (3.99)	3646 (4.10)	3617 (2.72)	1505 (1.52)	4.38	1.75
16.	Thanjavur	3373 (7.68)	3619 (7.50)	7033 (11.52)	10398 (12.51)	6226 (7.00)	5851 (4.40)	3404 (3.45)	7.72	3.10
17.	Thiruchirapalli	2973 (6.77)	2817 (5.84)	6639 (10.87)	8335 (10.03)	10032 (11.28)	14432 (10.85)	12235 (12.39)	9.72	2.27
18.	Tirunelveli	1476 (3.36)	3938 (8.16)	2732 (4.47)	3617 (4.35)	3695 (4.15)	3075 (2.31)	1505 (1.52)	4.05	1.95
19.	Tiruvannamalai	4164 (9.48)	2780 (5.76)	2403 (3.93)	2482 (2.98)	2680 (3.01)	22342 (16.80)	3246 (3.29)	6.46	4.74
20.	Thoothukudi	629 (1.43)	1908 (3.95)	2206 (3.61)	1493 (1.80)	3072 (3.45)	1665 (1.25)	1385 (1.40)	2.41	1.11
21.	Vellore	501 (1.14)	1062 (2.20)	1146 (1.88)	1690 (2.03)	2384 (2.68)	4359 (3.28)	13800 (13.97)	3.88	4.16
22.	Villupuram	2725 (6.21)	1432 (2.97)	1891 (3.10)	2473 (2.97)	2998 (3.37)	2711 (2.04)	-3171 (-3.21)	2.49	1.98
23.	Virudhunagar	1001 (2.28)	514 (1.06)	2300 (3.77)	2524 (3.04)	2068 (2.32)	2064 (1.55)	1897 (1.92)	2.28	0.84
	Total	43903 (100.00)	48256 (100.00)	61069 (100.00)	83138 (100.00)	88965 (100.00)	133027 (100.00)	98769 (100.00)	100.00	

Source: Annual Reports of all D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Note : Figures in parentheses indicate percentage to total ^aMean percentage.

CHART 4.1
ASSETS CLASSIFICATION

S.No	Types of Assets	Cash Credit and Over Draft	Bills Purchased and Discounted	Term Loans	Others
1	Standard assets	The account is not NPA and does not disclose any problem and does not carry more than normal risk attached to the business.			
2.	Sub-standard assets	The account remains as NPA for a period not exceeding three years as on the date of balance sheet for both agricultural and non-agricultural loans.	The bills purchased / bills discounted, overdue for a period of not exceeding three years as on the date of balance sheet.	The installment of principal are overdue for a period not exceeding three years on the date of balance sheet. All renegotiated/ rescheduled accounts until two years of satisfactory performance under revised terms.	The account remains as NPA for a period not exceeding three years as on the date of balance sheet.
3.	Doubtful assets	The account remains as NPA for a period exceeding three years as on the date of balance sheet.	The bills paid, bills discounted remain NPA for a period of not exceeding three years as on the date of balance sheet.	The installment of principal are overdue for a period exceeding three years on the date of balance sheet. (Rescheduling does not entitle a bank to upgrade the quality of an advance automatically.)	The account remains as NPA for a period exceeding three years as on the date of balance sheet.
4.	Loss assets	Account, identified by the bank's internal or external auditors or by the NABARD inspectors as wholly irrecoverable and against which provisions either fully or partly have not been made.			

CHART 4.2
 NORMS FOR CLASSIFICATION OF ASSETS AND PROVISIONING REQUIRED FOR N.P.A A/C IN DCCBs

CHAPER V

IMPACT OF NPAs ON VARIOUS PERFORMANCE VARIABLES IN DCC BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter analyses the data relating to non-performing assets of District Central Co-operative Banks, with a view to assess the magnitude of the influence of the non-performing assets on some selected variables taken from the Annual Audit Reports of all DCC banks in Tamil Nadu for the period of seven years from 1998-99 to 2004-05. Only those variables that have a bearing on NPA in a significant manner have been chosen. The study highlights the weakness of weak of the banks and the strengths of strong banks.

The problem of NPAs may be the root cause for the policy change of DCCBs. Credit necessarily involves taking risks. While focus on NPAs is necessary, it should not lead to total risk aversion and a feeling that the simplest way of reducing NPAs would be to lend only to blue-chip companies and the Government.

In order to examine the relationship with and influence on certain important variables that NPAs have in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu, simple regression and multiple regression tests have been carried out and the results are

furnished in this chapter. While carrying out the tests, care has been taken to include variables which have a strong relationship and influence on NPAs and the results have helped in arriving at certain definite conclusions with NPAs as the central figure.

The list of the variables identified and used in the simple regression tests is as under:

LIST OF VARIABLES USED, VARIABLES TAKEN AND THEIR CODES

Sl.No.	Variables Used	Variable Taken	Codes
1.	Advances (Absolute Figures)	I	X _{AD}
2.	Standard Assets (Absolute Figures)	I	X _{STA}
3.	NPAs (Absolute Figures)	I/D	X _{NA}
4.	Investments (Absolute Figures)	D	X _{INV}
5.	Legal Expenses (Absolute Figures)	D	X _{LE}
6.	Net Profit (Absolute Figures)	I/D	X _{NP}
7.	Spread (Absolute Figures)	D	X _{SP}
8.	Overdues (Absolute Figures)	I	X _{OD}
9.	Recovery (Absolute Figures)	D	X _{RV}

I = Independent Variable

D = Dependent Variable.

The impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu has been analysed with the help of simple regression for each bank separately.

$$Y = a + b X + e$$

Whereas

Y = Dependent Variable

X = Independent Variable

b = Regression Co-efficient of Independent Variable

a = Intercept and

e = Error term.

5.2 NON-PERFORMING ASSETS (X_{NA}) AND ADVANCES (X_{AD})

Non-performing assets form part of gross advances. As and when credit expansion takes place, some seeds of NPAs are sown. Some of the advances may not perform and banks may find it difficult to recover the dues by way of interest and principal amount as per the prudential norms prescribed. Such advances are termed non-performing assets and as per the regulations they have to be classified under sub-standard, doubtful and loss assets depending on the period for which the dues have remained unpaid and advances are unsecured. Immediately on expansion of credit, the level of NPAs as percentage of the total advances comes down, as there is always a time lag in the formation and identification of NPAs

after an advance has been released (minimum two quarters). This has since been changed as 90 days with effect from 31st March, 2006.

Banks can show reduction in the level of NPAs by expansion of credit and ever-greening of advances, i.e. by granting distinguished fresh loans (to repay old loans) to avoid classification of NPAs as per the time schedule. Keeping this aspect in view absolute figures of NPAs and absolute figures of advances have been taken for the purpose of analysis, as there been continuous growth of non-performing assets in absolute terms while there has been a decline in NPAs when expressed in terms of percentage to total advances. Since reliable organised data relating to NPAs are available only from 31.3.1999 onwards (i.e., from the time when the problem of NPAs was felt) absolute figures from the year has been used. The simple regression equation taking into account gross advances as the independent variable and NPAs as the dependent variable is formed to examine the degree of impact of the gross advances on NPAs. The results are presented in Table 5.1.

TABLE 5.1
IMPACT OF GROSS ADVANCES ON NPAs

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{AD}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-0.0063 (0.0031)	-2.035	2069.48*	0.4530	4.14
2.	Coimbatore	0.2466* (0.0571)	4.318	-2877.96	0.7886	18.65*
3.	Cuddalore	0.1484* (0.0355)	4.176	-1548.47	0.7772	17.44*
4.	Dharmapuri	0.2154 (0.5109)	0.422	-354.79	0.0343	0.178
5.	Dindigul	0.3119* (0.1193)	2.613	-2646.42	0.5773	6.83*
6.	Erode	0.2916* (0.0298)	9.802	-4749.93*	0.9505	96.07*
7.	Kancheepuram	0.3537* (0.0967)	3.659	-5092.03	0.7281	13.39*
8.	Kanyakumari	0.1048* (0.0257)	4.087	-331.17	0.7696	16.70*
9.	Kumbakonam	0.2861 (0.2499)	1.145	-2251.73	0.2078	1.31
10.	Madurai	1.0022* (0.1943)	5.157	-26087.42*	0.8417	26.59*
11.	Nilgiris	0.3408 (0.1371)	2.486	-237.31	0.5528	6.18
12.	Pudukkottai	0.2677* (0.0782)	3.423	-873.82	0.7009	11.72*
13.	Ramanathapuram	0.3839 (0.2087)	1.840	-472.05	0.4036	3.38
14.	Salem	0.2475* (0.0524)	4.755	-6882.44*	0.8189	22.61*
15.	Sivagangai	0.2451 (0.1677)	1.462	725.90	0.2995	2.14
16.	Thanjavur	0.2843 (0.4028)	0.706)	2313.29	0.0906	0.498
17.	Thiruchirapalli	0.3438* (0.0572)	6.014	-4523.07	0.8786	36.17*
18.	Tirunelveli	0.2181 (0.1247)	1.748	695.15	0.3794	3.06
19.	Tiruvannamalai	0.3768 (0.3120)	1.208	-2602.86	0.2257	1.46
20.	Thoothukudi	0.7592* (0.1040)	7.298	-5132.91*	0.9142	53.26*
21.	Vellore	0.1868* (0.0622)	3.004	-2224.46	0.6435	9.02*
22.	Villupuram	0.0593 (0.0520)	1.139	2380.88	0.2060	1.30
23.	Virudhunagar	0.3410* (0.1072)	3.183	-2383.18	0.6695	10.13*

* Significant at 5 Per cent Level. Figures in Parentheses are Standard Errors.

It could be seen from Table 5.1 that the independent variable namely gross advances of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu reflect a positive influence on the NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai bank. Though the regression co-efficient of the gross advances in the Chennai bank is -0.0063 unit, it is not statistically significant. The change in the gross advances of the above bank is explained by the change in NPAs to the extent of 45.30 per cent. The influences of gross advances are positive and statistically significant at the 5 per cent level in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Dindigul, Erode, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks. A unit increase in the gross advance has resulted in an increase of NPAs of these banks by 0.2466, 0.1484, 0.3119, 0.2916, 0.3537, 0.1048, 1.0022, 0.2677, 0.2475, 0.3438, 0.7592, 0.1868 and 0.3410 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination in the regression equation of these banks indicates that the changes in gross advances explained the changes in the NPAs to the extent of 78.86, 77.72, 57.73, 95.05, 72.81, 76.96, 84.17, 70.09, 81.89, 87.86, 91.42, 64.35 and 66.95 per cent respectively.

In the case of the Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai and Villupuram banks, the regression co-efficient of gross advances on NPAs is positive but these are not statistically significant. The analysis shows that the increase in the gross advances has resulted in an increase in NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai bank.

It may be inferred that every increase in the gross advances results in an increase in the net NPAs due to the increase in the Non-Performing Loans.

5.3 NON-PERFORMING ASSETS (X_{NA}) AND STANDARD ASSETS (X_{STA})

Gross advances minus NPAs form the standard assets, which establishes that NPAs are born out of standard assets. The position of standard assets is therefore subject to variation depending on the expansion/contraction of either gross advances or NPAs. Since NPAs basically emanate from Standard Assets, the study focuses on the relationship between Standard Assets and NPAs.

An account does not become an NPA overnight. The account sends out enough signals of the impending problems and the banker should be alert to catch these signals to quickly analyse, react and to take corrective action. Banks need a robust end-to-end credit process. Though appraisal is important, experience has shown that loans often go bad due to poor monitoring as well. While the importance of credit appraisal cannot be diluted for any reason, constant supervision also is essential to keep the advances performing. The task of containing NPAs by arresting slippage of accounts from the Standard Assets to Non-Performing Assets has been a cause for concern. Relentless monitoring and the introduction of a loan review mechanism of Standard Assets may be of some help to contain the slippage to NPAs.

India's credit risk problem is actually worse than it seems because it has been disguised by Accounting Norms less stringent than those of developed countries. The NPA would be around 12 to 13 per cent as against the 8 per cent disclosed. A simple regression equation taking into account standard assets as an independent variable and NPAs as dependent variable has been formed. The equation is shown in Table 5.2.

TABLE 5.2
IMPACT OF STANDARD ASSETS ON NPAs

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{STA}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-0.0063 (0.0048)	-1.308	2105.46*	0.2551	1.71
2.	Coimbatore	0.2902* (0.0978)	2.968	-2909.78	0.6379	8.80*
3.	Cuddalore	0.1463 (0.0614)	2.383	-1062.66	0.5317	5.68
4.	Dharmapuri	-0.5915 (0.2660)	-2.224	32883.62*	0.4972	4.94
5.	Dindigul	0.2633 (0.2192)	1.202	-255.50	0.2240	1.44
6.	Erode	0.3993* (0.0588)	6.795	-6440.55*	0.9023	46.17*
7.	Kancheepuram	0.3919 (0.2080)	1.884	-3710.53	0.4153	3.55
8.	Kanyakumari	0.1125* (0.0319)	3.530	-299.07	0.7137	12.46*
9.	Kumbakonam	-0.1314 (0.3041)	-0.432	8509.53	0.0359	0.187
10.	Madurai	-1.0116 (1.0291)	-0.983	40108.68	0.1620	0.966
11.	Nilgiris	0.2471 (0.2595)	0.952	1362.83	0.1536	0.907
12.	Pudukkottai	0.2919 (0.1380)	2.115	-141.24	0.4723	4.47
13.	Ramanathapuram	0.0315 (0.3493)	0.090	5470.60	0.0016	0.008
14.	Salem	0.2978* (0.0898)	3.318	-7820.94	0.6877	11.01*
15.	Sivagangai	0.0626 (0.2360)	0.265	4362.31	0.0319	0.070
16.	Thanjavur	-0.4593 (0.3044)	-1.509	13112.75*	0.3129	2.28
17.	Thiruchirapalli	0.4682* (0.1279)	3.661	-5113.25	0.7283	13.40*
18.	Tirunelveli	0.1345 (0.1810)	0.743	2421.42	0.0995	0.552
19.	Tiruvannamalai	-0.2879 (0.3566)	-0.807	11633.32	0.1153	0.652
20.	Thoothukudi	1.1481 (0.9280)	1.237	-5488.14	0.2344	1.53
21.	Vellore	0.1948 (0.0913)	2.132	-1823.74	0.4763	4.55
22.	Villupuram	0.0470 (0.0579)	0.811	3005.68	0.1163	0.658
23.	Virudhunagar	0.3404 (0.2179)	1.562	-1355.27	0.3278	2.44

* Significant at 5 Per cent Level. Figures in Parentheses are Standard Errors.

It is understood from Table 5.2 that the standard assets of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu show a negative impact on NPAs in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Thanjavur, and Tiruvannamalai banks, with the regression co-efficient of -0.0063 , -0.5915 , -0.1314 , -1.0116 , -0.4593 and -0.2879 units respectively. It is statistically not significant at the five per cent level. The standard assets have a positive impact on NPAs in all the other banks, which are statistically significant only in the Coimbatore, Erode, Kanyakumari, Salem and Tiruchirapally banks. A unit of increase in the standard assets has resulted in an increase in NPAs by 0.2902 , 0.3993 , 0.1125 , 0.2978 and 0.4682 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination in various regression equations under the Erode bank was the maximum of 0.9023 . It shows that the changes in standard assets explain the changes in the NPAs to the maximum extent of 90.23 per cent in the Erode bank. The impact analysis shows that the increase in the standard assets has resulted in an increase in NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Thanjavur and Tiruvannamalai banks.

5.4 NPAs (X_{NA}) AND INVESTMENTS (X_{INV})

The banks are inclined to take a safe route of reducing advances and increasing investments when there has been increase of NPAs. Since investments particularly in Government Securities are safe, liquid, fully secured and occasionally more profitable because of fluctuations in price and interest rates,

banks prefer investments to advances with a view to avoiding increase of NPAs. Further, by investing in Government Securities, banks can show better Capital Adequacy Ratio to Risk Weighted Assets as Investments are not required to be treated as part of Risk Weighted Assets.

A simple regression analysis taking into account investment as dependent variable and NPAs as independent variable is attempted. The test results are furnished in Table 5.3.

TABLE 5.3
IMPACT OF NPAs ON INVESTMENTS

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{NA}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-12.2321 (14.2173)	-0.860	71247.68*	0.1290	0.740
2.	Coimbatore	0.0381 (0.4431)	0.086	15950.11*	0.0015	0.007
3.	Cuddalore	1.2913 (1.1922)	1.083	7200.57	0.1900	1.17
4.	Dharmapuri	0.7607 (0.6455)	1.178	6600.59*	0.2174	1.39
5.	Dindigul	0.0271 (0.1225)	0.222	6997.46*	0.0097	0.049
6.	Erode	0.3162 (0.5931)	0.533	17397.18*	0.0538	0.284
7.	Kancheepuram	0.2859 (0.4388)	0.652	10965.34*	0.0783	0.425
8.	Kanyakumari	1.3972* (0.3358)	4.161	1572.79*	0.7759	17.31*
9.	Kumbakonam	0.0856 (0.1789)	0.478	6735.45*	0.0437	0.229
10.	Madurai	0.0600 (0.1119)	0.537	10978.26*	0.0545	0.288
11.	Nilgiris	0.1749 (0.4531)	0.386	2135.18	0.0289	0.149
12.	Pudukkottai	0.3833* (0.1440)	2.662	2498.45*	0.5863	7.08*
13.	Ramanathapuram	0.1823 (0.1064)	1.714	3200.49*	0.3701	2.94
14.	Salem	0.3603 (1.2994)	0.277	46447.75*	0.0152	0.769
15.	Sivagangai	0.2565 (0.1290)	1.989	2828.89*	0.4417	3.96
16.	Thanjavur	0.0828 (0.0483)	1.717	3401.86*	0.3709	2.95
17.	Thiruchirapalli	-0.0825 (0.1793)	-0.460	15106.79*	0.0406	0.212
18.	Tirunelveli	0.2238 (0.8122)	0.276	5008.09	0.0150	0.076
19.	Tiruvannamalai	0.0671 (0.1307)	0.513	4337.79*	0.0501	0.264
20.	Thoothukudi	-0.3163 (0.2601)	-1.216	5627.86*	0.2283	1.48
21.	Vellore	0.7025 (0.1673)	0.420	8829.85*	0.0341	0.176
22.	Villupuram	-0.6447 (1.4583)	-0.442	10323.97	0.0376	0.195
23.	Virudhunagar	-0.1465 (0.6304)	-0.232	9131.48*	0.0107	0.054

* Significant at 5 Per cent Level. Figures in Parentheses are Standard Errors.

It is evident from Table 5.3 that the NPAs in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu show a negative impact on the investments in the Chennai, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the investments of these banks by -12.2321 , -0.0825 , -0.3163 , -0.6447 and -0.1465 units respectively. But it is statistically insignificant. The impact of NPAs on investments has been positive in all the other banks but they are statistically significant at the five per cent level only in the Kanyakumari and Pudukkottai banks where a unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the investments by 1.3972 and 0.3833 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination (R^2) was higher at 0.7759 in the Kanyakumari bank, which shows that the changes in NPAs in this bank have explained changes in investments to the extent of 77.59 per cent. The impact analysis shows that an increase in NPAs has resulted in an increase in the investments in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks.

5.5 LEGAL EXPENSES (X_{LE}) AND NPAS (X_{NA})

There is a direct and very close relationship between Legal Expenses and NPAs. More non-performing assets mean more legal expenditure. The time taken to decide court cases is long and the expenses also mount. To examine this, regression co-efficient taking Legal Expenses as dependent variable and NPAs as independent variable has been formed. The result of the simple regression analysis is shown in Table. 5.4.

TABLE 5.4
IMPACT OF NPAs ON LEGAL EXPENSES

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{NA}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-3.9377 (8.9298)	-0.044	1.6894	0.0004	0.002
2.	Coimbatore	2.6352 (1.0622)	2.481	0.1198	0.5518	6.15
3.	Cuddalore	2.9586 (1.4469)	2.045	0.3435	0.4554	4.18
4.	Dharmapuri	2.7998 (1.8350)	1.526	0.4625	0.3177	2.33
5.	Dindigul	-8.8680 (5.6008)	-1.583	1.0456*	0.3339	2.51
6.	Erode	6.8386 (3.4040)	2.009	0.1720	0.4467	4.04
7.	Kancheepuram	2.3413 (6.1982)	0.378	0.6094	0.0278	0.143
8.	Kanyakumari	-1.6729 (3.1617)	-0.529	1.0993	0.0530	0.280
9.	Kumbakonam	-1.0218 (2.6750)	-0.382	0.6775*	0.0284	0.146
10.	Madurai	-7.0816 (4.3727)	-0.162	1.3592	0.0052	0.026
11.	Nilgiris	-1.3377 (2.8233)	-0.474	1.2776	0.0430	0.224
12.	Pudukkottai	1.5249 (7.5778)	2.012	-0.1409	0.4475	4.05
13.	Ramanathapuram	6.0507 (8.6359)	0.701	0.4803	0.0894	0.491
14.	Salem	1.1688 (5.2866)	2.211	0.0196	0.4943	4.89
15.	Sivagangai	-2.8638 (2.1359)	-1.341	2.4804	0.2645	1.80
16.	Thanjavur	-1.6730 (7.0378)	-0.024	0.8559	0.0001	0.0006
17.	Thiruchirapalli	-1.3694 (1.0944)	-0.125	1.2019	0.0031	0.016
18.	Tirunelveli	3.8220* (1.1574)	3.302	-0.1798	0.6856	10.90*
19.	Tiruvannamalai	6.8071* (2.2899)	2.973	0.0252	0.6387	8.84*
20.	Thoothukudi	1.4226 (5.5779)	2.550	-0.1060	0.5654	6.50
21.	Vellore	7.2768 (1.0092)	0.721	0.4341	0.0942	0.520
22.	Villupuram	-9.8889 (1.6009)	-0.618	1.1063	0.0709	0.382
23.	Virudhunagar	1.5654 (7.9548)	1.968	0.0594	0.4365	3.87

* Significant at 5 Per cent Level. Figures in Parentheses are Standard Errors.

Table 5.4 shows that the influence of the NPAs on the legal expenses in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu was negative in the Chennai, Dindigul, Kanyakumari, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur Thiruchirapalli and Villupuram banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the legal expenses of these banks by -3.9377, -8.8680, -1.6729, -1.0218, -7.0816, -1.3377, -2.8638, -1.6730, -1.3694 and -9.8889 units respectively during the period of study. But it is statistically insignificant at the five per cent level. The influences of NPAs on legal expenses are positive in all the other banks but they are statistically significant only in the Tirunelveli and Tiruvannamalai banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in legal expenses of these banks by 3.8220 and 6.8071 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination in these banks indicates that the changes in the NPAs have explained the changes in the legal expenses to the extent of 68.56 and 63.87 per cent respectively. The impact analysis shows that the increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the legal expenses in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai, Dindigul, Kanyakumari, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Thiruchirapalli and Villupuram banks.

5.6 NPAs (X_{NA}) AND NET PROFIT (X_{NP})

There is a very strong adverse relationship between net profit and NPAs. While the NPAs bring down the net profit substantially and affect the bank's Reserves and Provisions, the Regression Analysis may not fully reflect the

position, as net profit is a function of several variables which include non-performing assets, interest received from recapitalisation bonds, cash reserve ratio balances, income accrued from investments, exchange, commission and other miscellaneous items. It has been observed that banks do not make adequate provisions for NPAs identified which result in enhancing the profit. Further, to make up the loss of income from NPAs, banks charge a higher rate of interest on performing borrowers. Accounting is also resorted to inflate the profit by ever-greening of advances and adjusting interest arrears. Banks tend to add interest on hidden NPAs to enhance profit. The analysis of net profit vis-a-vis Non-Performing Assets has to be viewed from this angle. NPAs do not generate any income for the bank and at the same time banks have to incur recurring expenditure to maintain the NPAs in the books. This involves making provision for bad and doubtful debts, meeting legal expenses and maintaining the available securities.

Since NPAs affect repayments and interest recoveries, recycling of funds which is the essence of banking is virtually scuttled compelling the banks to lose out heavily by way of opportunity costs. The erosion of profit on account of all these cases is substantial, affecting the capital of the banks' reserves and their reputation in the market. A simple regression equation is taking NPAs as the independent and net profit as the dependent variable has been formed. The result is shown in Table 5.5.

TABLE 5.5
IMPACT OF NPAs ON NET PROFITS

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{NA}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-1.3085 (1.8283)	-0.716	6323.24	0.0929	0.512
2.	Coimbatore	0.0715 (0.0604)	1.184	-148.62	0.2190	1.40
3.	Cuddalore	0.0578 (0.0710)	0.814	-86.20	0.1169	0.66
4.	Dharmapuri	-0.4079* (0.1127)	-3.618	3167.92	0.7236	13.10*
5.	Dindigul	-0.2912 (0.2107)	-1.382	1225.33	0.2764	1.91
6.	Erode	0.0598* (0.0084)	7.128	25.511	0.9104	50.82*
7.	Kancheepuram	0.0037 (0.0123)	0.297	75.669	0.0174	0.088
8.	Kanyakumari	0.1673 (0.1526)	1.097	-140.22	0.1939	1.20
9.	Kumbakonam	-0.3131 (0.3531)	-0.887	1314.07	0.1359	0.786
10.	Madurai	0.0226 (0.0309)	0.732	-528.44	0.0968	0.536
11.	Nilgiris	0.1166 (0.1660)	0.070	99.73	0.0010	0.005
12.	Pudukkottai	0.0609 (0.0721)	0.846	-107.20	0.1252	0.716
13.	Ramanathapuram	-0.6275 (0.3272)	-1.918	2837.51	0.4238	3.68
14.	Salem	1.1469* (0.2865)	4.003	-2829.17	0.7622	16.02*
15.	Sivagangai	-0.4466 (0.3428)	-1.303	2177.56	0.2534	1.70
16.	Thanjavur	-0.0949 (0.2732)	-0.348	743.15	0.0236	0.121
17.	Thiruchirapalli	0.1438 (0.6644)	2.165	-1066.50	0.4833	4.69
18.	Tirunelveli	-0.3039 (0.7730)	-0.393	747.11	0.0300	0.155
19.	Tiruvannamalai	0.8880 (0.0408)	2.176	-388.65	0.4864	4.74
20.	Thoothukudi	-0.3367 (0.3613)	-0.932	585.11	0.1480	0.869
21.	Vellore	0.0866 (0.0709)	1.221	-127.52	0.2298	1.49
22.	Villupuram	0.0084 (0.0627)	0.134	236.71	0.0036	0.018
23.	Virudhunagar	0.0853 (0.3166)	0.269	-403.46	0.0143	0.072

* Significant at 5 Per cent Level. Figures in Parentheses are Standard Errors.

It is seen from Table 5.5 that the NPAs of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu have reflected a negative impact on net profit in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the net profit of these banks by -1.3085, -0.4079, -0.2912, -0.3131, -0.6275, -0.4466, -0.0949, -0.3039 and -0.3367 units respectively. But it is statistically significant at the five per cent level only in the Dharmapuri bank. The NPAs were positively influenced by net profit in all the other banks. But the influence is statistically significant only in the Erode and Salem banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in net profit of the Erode and Salem banks by 0.0598 and 1.1469 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination in regression equation under the Erode bank was the maximum of 0.9104. It shows that the changes in the NPAs have explained the changes in the net profit to the maximum extent of 91.04 per cent in the Erode bank. The impact analysis shows that the increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the net profit in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks. This may be due to accounting treatment.

5.7 NPAs (X_{NA}) AND SPREAD (X_{SP})

Spread means the difference between interest earned and interest spent. There is a relationship between NPAs and Spread as the income is received only from Performing Assets. This is indicative of the position that Performing Assets partially make up for the loss of income on account of NPAs. In this study, Spread is taken in absolute terms and is related to the absolute level of NPAs. Taking Spread as the dependent variable and NPAs as the independent variable, a regression model has been constructed to examine the degree of influence of NPAs on spread. The equation is shown in Table 5.6.

TABLE 5.6
IMPACT OF NPAs ON SPREAD

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{NA}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-2.2172 (2.0786)	-1.067	9714.30	0.1854	1.14
2.	Coimbatore	0.2931* (0.0815)	3.594	482.13	0.7210	12.92*
3.	Cuddalore	0.3594* (0.1020)	3.524	373.71	0.7129	12.42*
4.	Dharmapuri	0.0301 (0.0214)	1.409	678.35	0.2842	1.98
5.	Dindigul	0.1788* (0.0605)	2.956	191.75	0.6360	8.74*
6.	Erode	0.4132* (0.0348)	11.867	399.73*	0.9657	140.82*
7.	Kancheepuram	0.3510* (0.0732)	4.797	19.96	0.8215	23.00*
8.	Kanyakumari	0.4297* (0.1577)	2.726	1.760	0.5977	7.43*
9.	Kumbakonam	0.0550 (0.0389)	1.415	581.13	0.2860	2.00
10.	Madurai	0.1045* (0.0187)	5.589	457.19	0.8620	31.24*
11.	Nilgiris	-0.0903 (0.1128)	-0.800	412.96	0.1135	0.6399
12.	Pudukkottai	0.2535* (0.0737)	3.440	-448.55	0.7030	11.83*
13.	Ramanathapuram	0.0497 (0.0750)	0.664	556.13	0.0809	0.440
14.	Salem	0.2697* (0.0368)	7.323	1380.72*	0.9147	53.63*
15.	Sivagangai	0.0465 (0.0612)	0.759	333.77	0.1034	0.577
16.	Thanjavur	0.0250 (0.0510)	0.489	309.20	0.0457	0.240
17.	Thiruchirapalli	0.2360* (0.0311)	7.591	338.88	0.9202	57.62*
18.	Tirunelveli	0.0324 (0.0311)	1.042	317.21*	0.1785	1.09
19.	Tiruvannamalai	0.0510 (0.0466)	1.093	688.80	0.1929	1.20
20.	Thoothukudi	0.1953 (0.0843)	2.315	-713.51	0.5174	5.36
21.	Vellore	0.1894 (0.0805)	2.352	728.64	0.5253	5.53
22.	Villupuram	2.3762 (0.2397)	0.001	1635.10	0.0000	0.0000
23.	Virudhunagar	0.2022* (0.0731)	2.766	128.76*	0.6047	7.65*

* Significant at 5 per cent Level. Figures in parentheses are Standard Errors.

It is evident from Table 5.6 that the NPAs in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu show a negative impact on the spread in the Chennai, and the Nilgiris banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the spread of these banks by -2.2172 and -0.0903 units respectively but it is statistically insignificant at the five per cent level. The impact of the NPAs on the spread is positive in all the other banks and they are statistically significant in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Dindigul, Erode, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli and Virudhunagar banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the spread of these banks by 0.2931 , 0.3594 , 0.1788 , 0.4132 , 0.3510 , 0.4297 , 0.1045 , 0.2535 , 0.2697 , 0.2360 and 0.2022 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9657 is high in the Erode bank, which shows that the changes in the NPAs in the Erode bank have been explained by the changes in the spread to the extent of 96.57 per cent. The impact analysis shows that an increase in NPAs has resulted in an increase in the spread in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai, and the Nilgiris banks.

5.8 OVERDUES (X_{OD}) AND NPAs (X_{NA})

Overdues mean the amount of loan interest or instalments which were due for collection on or before 30th June of the year but were not actually recovered and for the payment of which no extension was granted. A Non-Performing Asset is defined as credit facility in respect of which the interest and or instalment of principal has remained “past due” (overdue) for a specified period of time. An

amount due under any credit facility is treated as 'past due' when it has not been paid within 30 days from the due date. There is a direct relationship between overdues and NPAs. A simple regression equation taking overdues as independent variable and NPAs as dependent variable has been formed. The result is shown in Table 5.7.

TABLE 5.7
IMPACT OF OVERDUE ON NPAs

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{OD}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-0.5067 (0.3553)	-1.426	2354.94*	0.2891	2.03
2.	Coimbatore	0.3225 (0.2139)	1.508	2458.62	0.3126	2.27
3.	Cuddalore	0.3011 (0.2688)	1.120	1370.57	0.2005	1.25
4.	Dharmapuri	0.5474 (0.3584)	1.527	8210.35	0.3182	2.33
5.	Dindigul	1.3640* (0.2294)	5.946	-784.81	0.8761	35.35*
6.	Erode	0.2441 (0.1462)	1.669	1325.61	0.3578	2.79
7.	Kancheepuram	1.1321* (0.3335)	3.394	396.17	0.6974	11.52*
8.	Kanyakumari	0.8943 (0.3576)	2.501	473.06	0.5557	6.25
9.	Kumbakonam	0.6633* (0.2308)	2.873	1554.91	0.6228	8.25*
10.	Madurai	3.0958 (1.3458)	2.300	-2525.81	0.5142	5.29
11.	Nilgiris	1.1961* (0.1472)	8.126	299.78	0.9296	66.03*
12.	Pudukkottai	0.4829 (0.2283)	2.115	1826.15	0.4723	4.47
13.	Ramanathapuram	0.8377 (0.8866)	0.945	2489.38	0.1515	0.89
14.	Salem	1.4984* (0.1708)	8.772	-526.72	0.9390	76.94*
15.	Sivagangai	0.5655 (0.3782)	1.495	2999.54	0.3089	2.23
16.	Thanjavur	0.7325 (0.7027)	1.042	3298.53	0.1785	1.09
17.	Thiruchirapalli	2.0166* (0.4846)	4.162	2579.06	0.7760	17.32*
18.	Tirunelveli	1.0344 (2.2040)	0.469	2341.57	0.0422	0.22
19.	Tiruvannamalai	-0.4693 (1.7467)	-0.269	8837.09	0.0142	0.07
20.	Thoothukudi	3.1682 (1.7075)	1.855	-515.34	0.4078	3.44
21.	Vellore	0.4954* (0.0834)	5.940	1205.81*	0.8759	35.28*
22.	Villupuram	0.7517 (0.2967)	2.534	1612.69	0.5622	6.42
23.	Virudhunagar	0.5039 (1.5167)	0.332	2112.61	0.0216	0.110

* Significant at 5 per cent Level. Figures in parentheses are Standard Errors.

It is evident from Table 5.7 that the overdues of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu show a negative influence on NPAs in the Chennai and Tiruvannamalai banks. A unit of increase in the overdues has resulted in a decrease in NPAs of the Chennai and Tiruvannamalai banks by -0.5067 units and -0.4693 units respectively. It is statistically not significant at the five per cent level. The overdues have a positive influence on NPAs in all the other banks. But they are statistically significant only in the Dindigul, Kancheepuram, Kumbakonam, Nilgiris, Salem, Thiruchirapalli and Vellore banks. A unit of increase in the overdues has resulted in an increase in NPAs of these banks by 1.3640, 1.1321, 0.6633, 1.1961, 1.4984, 2.0166 and 0.4954 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination in the regression equation under the Salem bank was maximum at 0.9390. It shows that the changes in the overdues have explained the changes in the NPAs to the maximum extent of 93.90 per cent in the Salem bank. The impact analysis shows that the increase in overdues has resulted in an increase in NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai and Tiruvannamalai banks.

5.9 NPAs (X_{NA}) AND RECOVERY (X_{RV})

The recovery of loans is an important factor for the sound functioning of the DCC Banks. Timely recovery of loans strengthens the resource position of the DCC Banks and enables them to repay the loans to the apex bank in time. The poor recovery of loans leads to adverse effects on the functioning of the DCC Banks resulting in increased NPAs. To examine this, regression co-efficient taking recovery as dependent variable and NPAs as independent variable has been formed. The result of the simple regression analysis is shown in Table 5.8.

TABLE 5.8
IMPACT OF NPAs ON RECOVERY

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{NA}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	-101.63* (21.33)	-4.765	202910.89*	0.8195	22.70*
2.	Coimbatore	1.2138* (0.3769)	3.220	6066.01*	0.6747	10.37*
3.	Cuddalore	3.9489* (1.0669)	3.701	7644.36*	0.7326	13.70*
4.	Dharmapuri	0.4499 (0.4326)	1.040	9190.39	0.1778	1.08
5.	Dindigul	0.8216 (0.5607)	1.465	6769.93	0.3004	2.15
6.	Erode	4.1958* (0.7069)	5.936	7644.61*	0.8757	35.23*
7.	Kancheepuram	1.6663* (0.4432)	3.760	2928.34	0.7387	14.14*
8.	Kanyakumari	9.3741* (1.3026)	7.197	-1694.68	0.9120	51.79*
9.	Kumbakonam	0.0687 (0.8934)	0.077	10106.68	0.0012	0.01
10.	Madurai	0.4643 (0.2337)	1.986	4070.57	0.4411	3.95
11.	Nilgiris	0.6307 (0.7957)	0.793	1854.22	0.1116	0.63
12.	Pudukkottai	4.2192 (1.8167)	2.323	-3080.20	0.5190	5.39
13.	Ramanathapuram	0.9552 (0.8986)	1.063	1300.54	0.1844	1.13
14.	Salem	1.4870* (0.2747)	5.413	10977.93*	0.8542	29.30*
15.	Sivagangai	2.6175 (1.7902)	1.462	-3352.25	0.2995	2.14
16.	Thanjavur	-0.0090 (0.3688)	-0.024	4188.84	0.0001	0.001
17.	Thiruchirapalli	1.0224 (0.5066)	2.018	10294.19	0.4489	4.07
18.	Tirunelveli	0.9252 (0.4782)	1.935	2256.40	0.4281	3.74
19.	Tiruvannamalai	0.3764 (0.2635)	1.428	5464.38*	0.2898	2.04
20.	Thoothukudi	0.6296* (0.2370)	2.657	2296.29	0.5853	7.06*
21.	Vellore	0.6791 (1.1902)	0.571	8174.31	0.0611	0.33
22.	Villupuram	2.0933 (1.9087)	1.097	2889.66	0.1939	1.20
23.	Virudhunagar	1.0874* (0.4198)	2.590	2985.94	0.5730	6.71*

* Significant at 5 per cent Level. Figures in parentheses are Standard Errors.

Table 5.8 shows that the impact of NPAs on recovery in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu was negative in the Chennai and Thanjavur banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in recovery of overdues of these banks by -101.63 units and -0.0090 units respectively during the study period, while it is statistically significant at the five per cent level only in the Chennai bank. The impact of NPAs on recovery was positive in all the other DCCBs, but statistically significant in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Erode, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Salem, Thoothukudi and Virudhunagar banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the recovery of overdues of these banks by 1.2138, 3.9489, 4.1958, 1.6663, 9.3741, 1.4870, 0.6296 and 1.0874 units respectively. The co-efficient of determination in the regression equation of the Kanyakumari bank shows that the changes in NPAs have explained the changes in the recovery to the extent of 91.20 per cent. The impact analysis shows that the increase in NPAs has resulted in an increase in the recovery of overdues in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai and Thanjavur banks.

5.10 SPREAD (X_{SP}) AND NET PROFIT (X_{NP})

The mutual impact between the spread and net profit in the DCCBs has been examined with the help of regression analysis. Initially, the net profit was considered a dependent variable and the spread was treated as the independent variable. After that, the spread was treated as dependent variable and the net profit as independent variable. The fitted regression model is

I)

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + e$$

Whereas

$$Y = \text{Net Profit}$$

$$X_1 = \text{Spread}$$

b_1 = Regression Co-efficient of independent variable.

a = Intercept and

e = Error term.

II)

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + e$$

Whereas

$$Y = \text{Spread}$$

$$X_1 = \text{Net profit}$$

b_1 = Regression Co-efficient of Independent variable

a = Intercept and

e = Error term.

The results have been presented in Table 5.9.

TABLE 5.9
IMPACT OF SPREAD ON NET PROFIT

Sl. No.	Name of the DCC Bank	Regression Co-efficient X_{SP}	t-Statistics	Constant	R ²	F
1.	Chennai	0.7859* (0.1242)	6.328	-578.49	0.8890	40.04*
2.	Coimbatore	0.3181 (0.1378)	2.309	-393.53	0.5160	5.33
3.	Cuddalore	0.2821 (0.1248)	2.260	-286.91	0.5053	5.11
4.	Dharmapuri	-5.916 (2.6216)	-2.257	4814.66	0.5046	5.09
5.	Dindigul	0.1420 (1.1034)	0.129	-296.01	0.0033	0.017
6.	Erode	0.1421* (0.0201)	7.065	-28.99	0.9090	49.91*
7.	Kancheepuram	0.0310 (0.0290)	1.072	25.864	0.1869	1.15
8.	Kanyakumari	0.3936 (0.2499)	1.575	-143.52	0.3315	2.48
9.	Kumbakonam	2.9386 (3.4531)	0.851	-3066.48	0.1265	0.724
10.	Madurai	0.1779 (0.2778)	0.640	-554.09	0.0758	0.410
11.	Nilgiris	-0.6684 (0.5431)	-1.231	232.64	0.2325	1.51
12.	Pudukkottai	0.2579 (0.2272)	1.135	-9.3823	0.2050	1.29
13.	Ramanathapuram	2.3006 (2.2409)	1.027	-2747.05	0.1741	1.05
14.	Salem	4.2614* (0.8424)	5.058	-8724.19*	0.8365	25.59*
15.	Sivagangai	2.7994 (2.4408)	1.147	-1741.19	0.2083	1.32
16.	Thanjavur	3.1001 (1.9176)	1.617	-1562.51	0.3433	2.61
17.	Thiruchirapalli	0.5244 (0.2937)	1.785	-1046.63	0.3893	3.19
18.	Tirunelveli	-9.0546 (9.4036)	-0.963	3577.99	0.1564	0.927
19.	Tiruvannamalai	0.9496* (0.2455)	3.867	-778.74*	0.7495	14.96*
20.	Thoothukudi	0.0488 (1.4417)	0.034	-618.70	0.0002	0.001
21.	Vellore	0.5028 (0.2119)	2.373	-522.28	0.5297	5.63
22.	Villupuram	-0.0224 (0.1168)	-0.192	310.21	0.0073	0.037
23.	Virudhunagar	1.4249 (1.0483)	1.359	-1192.98	0.2698	1.85

* Significant at 5 per cent Level. Figures in parentheses are Standard Errors.

It could be seen from Table 5.9 that there has been a negative impact of spread in the DCCBs on net profit in the Dharmapuri, Nilgiris, Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks. A unit of increase in the spread has resulted in a decrease in net profit of these banks by -5.9164, -0.6684, -9.0546 and -0.0224 units respectively. It is statistically not significant at the five per cent level. There has been a positive relationship between them in all the other DCC banks. But it is statistically significant only in the Chennai, Erode, Salem and Tiruvannamalai banks. A unit of increase in the spread has resulted in an increase in the net profit of these banks by 0.7859, 0.1421, 4.2614 and 0.9496 units respectively. The coefficient of determination was the maximum of 0.9090 in the Erode bank. It shows that the changes in the spread have explained the changes in the net profit to the maximum extent of 90.90 per cent. The impact analysis shows that an increase in the spread has resulted in an increase in net profit in all the DCCBs except in the Dharmapuri, Nilgiris Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks.

5.11 FACTORS INFLUENCING NET PROFIT OF DCC BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

This section discusses the impact of the various factors such as gross NPAs, overdues, advances, legal expenses and spread on the net profit of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu with the help of a multiple regression model.

In this model, the value of Net Profit was taken as a dependent variable and variables such as Gross NPAs, Overdues, Advances, Legal Expenses and Spread

were considered independent variables. This model focused on all the 23 DCCBs totally.

Initially the correlation co-efficients were worked out to study the relationship between Net Profit and other variables totally for all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu.

The inter-relationship between the variables is shown in Table 5.10.

TABLE 5.10
INTER-CORRELATION MATRIX IN ALL DCCBS IN TAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Name of the Variable	Net Profit	NPAs	Over Dues	Advances	Legal Expenses	Spread
1.	Net Profit	1.0000	-0.2566	-0.4904	0.2734	0.2046	0.2414
2.	NPAs		1.0000	0.8972*	0.8379*	0.8725*	0.8703*
3.	Over dues			1.0000	0.6482	0.6507	0.6829
4.	Advances				1.0000	0.9466*	0.9830*
5.	Legal Expenses					1.0000	0.9577*

* Significant at 5 per cent level.

Table 5.10 shows a significant and positive relationship in the case of NPAs, with overdues, advances, legal expenses and spread with the correlation co-efficients of 0.8972, 0.8379, 0.8725 and 0.8703 respectively. It indicates that these variables are associated with higher NPAs. Advances is positively and significantly correlated with the variables legal expenses and spread. A negative

relationship exists between net profit and NPAs and net profit and overdues since the correlation co-efficients are -0.2566 and -0.4904 which are statistically insignificant. The analysis shows that a higher spread is positively and significantly associated with higher NPAs, advances and legal expenses.

In order to find the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable in all the DCCBs a multiple regression model was applied. The fitted regression model is

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + b_5 X_5 + e$$

Where as

Y = Net Profit

X_1 = Gross NPAs

X_2 = Overdues

X_3 = Advances

X_4 = Legal Expenses

X_5 = Spread

b_1 b_5 = Regression Co-efficient

a = Intercept and

e = Error Term.

The result of the multiple regression analysis is shown in Table 5.11.

TABLE 5.11
IMPACT OF INDEPENDENT VARIABLES ON NET PROFIT IN ALL
DCCBs INTAMIL NADU

Sl. No.	Independent Variable	Regression Coefficient	Standard Error Coefficient	t-Statistics
1.	NPAs	-0.5170*	0.0042	-124.418
2.	Overdues	-0.1311*	0.0033	-40.247
3.	Advances	-0.0052	0.0018	-2.833
4.	Legal Expenses	1621.24*	46.1629	35.120
5.	Spread	2.2248*	0.0273	81.630
	Constant	-20955.66*	540.08	-38.801
	R ²	0.9999		
	F	25161.55*		
	D.W.	1.9425		

* Significant at 5 per cent level.

It is seen from Table 5.11 that the independent variables namely legal expenses and spread in all DCCBs in Tamil Nadu had a positive and significant impact on the net profit of the banks during the study period as the 't' values are significant at the five per cent level. It is inferred that a unit change in the value of legal expenses and spread leads to an increase of 1621.24 and 2.2248 units in the net profit of the banks. The regression co-efficients of NPAs, overdues and advances on Net profit in all the DCCBs are negative with -0.5170, -0.1311 and

-0.0052 respectively. It shows that the impact of these variables is negative but statistically significant only in NPAs and overdues.

The co-efficient of determination of 0.9999 shows that the change in the net profit in all DCCBs is explained by the independent variable to the extent of 99.99 per cent. The fitted regression model for the analysis is also significant at the five per cent level since its F value and Durbin Watson co-efficients are 25161.55 and 1.9425 respectively.

5.12 CONCLUSION

The impact of the NPAs on various performance variable in the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu was measured with the help of the correlation coefficient and multiple regression. The positive impact of the gross advances on the NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai bank has been found. But it is not statistically significant. The positive and significant impact of gross advances on NPAs have been identified in the DCCBs at the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Dindigul, Erode, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks.

The negative impact of the standard assets on the NPAs was found in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Thanjavur and Tiruvannamalai banks. It is statistically not significant at the five per cent level. The standard assets have a significant positive impact on the NPAs in the DCCBs at the

Coimbatore, Erode, Kanyakumari, Salem and Thiruchirapalli banks. The co-efficient of variation in the established regression equation varied from 90.23 per cent in the Erode bank to 0.16 per cent in the Ramanathapuram bank.

The influence of NPAs on investments in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu was negative in the Chennai, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks, but it is statistically insignificant. The positive influences of NPAs on investments were noticed in all the other DCCBs. It was significant at the five per cent level in the Kanyakumari and Pudukkottai banks. The co-efficient of determination was maximum of 0.7759 in the Kanyakumari bank.

The impact of NPAs on the legal expenses of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu was negative and insignificant in the Chennai, Dindigul, Kanyakumari, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Thiruchirapalli and Villupuram banks. The impact of NPAs on the legal expenses was positive in all the other DCCBs but it was statistically significant only in the Tirunelveli and Tiruvannamalai banks.

The NPAs of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed negative influences on the net profit in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks. It is statistically significant only in the Dharmapuri bank. In all the other DCCBs positive influences of NPAs on net profit have been found.

There were positive influences of NPAs on the spread in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu except in the Chennai and Nilgiris banks. The influences of NPAs on the spread were negative and insignificant only in the Chennai and Nilgiris banks.

The overdues of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed negative and insignificant impact on the NPAs in the Chennai and Tiruvannamalai banks. The overdues have a positive impact on NPAs in all the other DCCBs.

There has been a negative influence of NPAs on recovery in the Chennai and Thanjavur DCC banks. It is statistically significant at the five per cent level only in the Chennai bank. The influence of the NPA is positive in all the other DCCBs.

The spread of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu shows negative and insignificant impact on net profit in the Dharmapuri, Nilgiris, Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks. The spread has a positive impact on the net profit in all the other DCCBs.

Positive and significant correlation co-efficients were noted in the case of NPAs, with overdues, advances, legal expenses and spread. The advances correlated positively and significantly with legal expenses and spread. The negative and insignificant correlations between Net Profit and NPAs and Net Profit and overdues were found.

The positive and significant impacts of the variables such as legal expenses and spread on the net profit in all the DCCBs were found. The negative impact on net profit was found with regard to NPAs, overdues and advances. The impact analysis shows a comparatively good position in the Chennai bank only.

CHAPTER VI

PERCEPTION OF OFFICIALS ON NPAs IN DCC BANKS

IN TAMIL NADU

The opinion of bank officials connected with the banking system on the implications of NPAs of DCC Banks was ascertained by means of questionnaires. The questionnaires were mailed to 414 officials of all the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu. The study covers three categories of officials those belonging to Top level Management (Special Officer/Managing Director, General Manager and Executive Officers), Middle level Management (Assistant General Manager of Administration, Banking, Development, Agri-Credit and other Industrial credit) and Lower level Management (Managers of Administration, Banking, Development, Agri-credit and other Industrial Credit). Opinions of officials of all the DCC Banks of Tamil Nadu were sought from the angle of the regulator and supervisor of a branch to understand more about the problem of Non-performing Assets. The data for this chapter thus consist of the views expressed by the 322 completed questionnaires received from officials of all the DCC Banks in Tamil Nadu, chosen for the study. The views were given in their personal and individual capacity and need not be taken as views reflecting those of their banks.

This chapter deals with two parts, namely perception of officials on NPAs and their suggestions for reducing NPAs.

PART – A

The perception of officials on NPAs is assessed through factor analysis. It has been analysed from the point of view of banking operation, borrowers and general reasons. Accordingly statements have been framed in the questionnaires soliciting opinions on NPAs and their implications.

In order to study the perception of officials, the opinions on various statements have been grouped under different titles (vide Appendix A) and they were classified using Likert's five point scale. The five point scale consists of 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'no opinion', 'disagree' and 'strongly disagree'. The score of each statement in the five point scale carries five, four, three, two and one mark respectively.

In the present study, the principal components factor analysis method with Orthogonal Varimax Rotation is used to identify the officials' perception of NPAs in DCCBs. The significance of Eigen value and communality has been highlighted in the framework of analysis (2.2.8.5.)

6.1 IMPORTANT REASONS FOR HIGHER NPAs IN BANKS

6.1.1 Bank Related Reasons for Higher NPAs in Banks

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 13 dimensions of the bank related reasons for higher NPAs in banks and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax criteria. The data validity for factor analysis has been examined with the help of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measures of sampling adequacy and the Bartlett Test of Sphericity. The KMO measure of 0.45573 and zero level significance of the chi-square satisfy the validity of data for factor analysis. The factor analysis has resulted in the selection of seven factors. The factor loading of the variables in seven factors, its communality, eigenvalue and percentage of variation are shown in Table 6.1.

TABLE 6.1
ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX SHOWING BANK RELATED REASONS FOR
HIGHER NPAs IN DCCBs

Sl. No.	Variables	Rotated Factor Loading							H ²
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	
1.	Lack of proper pre-sanction appraisal of credit proposal	0.6906	0.2194	0.1998	0.1415	0.2119	0.0148	0.0033	0.6303
2.	Siphoning of funds	0.6599	0.2137	0.1054	0.0257	0.2540	0.1023	0.1580	0.5930
3.	Deficiencies in post-credit supervision	0.5854	0.2330	0.2884	0.1693	0.0735	0.0472	0.0877	0.5859
4.	Over/Under financing of project	0.0278	0.7202	0.0761	0.2146	0.1097	0.2858	0.0826	0.6719
5.	Lack of professionalism of bank's board	0.2169	0.7043	0.0904	0.0372	0.1424	0.0435	0.0979	0.5845
6.	Fear psychosis among banks for compromise settlements	0.3922	0.4633	0.2089	0.1306	0.2420	0.3058	0.0672	0.5859
7.	Poor auditing practices	0.0379	0.1326	0.7468	0.1013	0.0106	0.1634	0.2058	0.6558
8.	Direct lending by bank to priority sector	0.1523	0.2137	0.6947	0.1074	0.0158	0.0876	0.3759	0.7126
9.	Long interval between sanction and disbursement of loans	0.0673	0.0340	0.1567	0.8064	0.1629	0.2382	0.0471	0.7661
10.	Lack of proper co-ordination between various financial institutions and banks	0.0955	0.0869	0.1882	0.6868	0.3169	0.3223	0.1198	0.7426
11.	Low skill of the officials in processing loan proposals	0.0500	0.0812	0.0049	0.0064	0.9097	0.0255	0.0311	0.8383
12.	Non-adoption of K.Y.C. Norms	0.0480	0.0896	0.1059	0.0586	0.0204	0.8687	0.0163	0.7804
13.	Lack of supervision and follow-up action	0.0203	0.0353	0.0183	0.0360	0.0171	0.0002	0.9251	0.8595
	EigenValues	1.7500	1.4773	1.2797	1.2433	1.1621	1.0204	1.012	
	% of Variation	13.50	11.40	9.80	9.60	8.90	7.80	7.80	
	Cumulative percentage	13.50	24.90	34.70	44.30	53.20	61.00	68.80	

Factor 1

This factor consists of the variables namely, 'lack of proper pre-sanction appraisal of credit proposal', 'siphoning of funds' and 'deficiencies in post-credit supervision.' The matrix for these variables showed the values of 0.6906, 0.6599 and 0.5854 respectively. As the above variables related to credit proposal, fund and credit supervision are important bank related reasons for higher NPAs in banks. Factor one is characterised as the perception of the officials on 'credit and fund related reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation were 1.75 and 13.50 per cent respectively.

Factor 2

This factor consists of the variables namely, 'over/under financing of project' and 'lack of professionalism of bank's board' with factor loading values of 0.7202 and 0.7043 respectively. These variables represent financing and professionalism related reasons for higher NPAs in banks. It could be noted that 'fear psychosis among banks for compromise settlements' has not been considered for the explanation of the second factor, as its factor loading is 0.4633 which is less than 0.5. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by these factors were 1.48 and 11.40 per cent respectively.

Factor 3

The third factor consists of the variables namely, 'poor auditing practices' and 'direct lending by banks to priority sector' with factor loading values of 0.7468 and 0.6947 respectively. Since these variables represent auditing and lending related reasons for higher NPAs in banks, the third factor is called 'auditing and lending related reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by these factor were 1.28 and 9.80 per cent respectively.

Factor 4

This factor consists of the variables namely, 'long interval between sanction and disbursements of loans' and 'lack of proper co-ordination between various financial institutions and banks' with factor loading values of 0.8064 and 0.6868 respectively. Factor four can be named as 'time and co-ordination related reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by these factors 1.24 and 9.60 per cent respectively.

Factor 5

The fifth factor consists of only one variable - 'low skill of the officials in processing loan proposals' which had a factor loading of 0.9097. This factor has been named 'skill of the officials'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.16 and 8.90 per cent respectively.

Factor 6

The sixth factor consists of only one variable: non-adoption of 'know your customer (K.Y.C.) norms' with factor loadings of 0.8687. On the basis of this variable, factor 6 has been named 'K.Y.C. norms'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation explained by this factor were 1.02 and 7.8 per cent respectively.

Factor 7

The seventh factor consists of only one variable: 'Lack of supervision and follow-up action' with factor loading of 0.9251. On the basis of this variable, the seventh factor has been named 'supervision and follow-up action'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation explained by this factor were 1.01 and 7.80 per cent respectively.

Communality

Communality represents the extent of influence of a particular variable on all the factors together. It shows that the highest communality value was noticed pertaining to the variables namely 'lack of supervision and follow-up action', 'low skill of the officials in processing the loan proposals', 'non-adoption of K.Y.C. norms', 'long period between sanction and disbursement of loans' with 0.8595, 0.8383, 0.7804 and 0.7661 respectively.

6.1.2 Borrower Related Reasons for Higher NPAs in Banks

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 13 dimensions of the borrower related reasons for higher NPAs in banks and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax criteria. The data validity for factor analysis has been examined with the help of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and the Bartlett Test of Sphericity. The KMO measure of 0.65024 and zero level significance of the chi-square satisfy the validity of data for factor analysis. The factor analysis has helped to identify five factors for further analysis. The factor loading of the variables in the five factors, their communality, eigenvalue and percentage of variation explained are shown in Table 6.2.

TABLE 6.2

**ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX SHOWING BORROWERS RELATED
REASONS FOR HIGHER NPAs IN DCCBs**

Sl. No.	Variables	Rotated Factor Loading					h ²
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	
1.	Non-monitoring bank's accounts	0.8184	0.0596	0.1245	0.0941	0.0687	0.7026
2.	Unauthorized withdrawal of funds from bank A/c	0.7623	0.1206	0.3668	0.0346	0.1395	0.7509
3.	Time/cost overrun of project	0.5284	0.2899	0.0271	0.1435	0.4647	0.6006
4.	Lower Rate of interest	0.1549	0.8101	0.1294	0.0315	0.0764	0.7039
5.	Higher Rate of interest	0.0441	0.6734	0.2559	0.1784	0.1233	0.5681
6.	Diversion of funds	0.0827	0.6035	0.0230	0.3383	0.1511	0.5090
7.	Lack of proper project planning	0.0842	0.1711	0.7632	0.0189	0.1036	0.6299
8.	Inefficient financial management	0.0595	0.3294	0.6849	0.0837	0.1619	0.6145
9.	In appropriate technology	0.4538	0.0839	0.6761	0.0472	0.2662	0.7433
10.	Natural calamities like floods and accidents	0.1029	0.0573	0.0801	0.8054	0.1011	0.6794
11.	Adoption of lenient approach on defaults	0.1615	0.0017	0.0093	0.7155	0.1333	0.5560
12.	No demand for security	0.3207	0.2549	0.1459	0.5667	0.4693	0.7095
13.	Deficiency in credit appraisal standards	0.0699	0.1775	0.0865	0.0118	0.7954	0.6768
	EigenValues	2.8655	1.7532	1.5875	1.1519	1.0865	
	% of variation	22.00	13.50	12.20	8.90	8.40	
	Cumulative Percentage	22.00	35.50	47.70	56.60	65.00	

Factor 1

From the first factor it can be seen that the variables namely, 'non monitoring of banks accounts', 'unauthorised withdrawal of funds from bank A/C' and 'time/cost overrun of project' have factor loadings of 0.8184, 0.7623 and 0.5284 respectively. Since this factor is concerned with the bank accounts and time/cost, it can be named 'bank accounts and time/cost related reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 2.7 and 22 per cent respectively.

Factor 2

This factor consists of the variables namely, 'lower rate of interest', 'higher rate of interest' and 'diversion of funds' which have factor loadings of 0.8101, 0.6734 and 0.6035 respectively. Since this second factor is concentrated on the rate of interest and funds related reasons, it can be named 'interest rate and funds related reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.75 and 13.50 per cent respectively.

Factor 3

This factor consists of the variables namely, 'lack of proper project planning', 'inefficient financial management' and 'inappropriate technology' which have factor loadings of 0.7632, 0.6849 and 0.6761 respectively. Since this

third factor is concentrated on the planning, financial and technology related reason, it can be named 'planning, finance and technology related reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.59 and 12.20 per cent respectively.

Factor 4

The fourth factor consists of the variables namely 'natural calamities like floods and accidents', 'adoption of lenient approach on defaults' and 'no demand for security' which have loading values of 0.8054, 0.7155 and 0.5667 respectively. Since this factor is concentrated on the natural calamities, lenient approach and demand for security related reasons, it can be named 'calamities, lenient and demand related reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.15 and 8.90 per cent respectively.

Factor 5

The fifth factor consists of only one variable that is 'deficiency in credit appraisal standards' which has a loading factor of 0.7954. On the basis of this variable, the fifth factor has been named 'credit appraisal standards'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.08 and 8.40 percent respectively.

Communality

It represents the extend of influence of a particular variable on all the factors together. It shows that the highest communality value pertaining to the variables namely ‘unauthorised withdrawal of funds from bank account’ and ‘in appropriate technology’ were 0.7509 and 0.7433 respectively.

6.1.3 General Reasons for Higher NPAs in Banks

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of nine dimensions of the General Reasons for higher NPAs in banks and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax criteria. The validity for factor analysis has been examined with the help of the Kaiser-Meyer–Olkin Bartlett Test of Sphericity. The KMO measure of 0.48574 and zero level significance of the chi-square satisfy the validity of data for factor analysis. The factor analysis has helped identify four factors. The factor loadings of the variables in the four factors, its communality, eigenvalue and percentage of variation are shown in Table 6.3.

TABLE 6.3
ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX FOR IMPORTANT GENERAL REASONS FOR
HIGHER NPAs IN DCCBs

Sl. No.	Variables	Rotated Factor Loadings				h ²
		F1	F2	F3	F4	
1.	Slow legal process for recovery of bank dues	0.8066	0.0874	0.1262	0.1332	0.6920
2.	Lack of legal support through exemption to certain category	0.7367	0.1315	0.0929	0.1409	0.5886
3.	Liberalisation/operating of economy throwing new challenges	0.0908	0.6846	0.0236	0.0044	0.4775
4.	Industrial sickness and labour problem	0.0390	0.6459	0.1581	0.2522	0.5074
5.	Product/marketing failure	0.1896	0.5166	0.2983	0.4886	0.6307
6.	Liberalisation of government policies	0.1862	0.0479	0.7491	0.0393	0.5997
7.	Boom/depression of capital market	0.3173	0.1268	0.6840	0.0750	0.5904
8.	Political interference	0.0896	0.0698	0.0294	0.7261	0.5411
9.	Slow function of judiciary including DRTs and BIFR	0.3048	0.1695	0.2076	0.5674	0.4868
	EigenValues	1.5322	1.2796	1.1641	1.1386	
	% of Variation	17.00	14.20	12.90	12.70	
	Cumulative Percentage	17.00	31.20	44.10	56.80	

Factor 1

In the first factor variables namely, ‘slow legal process for recovery of bank dues’ and ‘lack of legal support through exemption to certain category’ have

been identified which have loadings of 0.8066 and 0.7367 respectively. As these variables are related to legal process and legal support, the first factor can be termed as 'legal reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.53 and 17 per cent respectively.

Factor 2

The second factor consists of the variables namely, 'liberalisation/operating of economy throwing new challenges', 'industrial sickness and labour problem' and 'product/marketing failure' which have factor loadings of 0.6846, 0.06459 and 0.5166 respectively. As the variables represent challenges, problem and failure related reasons, factor second can be termed 'challenges, problem and failure related reasons'. The eigenvalue and percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.28 and 14.20 per cent respectively.

Factor 3

Factor three consists of the variables namely, 'liberalisation government policies' and 'boom/depression of capital market' which have factor loadings of 0.7491 and 0.6840 respectively. Factor three can be called 'Government Policies and capital market related reasons'. The eigenvalue and percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.16 and 12.90 per cent respectively.

Factor 4

This factor consists of the variables namely 'political interference' and 'slow functioning of judiciary including DRTs and BIFR' which have factor loadings of 0.7261 and 0.5674 respectively. On the basis of these variables, factor fourth has been named 'political and legal reasons'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.14 and 12.70 per cent respectively.

Communality

It represents the extent of influence of a particular variable on all the factors together. It shows that the highest communality value pertaining to the variables namely 'slow legal process for recovery of bank dues' and product/marketing failure' were 0.6920 and 0.6307 respectively.

6.2. OPINION ON SUPPORT SYSTEM RELATING TO NPAs

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of seven dimensions of the statements on the support system causing NPAs and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax criteria. The data validity for factor analysis has been examined with the help of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and the Bartlett Test of Sphericity. The KMO measure of 0.53624 and zero level significance of the chi-square

satisfy the validity of data for factor analysis. The factor analysis has identified three factors. The factor loading of the variables, its communality, eigenvalue and percentage of variation are shown in Table 6.4.

TABLE 6.4
ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX FOR STATEMENT OF OPINIONS ON
SUPPORT SYSTEM RELATING TO NPAs

Sl. No.	Variables	Rotated Factor Loadings			h ²
		F1	F2	F3	
1.	Inadequate staff to manage loan portfolio	0.7815	0.0993	0.1622	0.6469
2.	Interest rates not fixed according to borrowers' repaying capacity	0.7381	0.1281	0.0429	0.5632
3.	Banks have no system of exchange of information on borrower customers'	0.6353	0.1396	0.2089	0.4668
4.	Banks do not pay adequate attention to borrowers	0.0797	0.7860	0.1599	0.6499
5.	Inadequate credit information is an important cause of NPAs	0.0708	0.7468	0.2502	0.6263
6.	Apex bodies like RBI / NABARD / RCS / TNSCB etc. do not support banks in the recovery of dues	0.1364	0.1426	0.8140	0.7016
7.	Banks do not have effective intelligence system to find more about the borrowers	0.0975	0.1699	0.5656	0.6263
	EigenValues	1.6940	1.2025	1.1166	
	% of Variation	24.20	17.20	16.00	
	Cumulative percentage	24.20	41.40	57.40	

Factor 1

In this first factor, three variables namely, 'inadequate staff to manage loan portfolio', 'interest rates are not fixed according to borrowers repaying capacity' and 'banks have no system of exchange of information on borrower customers' have been grouped which have factor loadings of 0.7815, 0.7381 and 0.6353 respectively. Since this factor is concentrated on the staff managing the loan portfolio, borrowers repaying capacity and no system of exchange of information about borrower, it can be named 'loan portfolio, repaying capacity and exchange of information'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.69 and 24.20 per cent respectively.

Factor 2

There are two variables namely, 'banks do not pay adequate attention to borrowers' and 'inadequate credit information an important cause of NPAs' which have factor loadings of 0.7860 and 0.7468 respectively. These variables have been characterised as 'inadequate attention and inadequate information'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused in this factor were 1.20 and 17.20 per cent respectively.

Factor 3

In the third factor two variables - 'apex bodies like RBI/NABARD/ RCS/ TNSCB etc., do not support banks in the recovery of dues' and 'banks do not have effective intelligence system to find more about the borrowers' - have been grouped which have factor loadings of 0.8140 and 0.5656 respectively. The variables have been characterised as 'apex bodies do not support the recovery of dues and banks do not know more about the borrowers'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.12 and 16 per cent respectively.

Communality

It represents the extend of influence of a particular variable on all the factors together. It shows that the highest communality values pertaining to the variables namely 'apex bodies like RBI/NABARD/RCS/TNSCB etc., do not support banks in the recovery of dues', 'banks do not pay adequate attention to borrowers' and 'inadequate staff to manage loan port folio' were 0.7016, 0.6499 and 0.6469 respectively.

6.3 OPINION ON NPAs AND THEIR IMPLICATION ON BANKING PRACTICES

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 12 dimensions of the statements of opinion on the implications of NPAs to banking system and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax criteria. The data validity for factor analysis has been examined with the help of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and the Bartlett Test of Sphericity. The KMO measure of 0.50155 and zero level significance of the chi-square satisfy the validity of data for factor analysis. The factor analysis has identified six factors. The factor loading of the variables in the six factors, its communality, eigenvalue and the percentage of variation are shown in Table 6.5.

TABLE 6.5
ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX FOR STATEMENT OF OPINIONS ON NPAs
AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS ON BANKING PRACTICES

Sl. No.	Variables	Rotated Factor Loadings						h ²
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	
1.	NPAs affect banks and other stake holders other than defaulting borrowers	0.7168	0.0751	0.1096	0.0316	0.0943	0.0446	0.5434
2.	Banks have a general aversion to lending because of NPAs	0.6912	0.0509	0.1513	0.0286	0.3300	0.0131	0.6133
3.	Banks raise subordinated debt at high cost to supplement tier II capital and to meet capital adequacy norms	0.0487	0.7489	0.0395	0.1066	0.0823	0.0728	0.5883
4.	Banks are unable to bring down interest rate on accounts of NPAs	0.1392	0.6420	0.1289	0.1567	0.3447	0.2624	0.6606
5.	Interest charge to borrowers far exceeds the declared PLR	0.3110	0.5386	0.1398	0.0378	0.1191	0.3787	0.5655
6.	Overall cost of borrowers very high resulting in NPAs	0.0416	0.0411	0.7922	0.0592	0.0296	0.0217	0.6359
7.	Loan to agriculture and SSI sector reduced	0.1487	0.1475	0.5658	0.3947	0.4089	0.0602	0.6907
8.	Banks prefer investment in Govt. securities to advances because of NPAs	0.4471	0.2375	0.4700	0.0648	0.1706	0.1007	0.5208
9.	Personal loan to business people decreased	0.0038	0.0038	0.0632	0.8556	0.1358	0.1307	0.7718
10.	Loan to self help group (SHG) decreased	0.5659	0.0142	0.0201	0.1084	0.8425	0.0405	0.7271
11.	Present capital adequacy norms can reduce / minimise the risk of NPAs for banks	0.0609	0.1195	0.2274	0.2182	0.0137	0.7381	0.6624
12.	Loans to small business under micro credit scheme decreased	0.2107	0.0286	0.2543	0.5008	0.1352	0.5886	0.7256
	EigenValues	1.6721	1.3981	1.2910	1.1841	1.1367	1.0232	
	% of variation	13.90	11.70	10.80	9.90	9.50	8.50	
	Cumulative Percentage	13.90	25.60	36.40	46.30	55.80	64.30	

Factor 1

This factor consists of two variables namely, 'NPAs affect banks and other stake holders other than defaulting borrowers' and 'banks have a general aversion to lending because of NPAs' which have factor loadings of 0.7168 and 0.6912 respectively. These variables have been characterised as 'NPAs affect banks and aversion to lending because of NPAs'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.67 and 13.90 per cent respectively.

Factor 2

This factor consists of three variables namely, 'banks raised subordinated debt at high cost to supplement Tier II capital and to meet capital adequacy norms', 'banks are unable to bring down interest rate on account of NPAs' and 'interest charged to borrowers far exceeds the declared PLR' which have factor loadings 0.7489, 0.6420 and 0.5386 respectively. These variables put together can be named 'capital adequacy, interest rate and interest charged'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.40 and 11.70 per cent respectively.

Factor 3

The third factor consists of variables namely, 'overall cost of borrowers very high resulting in NPAs' and 'loan to agriculture and SSI sector reduced'

which have factor loadings of 0.7922, 0.5658 respectively. These variables have been characterised as ‘overall cost of borrowers and loan to agriculture and SSI’. It is also to be noted that ‘banks prefer investment in Government securities to advances because of NPAs’ is not considered for inclusion in the factor as its factor loading was 0.4700 which is less than 0.5. The eigen value and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.29 and 10.80 per cent respectively.

Factor 4

The fourth factor consists of only one variable - ‘personal loan to business people decreased’ - which has a factor loading of 0.8556. The fourth factor has been named ‘loan to business people’. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.18 and 9.90 per cent respectively.

Factor 5

The fifth factor consists of only one variable - ‘loan to self help group (SHG) decreased’ which has a factor loading of 0.8425. On the basis of this variable the fifth factor has been named ‘loan to SHG’. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.14 and 9.50 per cent respectively.

Factor 6

This factor consists of two variables namely ‘present capital adequacy norms can reduce/minimise the risk of NPAs for banks’ and ‘loan to small business under micro credit scheme decreased’ which have factor loadings of 0.7381 and 0.5886 respectively. The sixth factor can be named ‘capital adequacy norms and decreased micro credit’. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.02 and 8.50 per cent respectively.

Communality

It represents the extent of influence of a particular variable on all the factors together. It shows that the highest communality value pertaining to the variables namely ‘personal loan to business people decreased’, ‘loans to small business under micro credit scheme decreased’ and ‘loan to self-help group (SHG) decreased’ were 0.7718, 0.7256 and 0.7271 respectively.

6.4 IMPACT OF NPAs ON REFLECTED AREAS

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 11 dimensions of the impact of NPAs on reflected areas and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax criteria. The data validity for factor analysis has been examined with the help of the Kaiser Meyer Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and the Bartlett Test of Sphericity. The KMO

measure of 0.41382 and zero level significance of the chi-square satisfy the validity of data for factor analysis. The factor analysis has identified five factors. The factor loading of the variables in five factors, its communality, eigenvalue and percentage of variation are shown in Table 6.6.

TABLE 6.6**ROTATED FACTOR MATRIX OF IMPACT OF NPAs ON BANKING NORMS**

Sl. No.	Variables	Rotated Factor Loading					h ²
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	
1.	Increased more legal expenditure	0.8448	0.2389	0.1058	0.1368	0.0233	0.8013
2.	Declining reserves and surpluses	0.6970	0.3627	0.0110	0.1689	0.0215	0.6466
3.	Erosion of profit	0.1021	0.7270	0.1059	0.0015	0.0098	0.5401
4.	Increase in interest rate	0.1383	0.6504	0.3174	0.0197	0.3498	0.6658
5.	Increase in market borrowings	0.0576	0.4210	0.0396	0.0199	0.2666	0.2537
6.	Increasing intermediation cost	0.0770	0.0363	0.8040	0.0597	0.0047	0.6573
7.	Increasing spread (Interest income)	0.0686	0.2038	0.4434	0.7019	0.0705	0.7406
8.	Increase in provisions for bad & doubtful debts	0.3641	0.1306	0.1887	0.6393	0.0936	0.6029
9.	Contraction of credit	0.2964	0.0139	0.3339	0.5576	0.0829	0.5175
10.	Increasing investment in Govt. Securities to meet SLR	0.0653	0.0638	0.1148	0.0021	0.8232	0.6993
11.	Increase in the Case Reserve Ratio (CRR)	0.4406	0.1903	0.4431	0.0981	0.5999	0.6040
	EigenValues	1.6282	1.4211	1.3823	1.1706	1.1267	
	% of variation	14.80	12.90	12.60	10.60	10.20	
	Cumulative Percentage	14.80	27.70	40.30	50.90	61.10	

Factor 1

In the first factor, variables namely, 'increased more legal expenditure' and 'declining reserve and surpluses' were included which have factor loadings of 0.8448 and 0.6970 respectively. As these variables are related to legal expenditure and reserve and surpluses, this factor can be termed 'expenditure, reserves and surpluses'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.63 and 14.80 per cent respectively.

Factor 2

The second factor consists of two variables namely 'erosion of profit' and 'increase in the interest rate' which have factor loading of 0.7270 and 0.6504 respectively. Thus factor two can be termed as 'profit and interest rate'. It is also noted that 'increase in the market borrowings' has not been considered for the explanation of the second factor as its factor loading is 0.4710 which is less than 0.5. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.42 and 12.90 per cent respectively.

Factor 3

The third factor consists of only one variable - 'increasing intermediation cost' which has a factor loading of 0.8040. On the basis of this variable, this factor

has been named 'intermediation cost'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.38 and 12.60 per cent respectively.

Factor 4

There are three variables in this factor namely, 'increasing spread (interest income)', 'increase in provision for bad and doubtful debts' and 'contraction of credit' with factor loadings of 0.7019, 0.6393 and 0.5576 respectively. These variables are characterised as 'spread, provision for bad debts and contraction of credit'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.17 and 10.60 per cent respectively.

Factor 5

This factor consists of two variables namely, 'increasing investment in Government Securities to meet (SLR)' and 'increase in the cash reserve ratio (CRR)' which have factor loadings of 0.8232 and 0.5999 respectively. On the basis of these variables, the fifth factor has been named 'investment in Government Securities and cash reserve ratio'. The eigenvalue and the percentage of variation caused by this factor were 1.13 and 10.20 per cent respectively.

Communality

It represents the extent of influence of a particular variable on all the factors together. It shows that the highest communality value pertaining to the

variables namely 'more legal expenditure' and 'increasing spread (interest income)' were 0.8013 and 0.7406 respectively.

PART – B

In this part of the chapter the researcher has analysed the officials' opinion on reducing NPAs under the following headings (1) officials' opinions to contain NPAs, (2) officials' opinions for improvement of banking performance, (3) officials' opinions on remedies for reducing NPAs and (4) officials' opinions on the borrowers' repaying behaviour. For the purpose of analysis, the opinions were collected from the respondents for five statements under the first heading, eight statements under the second heading, ten statements under the third heading and four statements under the fourth heading (vide Annexure- A) through the five point scaling technique. In order to ascertain whether there was any difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the various statements, null hypotheses were formulated (vide. CH.I). The formulated hypotheses have been tested by the researcher with the help of the Kolmogorov Smirnov test (KS test).

6.5 OFFICIALS OPINIONS TO CONTAIN NPAs

Table 6.7 presents the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement 'problems of NPA can be to a great extent contained by maintaining a continuous rapport /relationship with borrower' and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.7**RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-"MAINTAINING A CONTINUOUS RAPPORT / RELATIONSHIP WITH BORROWERS" (KS TEST)**

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	84	0.26	0.26	0.20	0.20	0.06
2.	Agree	188	0.58	0.84	0.20	0.40	0.44
3.	No opinion	10	0.03	0.87	0.20	0.60	0.27
4.	Disagree	24	0.08	0.95	0.20	0.80	0.15
5.	Strongly Disagree	16	0.05	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.44 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.44) exceeds the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement 'maintaining a continuous rapport/relationship with borrower' is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

Table 6.8 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement 'borrowers have to be made more accountable/responsible to contain NPA problem' and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.8

RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT—"BORROWERS HAVE TO BE MADE MORE ACCOUNTABLE / RESPONSIBLE TO CONTAIN NPA PROBLEM" (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	118	0.37	0.37	0.20	0.20	0.17
2.	Agree	180	0.56	0.93	0.20	0.40	0.53
3.	No opinion	24	0.07	1.00	0.20	0.60	0.40
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.53 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.53 is greater than the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement 'Borrowers have to be made more accountable/ responsible to contain the NPA problem' is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

Table 6.9 gives the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement 'Involvement of auditors, accountants, regulators, representative bodies would help recover bank dues in an effective manner' and the result of the KS test.

TABLE 6.9
RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT—"INVOLVEMENT OF
AUDITORS, ACCOUNTANTS, REGULATORS, REPRESENTATIVE BODIES
WOULD HELP RECOVER BANK DUES IN AN EFFECTIVE MANNER"
(KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	96	0.30	0.30	0.20	0.20	0.10
2.	Agree	178	0.55	0.85	0.20	0.40	0.45
3.	No opinion	14	0.04	0.89	0.20	0.60	0.29
4.	Disagree	34	0.11	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.45 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.45) exceeds the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement 'Involvement of auditors, accountants, regulators, representative bodies would help to recover the bank dues in an effective manner' is rejected. As such there is therefore difference in the ratings given by the officials.

Table 6.10 depicts the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement 'Corporate governance in corporate bodies can help improve the

conduct of accounts with banks and bring down level of NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.10
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATEMENT–“CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN CORPORATE BODIES CAN HELP IMPROVE THE CONDUCT OF ACCOUNTS WITH BANKS AND BRING DOWN LEVEL OF NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	124	0.39	0.39	0.20	0.20	0.19
2.	Agree	184	0.57	0.96	0.20	0.40	0.56
3.	No opinion	14	0.04	1.00	0.20	0.60	0.40
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.56 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value 0.56 is greater than the table value 0.076 the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents, on the statement ‘Corporate governance in corporate bodies can help improve the conduct of accounts with banks and bring down level of NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

The data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Banks will have to educate their employees about NPA and its effect on the banks’ performance’ and the data concerning the application of KS test are presented in Table 6.11.

TABLE 6.11
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATEMENT–“BANKS WILL HAVE TO EDUCATE THEIR EMPLOYEES ABOUT NPA AND ITS EFFECT ON THE BANKS’ PERFORMANCE” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	150	0.47	0.47	0.20	0.20	0.27
2.	Agree	140	0.43	0.90	0.20	0.40	0.50
3.	No opinion	32	0.10	1.00	0.20	0.60	0.40
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.50 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.50) exceeds the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Banks will should educate their employees about NPA and its effect on the banks’ performance’ is rejected. As such there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

The foregoing K.S. Test analysis shows that the entire set of hypotheses has been rejected. It further shows that the opinion of officials reflects a clear difference in giving their ratings to the statement.

Table 6.12 presents the data on the opinions of the officials on the first five statements to contain NPAs. It shows the difference in intensities of favourability and unfavourability and their respective scores on the statements.

Regarding the first statement, out of the 322 officials, 272 (84%) have a positive opinion, and 40 (12%) have a negative opinion. The intensity value is 300 and is ranked fifth. The majority of the respondents are of the views that the problems of NPAs can be contained to a great extent by maintaining a continuous rapport/relationship with the borrower.

With regard to the second statement out of the 322 respondents, 298 (93%) have a positive feeling and 24 (7%) are neutral. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the view that the borrowers have to be made more accountable/responsible to contain NPA problem. The intensity value of the statement is 416 and it is ranked third.

As far as the third statement is concerned, 274 respondents (85%) have a positive attitude on the statement and 34 (11%) officials have a negative attitude. The intensity value is 336 and is ranked fourth. Thus a majority of the officials were of the views that the involvement of auditors, accountants, regulators, representative bodies, etc., would help recover bank dues in an effective manner.

Regarding the fourth statement 308 respondents (96%) have a positive outlook and 14 (4%) are negative. The intensity value is 432 and is ranked second. The majority of the respondents are of the view that the corporate governance in corporate bodies can help improve the conduct of accounts with banks and thus help bring down level of NPAs.

Considering the fifth statement, out of the 322 officials, 290 (90%) officials have a positive opinion and 32 (10%) are neutral. The statement has the intensity value of 440 and ranked first. Thus a majority of the officials suggest that the bank should educate their employees on NPA and its effect on the bank's performance to contain NPAs.

6.6 OFFICIALS OPINIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF BANKING PERFORMANCE

Table 6.13 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement 'Improved credit appraisal system will help reduce NPAs' and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.13
RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-"IMPROVED CREDIT APPRAISAL SYSTEM WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs" (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	142	0.44	0.44	0.20	0.20	0.24
2.	Agree	76	0.24	0.68	0.20	0.40	0.28
3.	No opinion	20	0.06	0.74	0.20	0.60	0.14
4.	Disagree	48	0.15	0.89	0.20	0.80	0.09
5.	Strongly Disagree	36	0.11	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.28 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.28) exceeds the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement ‘Improved credit appraisal system will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

The data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘continuous monitoring and follow-up action are required for reducing NPAs’ and the results of the KS test are presented in Table 6.14.

TABLE 6.14
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-“CONTINUOUS
MONITORING AND FOLLOW-UP ACTION ARE REQUIRED FOR
REDUCING NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	74	0.23	0.23	0.20	0.20	0.03
2.	Agree	182	0.57	0.80	0.20	0.40	0.40
3.	No opinion	0	0.00	0.80	0.20	0.60	0.20
4.	Disagree	56	0.17	0.97	0.20	0.80	0.17
5.	Strongly Disagree	10	0.03	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.40 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.40 is greater than the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Continuous monitoring and follow-up action are required for reducing NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.15 presents the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Improved legal system with increased role of DRT will help bring down NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.15

RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-“IMPROVED LEGAL SYSTEM WITH INCREASED ROLE OF DRT WILL HELP BRING DOWN NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	160	0.50	0.50	0.20	0.20	0.30
2.	Agree	100	0.31	0.81	0.20	0.40	0.41
3.	No opinion	2	0.00	0.81	0.20	0.60	0.21
4.	Disagree	54	0.17	0.98	0.20	0.80	0.18
5.	Strongly Disagree	6	0.02	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.41 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.41) exceeds the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement ‘Improved legal system with increased role of DRT will help bring down NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

Table 6.16 presents the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘Improved exchange of information will reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.16

RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-“IMPROVED EXCHANGE OF INFORMATION WILL REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	102	0.32	0.32	0.20	0.20	0.12
2.	Agree	78	0.24	0.56	0.20	0.40	0.16
3.	No opinion	32	0.10	0.66	0.20	0.60	0.06
4.	Disagree	60	0.19	0.85	0.20	0.80	0.05
5.	Strongly Disagree	50	0.15	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.16 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value 0.16 is greater than the table value 0.076 the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Improved exchange of information will reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.17 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘Improved market intelligence system will help reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.17
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-“IMPROVED MARKET INTELLIGENCE SYSTEM WITH HELP REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	138	0.43	0.43	0.20	0.20	0.23
2.	Agree	86	0.27	0.70	0.20	0.40	0.30
3.	No opinion	4	0.01	0.71	0.20	0.60	0.11
4.	Disagree	54	0.17	0.88	0.20	0.80	0.08
5.	Strongly Disagree	40	0.12	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.30 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value 0.30 exceeds the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Improved intelligence system will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

The data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘Avoiding political interference for reducing NPAs’ and the results of the KS test is given in Table 6.18.

TABLE 6.18

RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATMENT - “AVOIDING POLITICAL INTERFERENCE WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs ” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	204	0.63	0.63	0.20	0.20	0.43
2.	Agree	116	0.36	0.99	0.20	0.40	0.59
3.	No opinion	2	0.01	1.00	0.20	0.60	0.40
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.59 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.59 is greater than the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Avoiding political interference will reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.19 gives the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Involvement of representative bodies will reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.19

RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-“INVOLVEMENT OF REPRESENTATIVE BODIES WILL REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	144	0.45	0.45	0.20	0.20	0.25
2.	Agree	122	0.38	0.83	0.20	0.40	0.43
3.	No opinion	18	0.06	0.89	0.20	0.60	0.29
4.	Disagree	22	0.07	0.96	0.20	0.80	0.16
5.	Strongly Disagree	16	0.04	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.43 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.43 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Involvement of representative bodies will reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

The data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Introduction of incentive/ reward system to staff engaged in collection process will help reduce NPAs’ and the data concerning the application of the KS test are presented in Table 6.20.

TABLE 6.20

RESPONDENTS’ OPINION ON THE STATMENT-“INTRODUCTION OF INCENTIVE / REWARD SYSTEM TO STAFF ENGAGED IN COLLECTION PROCESS WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	232	0.72	0.72	0.20	0.20	0.52
2.	Agree	64	0.20	0.92	0.20	0.40	0.52
3.	No opinion	2	0.00	0.92	0.20	0.60	0.32
4.	Disagree	12	0.04	0.96	0.20	0.80	0.16
5.	Strongly Disagree	12	0.04	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.52 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.52 is greater than the table value (0.076), the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement 'Introduction of incentive/reward system to staff engaged in collection process will bring down NPAs' is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

The foregoing K.S. Test analysis shows that the entire hypotheses have been rejected. It further shows that the opinion of officials reflects clear difference in giving their ratings to the statements.

Table 6.21 shows the data on the opinion of the officials on the statements for improvement of banking performance. It shows the different intensities of favourability and unfavourability and their respective scores on the statements.

Regarding the first statement, out of the 322 officials, 218 (68%) are positive and 84 (26%) are negative and 20 (6%) officials are neutral. The intensity value of this statement is 240 and is ranked sixth. Thus majority of the officials feel that an improved credit appraisal system will help improve the banking performance.

Considering the second statement, out of the 322 respondents, 256 (80%) have a positive opinion while 66 (20%) have a negative opinion. The intensity value is 254. The statement is ranked fifth. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the view that continuous monitoring and follow-up action will help improve the banking performance.

As regards the third statement out of the 322 officials, 260 (81%) have given a positive attitude, while 60 (19%) have given negative attitude two officials are neutral. The intensity value of this statement is 354 and is ranked fourth. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the opinion that an improved legal system and increased role of DRT will help improve the banking performance.

About the fourth statement, out of the 322 respondents 180 (56%) have a positive opinion, while 110 (34%) have a negative opinion and 32 (10%) stood neutral. The intensity value of this statement is 122 and ranked eighth. Thus a

majority of the respondents feel that improved exchange of information will help improve the performance.

Regarding the fifth statement, out of the 322 respondents 224 (70%) have a positive outlook while 94 (29%) have a negative outlook. 4 (1%) respondents are neutral. The intensity value is 228 and the statement is ranked seventh. Thus a majority of the respondents consider that an improved market intelligence system will help improve the performance.

As regards the sixth statement, out of the 322 officials, 320 (99.38%) have a positive outlook and two (0.62%) are neutral. The intensity value of this statement is 524 and is ranked first. Thus a majority of the officials are of the opinion that avoiding political interference will help improve the performance.

About the seventh statement, out of the 322 respondents, 266 (83%) have a positive opinion while 38 (12%) have a negative opinion, 18 respondents (5%) take a neutral position. The intensity value is 356 and the statement is ranked third. The majority of the respondents feel that the involvement of representative bodies in the banking operation will help improve the performance.

With regard to the eighth statement, out of the 322 officials, 296 (91.93%) have a positive outlook while 24 (7.45%) have a negative outlook and two respondents (0.62%) are neutral. The intensity value is 492 and the statement is

ranked second. Thus a majority of the officials are of the opinion that the introduction of incentive/ reward system to the staff engaged in the collection process will help improve the performance.

6.7 OFFICIALS OPINIONS ON REMEDIES FOR REDUCING NPAs

Table 6.22 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘proper selection of the borrower’s project will reduce NPAs’ and the results of KS test.

TABLE 6.22
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATEMENT-“PROPER SELECTION OF
THE BORROWER’S PROJECT WILL REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	120	0.37	0.37	0.20	0.20	0.17
2.	Agree	190	0.59	0.96	0.20	0.40	0.56
3.	No opinion	12	0.04	1.00	0.20	0.60	0.40
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.56 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.56 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘proper selection of the borrower’s project will reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.23 presents the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Financing only viable projects will help reduce NPAs’ and data concerning the application of the KS test.

TABLE 6.23

**RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATEMENT-“FINANCING ONLY
VIALE PROJECTS WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)**

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	84	0.26	0.26	0.20	0.20	0.06
2.	Agree	184	0.57	0.83	0.20	0.40	0.43
3.	No opinion	36	0.11	0.94	0.20	0.60	0.34
4.	Disagree	10	0.03	0.97	0.20	0.80	0.17
5.	Strongly Disagree	8	0.03	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.43 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.43 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Financing only viable projects will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

The data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘Extending need based financing will help reduce NPAs’ and data relating to the application of the KS test are given in Table 6.24.

TABLE 6.24

**RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATEMENT-“EXTENDING NEED
BASED FINANCING WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)**

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	80	0.25	0.25	0.20	0.20	0.05
2.	Agree	150	0.47	0.72	0.20	0.40	0.32
3.	No opinion	56	0.17	0.89	0.20	0.60	0.29
4.	Disagree	28	0.08	0.97	0.20	0.80	0.17
5.	Strongly Disagree	8	0.03	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.32 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.32 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Extending need based financing will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

The data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘Ensuring proper end-use will help reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test are presented in Table 6.25.

TABLE 6.25
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATEMENT-“ENSURING PROPER
END-USE WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	94	0.29	0.29	0.20	0.20	0.09
2.	Agree	176	0.55	0.84	0.20	0.40	0.44
3.	No opinion	40	0.12	0.96	0.20	0.60	0.36
4.	Disagree	10	0.03	0.99	0.20	0.80	0.19
5.	Strongly Disagree	2	0.01	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.44 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.44 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Ensuring proper end-use will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.26 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘proper post sanction follow-up will reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.26
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATMENT-“PROPER POST SANCTION FOLLOW-UP WILL REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	106	0.33	0.33	0.20	0.20	0.13
2.	Agree	204	0.63	0.96	0.20	0.40	0.56
3.	No opinion	12	0.04	1.00	0.20	0.60	0.40
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.56 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.56 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘proper post sanction follow-up will reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.27 depicts the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘Regular contact with borrowers will help reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.27
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATEMENT-“REGULAR CONTACT WITH BORROWERS WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	88	0.27	0.27	0.20	0.20	0.07
2.	Agree	206	0.64	0.91	0.20	0.40	0.51
3.	No opinion	20	0.06	0.97	0.20	0.60	0.37
4.	Disagree	8	0.03	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.51 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.51 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Regular contact with borrowers will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.28 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Regular monitoring of the accounts will help reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.28

RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATMENT-“REGULAR MONITORING OF THE ACCOUNTS WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	122	0.38	0.38	0.20	0.20	0.18
2.	Agree	162	0.50	0.88	0.20	0.40	0.48
3.	No opinion	20	0.06	0.94	0.20	0.60	0.34
4.	Disagree	12	0.04	0.98	0.20	0.80	0.18
5.	Strongly Disagree	6	0.02	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.48 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.48 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Regular monitoring of the accounts will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

The data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Avoiding overdrawing extraneous debt will help reduce NPAs’ and the application of KS test are presented in Table 6.29.

TABLE 6.29
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATMENT -“AVOIDING
OVERDRAWING EXTRANEIOUS DEBT WILL HELP REDUCE NPAs”
(KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	98	0.30	0.30	0.20	0.20	0.10
2.	Agree	114	0.35	0.65	0.20	0.40	0.25
3.	No opinion	26	0.08	0.73	0.20	0.60	0.13
4.	Disagree	76	0.24	0.97	0.20	0.80	0.17
5.	Strongly Disagree	8	0.03	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.25 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.25 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Avoiding overdrawing extraneous debt will help reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.30 gives the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Holding of recovery camps will reduce NPAs’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.30
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATEMENT-“HOLDING OF
RECOVERY CAMPS WILL REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	120	0.37	0.37	0.20	0.20	0.17
2.	Agree	140	0.44	0.81	0.20	0.40	0.41
3.	No opinion	20	0.06	0.87	0.20	0.60	0.27
4.	Disagree	32	0.10	0.97	0.20	0.80	0.17
5.	Strongly Disagree	10	0.03	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.41 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.41 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Holding of recovery camps will reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.31 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement ‘Special incentives for prompt repayment will reduce NPAs’ and the data relating to the application of the KS test.

TABLE 6.31
RESPONDENTS’ OPINION TO THE STATEMENT-“SPECIAL INCENTIVES
FOR PROMPT REPAYMENT WILL REDUCE NPAs” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	118	0.37	0.37	0.20	0.20	0.17
2.	Agree	172	0.53	0.90	0.20	0.40	0.50
3.	No opinion	24	0.08	0.98	0.20	0.60	0.38
4.	Disagree	4	0.01	0.99	0.20	0.80	0.19
5.	Strongly Disagree	4	0.01	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.50 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value i.e. 0.50 is greater than the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Special incentives for prompt repayment will reduce NPAs’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

The foregoing K.S. Test analysis shows that the entire set of hypotheses have been rejected. It further shows that the opinion of officials reflects a clear difference in giving their ratings to the statements.

Table 6.32 presents the data on the opinion of the officials on the statement regarding remedies for reducing NPAs. It shows the different intensities of the favourability and unfavourability and their respective scores on the statement.

Regarding the first statement, out of the 322 officials, 310 (96%) have a positive attitude and 12 (4%) are neutral. The intensity value of this statement is 430 and this statement is ranked first. Thus a majority of the officials are of the views that proper selection of borrowers' activity will help reduce NPAs.

As regards the second statement, out of the 322 respondents, 268 (83%) have positive outlook and 36 (11%) are neutral. 18 (6%) respondents have a negative outlook. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the opinion that financing only viable projects will help reduce NPAs. The intensity value of the statement 326 and is ranked eighth.

About the third statement, out of the 322 officials 230 (71%) have a positive opinion and 56 (17%) are neutral 36 (11%) officials have a negative opinion. The intensity value of this statement is 266 and is ranked ninth. Thus a majority of the officials feel that extending need based financing alone will help reduce NPAs.

Out of the 322 respondents, 270 (84%) have a positive attitude towards the fourth statement while 12 (4%) have a negative attitude and 40 (12%) respondents are at neutral. The intensity value of the statement is 350 and is ranked sixth. Thus a majority of the respondents consider that ensuring proper end-use will help reduce NPAs.

With regard to the fifth statement, out of the 322 respondents, 310 (96%) have given a positive outlook and 12 (4%) are neutral. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the opinion that proper post sanction follow-up action will help reduce NPAs. The intensity value of the statement is 416 and is ranked second.

Regarding the sixth statement, out of the 322 officials, 294 (91%) have given the positive opinion. 8 (3%) are at the neutral position and 20 (6%) have a negative opinion. The intensity value of the statement is 374 and is ranked fifth. Thus according to the majority of the officials, regular contact with borrowers will help reduce NPAs.

Regarding the seventh statement, out of the 322 officials, 284 (88%) officials have given a positive opinion while 18 (6%) have given a negative opinion and 20 respondents (6%) are neutral. The intensity value is 382 and is ranked fourth. Thus the majority of the respondents are of the view that regular monitoring of the accounts will help reduce NPAs.

As far as the eighth statement is concerned, out of the 322 respondents, 212 (66%) have given a positive opinion, while 84 (26%) have given negative opinion and 26 (8%) are at the neutral position. The intensity value is 218 and the statement is ranked tenth. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the view that avoiding overdrawing extraneous debt will help reduce NPAs.

Considering the ninth statement, out of the 322 respondents, 260 (81%) have a positive attitude while 42 (13%) have a negative attitude and 20 respondents (6%) take the neutral position. The intensity value is 328 and the statement is ranked seventh. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the view that holding of recovery camps will help reduce NPAs.

With regard to the tenth statement out of the 322 respondents 290 (90%) have a positive outlook. while 8 (3%) have a negative outlook and 24 respondents (7%) are neutral. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the opinion that special incentives for prompt repayment will encourage the borrowers to repay and thus help reduce NPAs. The intensity value of this statement is 396 and is ranked third.

6.8 OFFICIALS OPINIONS ON BORROWERS REPAYING BEHAVIOUR

Table 6.33 shows the data on the opinion of the officials regarding the statement ‘Good borrowers are willing to repay’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.33

RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT -"GOOD BORROWERS ARE WILLING TO REPAY" (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	118	0.37	0.37	0.20	0.20	0.17
2.	Agree	176	0.55	0.92	0.20	0.40	0.52
3.	No opinion	28	0.08	1.00	0.20	0.60	0.40
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.52 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.52) exceeds the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement 'Good borrowers are willing to repay' is rejected. As such, there is difference in the importance of ratings given by the officials.

Table 6.34 gives the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement 'Good borrowers are not willing to repay' and the data relating to the application of the KS test.

TABLE 6.34
RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-“GOOD BORROWERS
ARE NOT WILLING TO REPAY” (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	76	0.24	0.24	0.20	0.20	0.04
2.	Agree	206	0.64	0.88	0.20	0.40	0.48
3.	No opinion	26	0.08	0.96	0.20	0.60	0.36
4.	Disagree	12	0.04	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	2	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.48 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.48) exceeds the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement ‘Good borrowers are not willing to repay’ is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.35 gives the data on the opinion of the respondents regarding the statement ‘Bad borrowers are willing to repay’ and the results of the KS test.

TABLE 6.35
RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-"BAD BORROWERS ARE
WILLING TO REPAY" (KS TEST)

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	58	0.18	0.18	0.20	0.20	-0.02
2.	Agree	256	0.80	0.98	0.20	0.40	0.58
3.	No opinion	0	0.00	0.98	0.20	0.60	0.38
4.	Disagree	0	0.00	0.98	0.20	0.80	0.18
5.	Strongly Disagree	8	0.02	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.58 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.58) exceeds the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the respondents on the statement 'Bad borrowers are willing to repay' is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the respondents.

Table 6.36 shows the data on the opinion of the respondents on the statement 'Bad borrowers are not willing to repay' and the data relating to the application of the KS test.

TABLE 6.36

**RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON THE STATEMENT-"BAD BORROWERS ARE
NOT WILLING TO REPAY" (KS TEST)**

Sl. No.	Opinion	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Cumulative Observed Proportion (O)	Expected Proportion	Cumulative Expected Proportion (E)	O-E
1.	Strongly Agree	78	0.24	0.24	0.20	0.20	0.04
2.	Agree	230	0.72	0.96	0.20	0.40	0.56
3.	No opinion	0	0.00	0.96	0.20	0.60	0.36
4.	Disagree	14	0.04	1.00	0.20	0.80	0.20
5.	Strongly Disagree	0	0.00	1.00	0.20	1.00	0.00

Source: Primary data.

Calculated value : 0.56 (i.e. the largest difference)

Table value at 95% Confidence Level : $1.36 / \sqrt{322} = 0.076$

As the calculated value (0.56) exceeds the table value (0.076) the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the ratings given by the officials on the statement 'Bad borrowers are not willing to repay' is rejected. As such, there is difference in the ratings given by the officials.

The foregoing K.S. Test analysis shows that the entire hypotheses have been rejected. It further shows that the opinions of officials reflect a clear difference in giving their ratings to the statements.

Table 6.37 shows the data on the opinion of the officials on the statement regarding the borrowers' repaying behaviour.

As far as the first statement is concerned out of the 322 respondents 294 (91%) have given a positive opinion and 28 (9%) have a neutral position. The intensity value is 412 and is ranked first. Thus a majority of the respondents are of the view that good borrowers are willing to repay.

Regarding the second statement, out of the 322 officials, 282 (87%) have given a positive outlook while 16 (5%) officials have a negative outlook on the statement. 26 (8%) officials are at the neutral position. Thus a majority of the officials are of the opinion that good borrowers are not willing to repay. The intensity value is 342 and is ranked fourth.

With regard to the third statement, out of the 322 respondents, 314 (98%) have adopted a positive attitude. 8 (2%) respondents have a negative attitude. The intensity value of this statement is 356 and is ranked third. Thus a majority of the respondents feel that bad borrowers are willing to repay.

On the fourth statement, out of the 322 officials, 308 (96%) have a positive opinion and 14 (4%) have a negative opinion. The intensity value of the statement is 372 and it is ranked second. Thus a majority of the officials feel that bad borrowers are not willing to repay the dues in time.

6.9 CONCLUSION

This chapter deals with the perception of officials on NPAs and their opinions for reducing NPAs and improving bank performance. This chapter is divided into two parts. Part 'A' consists of the opinions of the officials regarding the management of NPAs and factor analysis has been used to highlight the impact. In Part 'B' opinions in the form of suggestions regarding NPAs are analysed through the KS test. Questionnaires were used to collect data from the officials through the five point scale.

192-224,226-235,237-249,251-256,258,259

TABLE 6.12

OFFICIALS' OPINIONS ON STEPS TO CONTAIN NPAs

Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree +2	Agree +1	No Opinion 0	Disagree -1	Strongly Disagree -2	Intensity Value	Rank
1.	The problems of NPA can be contained to a great extent by maintaining a continuous rapport/ relationship with borrower.	84	188	10	24	16	300	5
2.	Borrowers have to be made more accountable/ responsible to contain NPA problem	118	180	24	0	0	416	3
3.	Involvement of Auditors, Accountants, Regulators, Representative Bodies, would help recover bank dues in an effective manner	96	178	14	34	0	336	4
4.	Corporate Governance in corporate bodies can help improve the conduct of accounts with banks and bring down level of NPAs	124	184	14	0	0	432	2
5.	Bank will have to educate their employees about NPA and its effect on the banks' performance	150	140	32	0	0	440	1

Source: Primary data.

TABLE 6.21
OFFICIALS' OPINIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF BANKING PERFORMANCE

Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree +2	Agree +1	No Opinion 0	Disagree -1	Strongly Disagree -2	Intensity Value	Rank
1.	Improved credit appraisal system will help reduce NPAs	142	76	20	48	36	240	6
2.	Continuous monitoring and follow-up action are required for reducing NPAs	74	182	0	56	10	254	5
3.	Improved legal system with increase in the role of DRT will bring down NPAs	160	100	2	54	6	354	4
4.	Improved exchange of information will reduce NPAs	102	78	32	60	50	122	8
5.	Improved market intelligence system will help reduce NPAs	138	86	4	54	40	228	7
6.	Avoiding political interference will help reduce NPAs	204	116	2	0	0	524	1
7.	Involvement of representative bodies will help reduce NPAs	144	122	18	22	16	356	3
8.	Introduction of incentive/reward system to staff engaged in collection process will help reduce NPAs	232	64	2	12	12	492	2

Source: Primary data.

TABLE 6.32
OFFICIALS' OPINIONS REGARDING REMEDIES FOR REDUCING NPAs

Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree +2	Agree +1	No Opinion 0	Disagree -1	Strongly Disagree -2	Intensity Value	Rank
1.	Proper selection of the borrower's project will reduce NPAs	120	190	12	0	0	430	1
2.	Financing only viable projects will help reduce NPAs	84	184	36	10	8	326	8
3.	Extending need based financing will help reduce NPAs	80	150	56	28	8	266	9
4.	Ensuring proper end-use will help reduce NPAs	94	176	40	10	2	350	6
5.	Proper post sanction follow-up will reduce NPAs	106	204	12	0	0	416	2
6.	Regular contact with borrowers will help reduce NPAs	88	206	20	8	0	374	5
7.	Regular monitoring of the accounts will help reduce NPAs	122	162	20	12	6	382	4
8.	Avoiding overdrawing extraneous debt will help reduce NPAs	98	114	26	76	8	218	10
9.	Holding of recovery camps will reduce NPAs	120	140	20	32	10	328	7
10.	Special incentives for prompt repayment will reduce NPAs	118	172	24	4	4	396	3

Source: Primary data.

TABLE 6.37**OFFICIALS' OPINIONS ON THE "BORROWERS' REPAYING BEHAVIOUR"**

Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree +2	Agree +1	No Opinion 0	Disagree -1	Strongly Disagree -2	Intensity Value	Rank
1.	Good borrowers are willing to repay	118	176	28	0	0	412	1
2.	Good borrowers are not willing to repay	76	206	26	12	2	342	4
3.	Bad borrowers are willing to repay	58	256	0	0	8	356	3
4.	Bad borrowers are not willing to repay	78	230	0	14	0	372	2

Source: Primary data.

CHAPTER VII

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

In the preceding chapters, introduction, review and methodology, financial performance of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu, NPAs, their concept and status, impact of NPAs on various performance variables and perception of officials on NPAs were discussed. The summary of the findings from the study, suggestions and conclusion are presented in this chapter.

7.1 FINDINGS

7.1.1. Financial Performance of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

The financial performance of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu has been measured with the help of memberships, branches, share capital, reserves, deposits, borrowings, loans and advances outstanding, investments, working capital, net profit and overdues during the study period. The findings are presented below.

i) Growth of Memberships

Regarding the number of members in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu, the annual growth rates are positive in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kancheepuram, Kumbakonam, the Nilgiris, Ramanathapuram, Salem,

Thanjavur, Thiruchirapalli, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai and Villupuram banks. The highest annual growth rate of memberships has been found in the Tiruvannamalai, Coimbatore and Dharmapuri with annual growth rates of 32, 9.25 and 6.21 times respectively. Negative annual growth rates were noticed in the Chennai, Erode, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Sivagangai, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks as their annual growth rates were -1.36, -13.18, -1.07, -8.18, -1.36, -0.50, -0.11, -3.71 and -6.96 times respectively. The compound growth rates varied from 5.11 per cent in the Tiruvannamalai bank to -1.35 per cent in the Virudhunagar bank.

ii) Growth of Branches

The annual growth rates of branches in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive in the Chennai, Coimbatore, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Ramanathapuram, Thiruchirapalli and Thoothukudi banks with 0.39, 0.61, 0.64, 0.57, 0.43, 0.54, 0.11, 1.36 and 0.43 times respectively. Negative annual growth rates were noticed in the Erode, Kumbakonam, the Nilgiris, Salem, Sivagangai, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore, Villupuram and Virudhunagar banks with -0.61, -0.71, -0.93, -0.18, -0.07, -0.11, -0.39, -0.18, -0.11 and -0.36 times respectively. In the Cuddalore, Madurai, Pudukkottai and Thanjavur banks the annual growth rates were negligible and hence it is left out of the analysis.

The compound growth rates varied from 3.54 per cent in the Kanyakumari bank to –6.67 per cent in the Nilgiris bank.

iii) Growth of Share Capital

All the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed a positive annual growth rate of share capital. The fitted trend equations for all the 23 DCCBs are also statistically significant. The compound growth rates were positive in all the DCCBs ranging from 17.95 per cent in the Chennai bank to 2.04 per cent in the Thoothukudi bank.

iv) Growth of Reserves

The annual growth rates of total reserves in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed a positive growth in all the banks. It was statistically significant at the five per cent level in all the banks except in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Kumbakonam, Thanjavur and Thoothukudi banks where the rates were 3.63, 1.87, 6.83, 2.80 and 6.22 respectively. The compound growth rates were positive in all the DCCBs.

v) Growth of Deposits

Positive annual growth rates of deposits were noticed in all the DCCBs except in the Tirunelveli bank. In this bank, the annual growth rate was –0.94 time which is not significant. Insignificant annual growth rates were seen in

the Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Salem, Sivagangai and Thoothukudi banks with 8.26, 1.56, 1.25, 30.13, 6.77 and 1.04 times respectively. The compound growth rates were positive in all the DCCBs except in the Tirunelveli bank where the compound growth rate was -0.38 per cent.

vi) Growth of Borrowings

The annual growth rates of borrowings in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu are positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram bank. The annual growth rate in borrowings in the Kancheepuram bank was -0.86 time while the coefficient was insignificant. In all the other DCCBs, the annual growth rates were statistically significant except in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Erode, Kanyakumari, Madurai and Thoothukudi banks with growth rates of 4.76, 9.13, 3.84, 7.38, 15.35 and 2.33 respectively. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram bank which had a negative growth rate of -1.54 per cent.

vii) Growth of Loans and Advances

The annual growth rates of loans and advances outstanding in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu reflected positive growth rates in all the DCCBs. But the growth rates were statistically significant in all the banks except in the Dharmapuri bank. The co-efficients of determination in all the banks were higher than 0.90 except in

the Dharmapuri, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks where the values were 0.44, 0.89 and 0.84 times respectively which indicates that changes in loans and advances outstanding vary only to the maximum extent of 99.44 per cent in the Dindigul bank. The compound growth rates were positive in all the DCC Banks.

viii) Growth of Investments

The total investments in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu show a negative and insignificant annual growth rates in the Coimbatore, Thiruchirapalli, Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Virudhunagar banks with the recorded rates of -0.05 , -1.70 , -4.62 , -2.99 and -2.48 times respectively. In all the other DCCBs there were positive growth rates and they were statistically significant in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kanyakumari, Pudukkottai, Ramanathapuram and Tiruvannamalai banks with 3.99, 6.30, 3.56, 2.71, 2.29 and 5.05 times respectively. The compound growth rates varied from 12.61 per cent in the Tiruvannamalai bank to -6.97 per cent in the Tirunelveli bank.

ix) Growth of Working Capital

The working capital in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu reflected positive growth rates. Significant growth rates were found in all the banks except in the Dharmapuri bank with 26.73 times which indicates that changes in time variable explain the changes in the amount of working capital to the extent of 47.38 per

cent. The compound growth rates were positive in all the DCCBs during the study period.

x) Growth of Net Profit

It shows that the growth rates of net profit in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were negative and insignificant growth rates were found in the Ramanathapuram, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks with -1.77 , -0.82 and -0.61 times respectively whereas all the other banks showed positive growth rates and the growth rates were significant in the Chennai, Erode, Salem and Tiruvannamalai banks with 4.63 , 0.38 , 0.32 and 2.06 times respectively. Positive compound growth rates were noticed in the Chennai, Erode, Kancheepuram, Salem and Villupuram banks which recorded growth rates of 12.90 , 31.49 , 10.03 , 8.43 and 8.65 per cent respectively, whereas in all the other banks growth was in 0 per cent.

xi) Growth of Overdues

The overdues of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed negative annual growth rates in the Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur and Virudhungan banks with -0.76 , -0.11 , -0.17 and -1.30 times respectively. It shows that the amount of overdues in these banks have declined during the study period. There are positive annual growth rates in all the other banks but they were at the significant level only in the Chennai, Kancheepuram, Ramanathapuram, Salem and Thiruchirapalli

banks with 0.91, 7.62, 4.04, 8.21 and 6.92 times respectively. It shows that the amount of overdues in these banks reflect an increasing trend. This may be due to the poor recovery process. The compound growth rates varied from 91.22 per cent in the Dharmapuri bank to -3.34 per cent in the Virudhunagar bank.

7.1.2. NPAs- Concept and Status in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

In the fourth chapter, the concept and the status of NPAs in the DCCBs were discussed. The first part of this chapter explains the theoretical discussion on the concept in depth and breadth. In the second part the position and growth of standard assets, sub-standard assets, doubtful assets, loss assets, gross NPAs, provision for NPAs and net NPAs are highlighted. The findings are presented below:

i) Position and Growth of Standard Assets

The total standard assets of all the DCCBs were Rs.3,83,311 lakhs in 1998-99 which gradually increased to Rs.5,63,327 lakhs by 2002-03. But they decreased to Rs.5,61,360 lakhs in 2003-04, and then increased to Rs.6,83,679 lakhs in the year 2004-05. The average level of standard assets was the highest in the Chennai bank with 12.56 per cent and the lowest in the Nilgiris bank with 1.22 per cent during the study period. Negative and insignificant growth rates of standard assets were seen in the Madurai bank with the annual growth rates of

-158.56 times. Positive growth rates of standard assets were found in all the other DCCBs. But it is statistically insignificant in the Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Thanjavur, Tiruvannamalai and Thoothukudi banks with 469, 2286.68, 926.54, 835.14, 821.25, 1419.18 and 169.46 times respectively. The compound growth rates varied from 17.10 per cent in the Chennai bank to -0.70 per cent in the Madurai bank.

ii) Position and Growth of Sub-Standard Assets

Sub-standard assets in all the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu have increased from Rs.34739 lakhs in 1998-99 to Rs.95062 lakhs in 2003-04. But they decreased to Rs.38268 lakhs in 2004-05 due to increase in the recovery of loans in this year. The highest average level of sub-standard assets was found in the Madurai bank at 13.98 per cent and the lowest in the Kanyakumari bank at 0.86 per cent. Negative growth rates were found in the Chennai, Kancheepuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks with -142.11, -84.79, -58.93, -129.22, -113.43 and -197.93 times respectively. But it is statistically significant only in the Chennai bank. There are positive annual growth rates in all the other DCCBs but they were significant only in the Madurai, Salem and Thoothukudi banks with 1460.93, 634.21 and 167.32 times respectively. The compound growth rate varied from 37.32 per cent in the Erode bank to -23.92 per cent in the Chennai bank.

(iii) Position and Growth of Doubtful Assets

The total doubtful assets of all the DCCBs increased three fold from Rs.20892 lakhs in 1998-99 to Rs.67975 lakhs in 2003-04; they declined to Rs.49,788 lakhs in 2004-05 due to increased recovery of loans in this period. The Madurai bank has recorded the highest average level of doubtful assets at 12.59 per cent and the lowest level was found in the Kanyakumari bank at 0.47 per cent. The annual growth rates of doubtful assets were negative and insignificant in the Kancheepuram and the Nilgiris banks with -223.21 and -18.86 times respectively. In all the other DCCBs positive growth rates were found and they were significant in the Coimbatore, Dindigul, Erode, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Thiruchirapalli, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks with 436.54, 311.54, 139.64, 482.68, 899.18, 175.54, 1211, 382 and 215.46 times respectively. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Kancheepuram and the Nilgiris banks which recorded negative growth rates of -25.87 and -2.38 per cent respectively.

iv) Position and Growth of Loss Assets

The total loss assets of all the DCCBs also increased over the period of study from Rs.7404 lakhs in 1998-99 to Rs.41,609 lakhs in 2004-05 due to non-availability of realisable value of security against the loans. The Kancheepuram bank has the highest average level of loss assets of 14.42 per cent and the lowest

of 0.46 per cent was found in the Vellore bank. The annual growth rates of loss assets in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu were positive in all the banks except in the Coimbatore bank which recorded a negative growth rate of -48.32 times. But it is statistically insignificant at the five per cent level. In all the other DCCBs they are statistically significant except in the Chennai, Cuddalore, Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Thanjavur, Thoothukudi and Villupuram banks which have growth rates of 22.50, 233.07, 129.03, 33.25, 625.43, 182.32 and 235.39 times respectively. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Coimbatore bank which showed a negative growth rates of -21.98 per cent.

v) Position and Growth of Gross NPAs

The gross NPAs of the DCCBs tripled from Rs.63035 lakhs in 1998-99 to Rs.202445 lakhs in 2003-04. They decreased to Rs.1,29,665 lakhs in 2004-05 due to increase in the recovery of outstanding loans. The Madurai bank has the highest average level of Gross NPAs with 11.55 per cent while the lowest level of 1.24 per cent was found in the Kanyakumari bank. The total gross NPAs in the DCCBs show a positive trend in all the banks except in the Chennai bank with a record of -75.39 time, while it is statistically not significant. Positive and insignificant annual growth rates were found in the Kumbakonam, the Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore and Villupuram banks with growth rates of 562.07, 283.29, 347.64, 704.93, 292.18, 863.36,

663.86 and 221.86 times respectively. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Chennai bank where it was –4.99 per cent.

vi) Position and Growth of Provision for NPAs

The provision for NPAs which had been Rs.19132 lakhs in 1998-99 increased to Rs.79418 lakhs in 2003-04, but it decreased to Rs.74271 lakhs in 2004-05. The Kancheepuram bank has the highest average level of provision for NPAs at 9.86 per cent and the lowest level was found in the Kanyakumari bank at 1.84 per cent. The annual growth rates of provision for NPAs were negative and insignificant in the Thiruchirapalli bank with –152.18 times. There are positive and significant annual growth rates in all the other banks but they were not statistically significant in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kanyakumari and Thanjavur banks where the growth rates were 117.46, 569.54, 155.57, 90.21 and 571 times respectively. The compound growth rates were positive in all the banks except in the Thiruchirapalli bank which recorded a negative growth of –5.41 per cent.

vii) Position and Growth of Net NPAs

The amount of net NPAs of all the DCCBs put together increased from Rs.43903 lakhs in 1998-99 to Rs.1,33,027 lakhs in 2003-04. But it decreased to Rs.98769 lakhs in 2004-05 due to increased recovery of overdues in this period.

The Madurai bank has the highest level of net NPAs with an average of 11.94 per cent and the lowest of 0.48 per cent was found in the Cuddalore bank. It shows that the annual growth rate of net NPAs in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu was negative in the Chennai, Cuddalore, Kancheepuram, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Tirnelveli and Villupuram banks with -192.93, -73.89, -184.32, -74.96, -66.43, -24.14 and -500.82 times respectively. It is not statistically significant in these banks except in the Chennai bank. All the other banks have positive growth rates, but they are statistically significant in the Dindigul, Madurai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli and Vellore banks with 675.46, 1665.14, 685.04, 1943.18 and 1704.61 times respectively. The compound growth rates varied from 49.46 per cent in the Coimbatore bank to 0 per cent in the Chennai, Cuddalore and Villupuram banks respectively.

7.1.3. Impact of NPAs on Various Performance Variables in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

The fifth chapter deals with the impact of NPAs on various performance variables such as advances, standard assets, investments, legal expenses, net profits, spread, overdues and recovery. The findings are presented below:

i) Impact of Advances on NPAs

There was a positive impact of gross advances on NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai bank, where the regression co-efficient of gross advances

was -0.0063 unit. It is not statistically significant. Positive and significant impact of gross advances on NPAs were found in the DCCBs at Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Dindigul, Erode, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar. A unit increase in the gross advances has resulted in an increase in NPAs of these banks by 0.2466, 0.1482, 0.3119, 0.2916, 0.3537, 0.1048, 1.0022, 0.2677, 0.2475, 0.3438, 0.7592, 0.1868 and 0.3410 units respectively. The impact analysis shows that the increase in gross advances has resulted in an increase in NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai bank.

ii) Impact of Standard Assets on NPAs

The negative impact of standard assets on NPAs has been found in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Thanjavur and Tiruvannamalai banks. A unit of increase in the standard assets has resulted in a decrease in NPAs of these banks by -0.0063 , -0.5915 , -0.1314 , -1.0116 , -0.4593 and -0.2879 units respectively. The standard assets have a positive impact on NPAs in all the other banks. But they are statistically significant in the Coimbatore, Erode, Kanyakumari, Salem and Thiruchirapalli banks. A unit of increase in the standard assets has resulted in an increase in NPAs of these banks by 0.2902, 0.3993, 0.1125, 0.2978 and 0.4682 units respectively. The co-efficient of variation in the established regression equation varied from 90.23 per cent in the Erode bank to

0.16 per cent in the Ramanathapuram bank. It can be inferred that the changes in standard assets explain the changes in NPAs to the extent of 90.23 per cent in the Erode DCCBs. The impact analysis shows that the increase in standard assets has resulted in an increase in NPAs in all the DCCBs except in Chennai, Dharmapuri, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Thanjavur and Tiruvannamalai.

iii) Impact of NPAs on Investments

The influence of NPAs on investments in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu was negative in the Chennai, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks. An unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in investments of these banks with -12.2321 , -0.0825 , -0.3163 , -0.6447 and -0.1465 units respectively while it is statistically insignificant. The positive impact of NPAs on investments was noticed in all the other DCCBs but they are statistically significant only in the Kanyakumari and Pudukkottai banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in investments of these banks by 1.3972 and 0.3833 units respectively. It shows that the changes in NPAs in the Kanyakumari bank were explained by the changes in investments to the extent of 77.59 per cent. The impact analysis shows that the increase in NPAs has resulted in an increase in investments in all the DCCBs except in Chennai, Thiruchirapalli, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar.

iv) Impact of NPAs on Legal Expenses

The impact of NPAs on legal expenses of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu had been negative and insignificant in the Chennai, Dindigul, Kanyakumari, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Thiruchirapalli and Villupuram banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the legal expenses of these banks by -3.9377 , -8.8680 , -1.6729 , -1.0218 , -7.0816 , -1.3377 , -2.8638 , -1.6730 , -1.3694 and -9.8889 units respectively. The influence of NPAs on legal expenses was positive in all the other banks but statistically significant in the Tirunelveli and Tiruvannamalai banks. The co-efficient of determination in the regression equation of these banks indicates that the changes in the NPAs explain the changes in the legal expenses to the extent of 68.56 and 63.87 per cent respectively. The impact analysis shows that the increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the legal expenses in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai, Dindigul, Kanyakumari, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Thiruchirapalli and Villupuram banks.

v) Impact of NPAs on Net Profit

The NPAs of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed a negative influence on the net profit in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the net profit of these

banks by -1.3085 , -0.4079 , -0.2912 , -0.3131 , -0.6275 , -0.4466 , -0.0949 , -0.3039 and -0.3367 units respectively. It is statistically significant only in the Dharmapuri bank. The other DCCBs had positive influences of NPAs on net profit. But they were statistically significant only in the Erode and Salem banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the net profit of the Erode and Salem banks by 0.0598 and 1.1469 units respectively. The co-efficient of variation in the established regression equation varied from 91.04 per cent in the Erode bank to 0.10 per cent in the Nilgiris bank. The impact analysis shows that the increase in NPAs has resulted in an increase in the net profit in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai, Dharmapuri, Dindigul, Kumbakonam, Ramanathapuram, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks.

vi) Impact of NPAs on Spread

The impact of NPAs on spread in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu was negative and insignificant in the Chennai and Nilgiris banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the spread of these banks by -2.2172 and -0.0903 units respectively. The impact of NPAs on spread was positive in all the other banks but they were statistically significant in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Dindigul, Erode, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Salem, Thiruchirapalli and Virudhunagar banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the spread of these banks by 0.2931 , 0.3594 , 0.1788 ,

0.4132, 0.3510, 0.4297, 0.1045, 0.2535, 0.2697, 0.2360 and 0.2022 units respectively which shows that the changes in NPAs in the Erode bank is explained by the changes in spread to the extent of 96.57 per cent. The impact analysis shows that an increase in NPAs has resulted in an increase in the spread in all the DCCBs except in Chennai and Nilgiris.

vii) Impact of Overdues on NPAs

The overdues of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed negative and insignificant impact on NPAs in the Chennai and Tiruvannamalai banks. A unit of increase in the overdues resulted in a decrease in NPAs in the Chennai and Tiruvannamalai banks by -0.5067 and -0.4693 units respectively. The overdues have a positive impact on NPAs in all the other DCCBs. But they are statistically significant in the Dindigul, Kancheepuram, Kumbakonam, the Nilgiris, Salem, Thiruchirapalli and Vellore banks. A unit of increase in the overdues resulted in an increase in NPAs of these banks by 1.3640, 1.1321, 0.6633, 1.1961, 1.4984, 2.0166 and 0.4954 units respectively. It shows that the changes in the overdues explain the changes in the NPAs to the maximum extent of 93.90 per cent in the Salem bank. The impact analysis shows that the increase in overdues has resulted in increase in the NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai and Tiruvannamalai banks.

viii) Impact of NPAs on Recovery

There has been a negative impact of NPAs on the recovery in the Chennai and Thanjavur DCCBs. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in a decrease in the recovery of overdues of these banks by -101.63 and -0.0090 units respectively. It is statistically significant at the five per cent level in the Chennai bank. The impact of NPAs was positive in all the other DCCBs but statistically significant in the Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Erode, Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Salem, Thoothukudi and Virudhunagar banks. A unit of increase in the NPAs has resulted in an increase in the recovery of overdues of these banks by 1.2138 , 3.9489 , 4.1958 , 1.6663 , 9.3741 , 1.4870 , 0.6296 and 1.0874 units respectively. It shows that the changes in NPAs explain the changes in the recovery of overdues to the extent of 91.20 per cent in the Kanyakumari bank. The impact analysis shows that the increase in NPAs has resulted in an increase in the recovery of overdues in all the DCCBs except in the Chennai and Thanjavur banks.

ix) Impact of Spread on Net Profit

The spread of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu shows a negative and insignificant impact on net profit in the Dharmapuri, the Nilgiris, Tirunelveli and Villupuram banks. A unit of increase in the spread has resulted in a decrease in the net profit of these banks by -5.9164 , -0.6684 , -9.0546 and -0.0224 units respectively. The spread has a positive impact on the net profit in all the other

DCC banks. But they were statistically significant in the Chennai, Erode, Salem and Tiruvannamalai banks. A unit of increase in the spread has resulted in an increase in the net profit of these banks by 0.7859, 0.1421, 4.2614 and 0.9496 units respectively. The co-efficient of variation in the established regression equation varied from 90.90 per cent in the Erode bank to 0.02 per cent in the Thoothukudi bank. The impact analysis shows that the increase in spread has resulted in an increase in net profit in all the DCCBs except in the Dharmapuri, the Nilgiris, Tirunelveli and Villupuram DCC banks.

x) Impact of Independent Variables on Net Profit

NPAs were positive and significantly correlated with overdues, advances, legal expenses and spread since the correlation co-efficients were 0.8972, 0.8379, 0.8725 and 0.8703 respectively, whereas the advances were positive and significantly correlated with the legal expenses and spread since the correlation co-efficients were 0.9466 and 0.9830 respectively. The variables which have a significant impact on the net profit in the DCCBs were legal expenses and spread since the regression co-efficients of these variables were 1621.24 and 2.2248 respectively.

7.1.4. Perception of Officials on NPAs in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

In the sixth chapter the perception of the officials of NPAs and their opinions for reducing NPAs were analysed in two parts.

PART –A

The first part of the sixth chapter focused on the perception of officials of the reasons for higher NPAs in banks, on the support system of the NPAs, their implication on banking practices and the impact of NPAs on the banking performance. Factor analysis has been applied to analyse the data.

(i) The Important Reasons for Higher NPAs in Banks

a) Bank Related Reasons

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 13 dimensions of the bank related reasons for higher NPAs in banks and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax Criteria. It has been observed from the factor analysis that the first factor is credit and fund related reasons, which is followed by the financial and profession related reasons, auditing and lending related reasons, time and co-ordination related reasons, the skill of the officials, the K.Y. C. Norms and the seventh factor is supervision and follow up action.

(b) Borrower Related Reasons

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 13 dimensions of the borrower related reasons for higher NPAs in banks and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax Criteria.

Factor analysis highlights the fact that five factors namely ‘bank account and time/cost related reasons’, ‘interest rate and funds related reasons’, ‘planning, finance and technology related reasons’, ‘calamities, lenience and demand related reasons and credit appraisal standards’ were identified as official attitude factors towards important borrower related reasons for higher NPAs in banks.

(c) General Reasons

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 9 dimensions of the general reasons for higher NPAs in the banks and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax Criteria. The four factors - ‘legal reasons’, ‘challenges, problems and failure related reasons’, ‘Government policy and capital market related reasons’ and ‘political and legal reasons’ have been identified as general related factors causing NPAs in banks.

(ii) Opinion on Support System Relating to NPAs

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 7 dimensions of the statement of opinion on the support system and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax Criteria. The following three important factors – ‘loan portfolio, repaying capacity and exchange of information’, ‘adequate attention and inadequate information’, and

‘apex bodies do not support the recovery of dues and banks do not know more about the borrowers’ have been identified as reasons for NPAs.

(iii) Opinion on NPAs and their Implication on Banking Practices

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 12 dimensions of the statement of opinion on the implication of NPAs on banking performance and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax Criteria. It has been observed that the following factors ‘NPAs affect banks and aversion to lending because of NPAs’, ‘capital adequacy, interest rate and interest charge’, ‘over all cost of borrowers and loan to agriculture and SSI’, ‘loan to business people’, ‘loan to SHG’ and ‘capital adequacy norms can reduce/minimise the risk and loan to micro credit scheme decreased’ have been found to be significant factors causing NPAs.

(iv) Impact of NPAs on Banking Norms

The principal component factor analysis method was applied to the inter correlation matrix of 11 dimensions of the impact of NPAs on reflected areas and the results were rotated using the Kaiser Varimax Criteria. The analysis shows that the following five factors namely, ‘expenditure and reserve and surplus’, ‘profit and interest rate’, ‘intermediation cost’ and ‘spread’, ‘provision for bad debts and contraction of credit’ and ‘investment in Government securities and

CRR' were significant opinion factors for causing the impact of NPAs on reflected areas.

PART B

In the second part of the sixth chapter the researcher has analysed the opinions of officials to contain NPAs, for improvement of banking performance, on remedies for reducing NPAs and their observations on borrowers' repaying behaviour. These have been analysed with the help of the KS Test.

(i) Opinions of Officials to Contain NPAs

The hypotheses on the opinion of officials to contain NPAs have been tested with the help of the KS Test. All the null hypotheses have been rejected. Thus each statement has positive attitude of the officials according to their importance of ratings (Vide Table 6.7 – 6.11). A majority of the officials have suggested that the banks should have to educate their employees on NPAs and their effect on the banks' performance. This statement is ranked first (Vide Table 6.12).

(ii) Opinions of Officials for Improvement of Banking Performance

The hypotheses on the opinions of officials on the improvement of banking performance have been tested with the help of the KS Test. All the null

hypotheses have been rejected. Thus each statement has a positive attitude of the officials according to their importance of ratings (Vide Table 6.13 – 6.20). A majority of the officials are of the view that political interference must be avoided. This statement is ranked first (Vide Table 6.21).

(iii) Opinions on Remedies for Reducing NPAs

The hypotheses on the opinion of officials regarding the remedies for reducing NPAs have been tested with the help of the KS Test. All the null hypotheses have been rejected. Thus each statement has a positive attitude of the officials according to their importance of ratings (Vide Table 6.22 – 6.31). A majority of the officials have suggested that proper selection of the borrowers' activity will help reduce NPAs. This statement is ranked first (Vide Table 6.32).

(iv) Opinions on Borrowers' Repaying Behaviour

The hypotheses on the opinion of officials regarding the borrowers repaying behaviour have been tested with the help of the KS Test. All the null hypotheses have been rejected. Thus each statement has a positive attitude of the officials according to their importance of ratings (Vide Table 6.33 – 6.36). A majority of the officials view that good borrowers were willing to repay. This statement is ranked first (Vide Table 6.37).

7.2 SUGGESTIONS

The following suggestions are framed from the study which may help solve the problem of NPAs if they are accommodated in the future decision making process.

1. The growth rate in the number of memberships in the DCCBs is not significant in the Chennai, Erode, Kanyakumari, Madurai, Pudukkottai, Sivagangai, Thoothukudi, Vellore and Virudhunagar banks. An attempt is required to be made by these banks to increase the number by enrolling new societies into membership. The banks should provide adequate guidance to the members by instituting member education programmes which will make them aware of their rights and duties.

2. The growth rate of branches is found statistically not significant in the Cuddalore, Erode, Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Pudukkottai, Salem, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, Tirunelveli, Tiruvannamalai, Vellore, Villupuram and Virudhunagar banks. These banks should open new branches at suitable places with a view to augmenting their deposits.

3. A negative growth rates of deposits was found in the Tirunelveli bank. This bank should review its deposit mobilisation process and take additional steps to mobilise deposits from untapped resources.

4. A negative growth rates of borrowings was found only in the Kancheepuram bank. The state co-operative bank and the state government must provide the necessary financial support to this bank by which the bank will be able to distribute loans to the Primary Agricultural Co-operative Banks (PACBs).

5. Negative growth rates of investments were found in the Coimbatore, Thiruchirapalli, Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Virudhunagar banks. These banks should take all the necessary steps to increase their investments in the appropriate financial agencies.

6. The Ramanathapuram, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks had negative growth rates of net profit. There is need for special efforts to improve profitability through cost reduction devices.

7. The problem of overdues has been found in five DCCBs in Tamil Nadu viz., the Kancheepuram, Kanyakumari, Ramanathapuram, Salem and Thiruchirapalli banks. This must be addressed through proper recovery proceeding and the level of NPA must be brought down so that the banks can have liquidity and profitability.

8. NPAs include sub-standard assets, doubtful assets and loss assets. The growth rates of sub-standard assets, doubtful assets and loss assets were positive in a majority of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu. The positive growth rates of

these assets would have led to falling profitability and erosion of the net worth of the banks. The banks have to minimise these assets considerably through effective recovery proceedings for earning profit.

9. The growth rates of Gross NPAs and Net NPAs were positive in a majority of the banks. The problems of NPAs together (both in gross and net terms) were relatively high during the study period. NPA is not just a problem for banks, they are bad for the economy. The money locked up as NPA is not available for productive use and to that extent the banks seek to make provisions for NPA or write them off. It adversely affects their profit and results in a higher rate of interest to their diligent borrower customers. This also raises the cost of administration. The steps taken at the appropriate time may help in avoiding NPAs. Qualitative appraisal, supervision and follow up should be taken up for the present advances to avoid future NPAs.

10. The positive growth rates in the provision for NPAs in all the DCCBs except in the Thiruchirapalli bank result in the growing problem of the existence of NPAs. This suggests that the quality of assets must be improved through an effective credit delivery system and an effective recovery mechanism.

11. The task of containment of NPAs by arresting slippage of accounts from standard assets to NPAs was a cause of concern for almost all the banks due to the government policy of liberal credit to farmers and other weaker sections

under priority sector loan. Relentless monitoring and introduction of loan review mechanism of standard assets may be of some help in containing the slippage to NPAs.

12. The impact of NPAs has resulted in lower interest rates to depositors, higher intermediation cost, higher rate of interest to borrowers, higher rates of service charges to all customers, more provisions towards loan losses, more capital contribution and less return to share holders by way of dividend, etc. All these costs are finally passed on to the Government, which is forced to bail out the banks through its budgetary provisions. This means that ultimately the tax payers bear the cost of NPAs for no fault of theirs. So the DCCBs should create a separate cells for speedy recovery of loans. Recovery performance of all the officials concerned should be critically evaluated and outstanding performance should be properly rewarded. The banks should also adopt risk management systems and practices to prevent the emergence of fresh NPAs.

13. The DCCBs in Tamil Nadu should have to educate their employees on NPAs and their effect on the banks' performance through periodic awareness programmes.

14. The political interference in credit allocation, and in the appointment of chief executives, proposed concessions/relief announced by political functionaries from public platforms, stay orders on legal process of recovery and disbursement

of loans at the hands of political dignitaries in loan melas were a few more factors observed to have increased NPAs in the DCCB in Tamil Nadu. These banks should necessarily avoid political interference.

15. The DCCBs in Tamil Nadu should introduce incentive/reward system to staff engaged in the collection process.

16. The banks should update the addresses of borrowers, so that the recovery process can be followed up. Banks should have personal contact with the borrowers through periodic meets under the KYC norms.

17. The DCCBs in Tamil Nadu have to give a lot of importance to credit monitoring and follow-up action so that the symptoms of sickness can be detected at an early stage for taking timely corrective action. Proper follow up and supervision are required to ensure asset creation, asset utilisation and to prevent under-utilisation and mis-utilisation of loans.

18. Officials have assigned first rank to good borrowers are willing to repay (vide table 6.37). The banks therefore should be very careful in selecting the good borrowers to avoid NPAs by giving due weightage to the honesty integrity and credit worthiness of the borrowers.

7.3 CONCLUSION

The DCCBs play a significant role in the economy of Tamil Nadu. The overall performance of the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu is, however, a mixed one. The heavy overdues, inefficient funds management, inadequate and untrained staff, lack of adequate supervision, poor profit earning, defective loan policies, book-adjustments and inadequate bad and doubtful debt reserves are some of their weaknesses. The accumulation of NPAs has been detrimental to the financial health of the banks. The banks have faced additional burden by creating more provision for management of NPAs. While the profitability of the banks is rather low, the liquidity position warrants strengthening. The depleting solvency is fatal to operational efficiency.

This picture reiterates the need for effective recovery management, particularly of short-term loans. Stringent measures must be taken to control and prevent NPAs; besides, effective credit monitoring and use of effective execution of decrees, and resort to various avenues of recovery, especially compromise settlements, would contain the problem of NPAs effectively.

In this study, a sound theoretical and analytical background has been provided. If the study could help the planners and officials of the co-operative banks in removing the problem of NPAs the researcher will feel that he has been amply rewarded. It is hoped that this endeavour will provide the basis for further research in other states of India. The researcher has the satisfaction of having undertaken a socially relevant project.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abhiman Roy Das, "Profitability in Public Sector Banks", *RBI Occasional Papers*, Vol.20, No.1, Summer 1999, pp. 55-77.
- Ammannaya, K.K., "Banking Reforms and New Challenges for Banks", *Southern Economist*, 15th July 1997, p.4.
- Annual Report*, Tamil Nadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Ltd., Chennai, 2005.
- Annual Report*, The Tamilnadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Ltd., Chennai, 2003-2004, pp.125-129.
- Anumudgavkar, Leopuri and Joydeep Sengupta, Revitalising Indian banks., *Treasury Management*, November 2001, pp.56-58.
- Arun Yeole, "The Problem of NPAs", *Yojana*, Vol.48, November 2004, pp. 35-38.
- Arvind Jain, *Credit Risk Management in Banks*, Edited Book, Raj Publishing Houses, Jaipur, 2005.
- Ballabh, J., "The Indian Banking Industry: Challenges Ahead", *IBA Bulletin*, Vol. XXIII, No. 4 & 5, April 2001, pp. 8-10.
- Berger, Allen N. and Robert De Young, "Problems of Loans and Cost Efficiency in Commercial Banks", *Journal of Banking and Finance*, Vol.21, No.6, June 1997.
- Bhattacharjee, P.K., "NPA Management – Perform or Perish", *ICFAI Readers*, Vol.1, No.11, October 1999, pp. 51-52.
- Bhupesh, "Ernst Pegs NPA 50% Higher at \$ 25 Billion", *The Business Standard*, July 12, 2002.
- Bidani, S.N., *Management of Non-Performing Assets in Banks*, Vision Book Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 2002.
- Caprio, G. and Klingebiel, D., "Bank Insolvency Bad Luck, Bad Policy or Bad Banking?", Annual World Bank Conference on Development Economics 1996, *Policy Research Working Paper*, 1620, World Bank, 1996.

- Carlton Pereira, "Investing in NPAs will Investors Bite?", *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. XXXIX, No.42, October 16, 2004, pp. 4602-4604.
- Ganesan, N., "A Study on the Performance Analysis of the State Co-operative Banks in India", *Prajnan*, Vol.XXXIV, No.4, 2005-06, pp.311-321.
- Chakraborty, K.C., "Management of NPAs Trends and Challenges", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, October 2005, pp. 30-33.
- Chari, P.S.V. and Narasimham, P.S., "A Prescription of Good Credit Management", *The Hindu* (Chennai), 3rd January 2002, BS-1.
- Chellani, D.K. and Rita Rai, "The Performance of District Central Co-operative Banks in Gujarat", *Indian Co-operative Review*, Vol.41, No.4, April 2004, pp. 289-296.
- Chinnappa, B. and Keshava Reddy, "An Empirical Analysis of Growth and Instability in Sugar Industry", *Agricultural Bankers*, Vol.23, No.2, April-June 1999, pp.27-32.
- Circular of the NABARD Letter No.(TN) 972/DOS/1/2003-04 Dated 2.05.2003, pp. 1-2.
- Circular of the RBI, Letter No. RPCD; No. BC-155/07-37-02/95-96, Dated 22nd June 1996.
- Circular of the Registrar of Co-operative Societies, Tamil Nadu, No. 500057/73, Dated 27.04.1973.
- Circular of the Registrar of Co-operative Societies, Tamil Nadu, No. 200031/8/A1 (2), Dated 24.08.1982.
- Das and Abhiman, "Efficiency of Public Sector Banks: An Application of Data Development Model", *Prajnan*, Vol. 28, No.2, September 1999.
- Das, A. and Ghosh, S., "Determination of Credit Risk", Paper presented at the Conference of *Money, Risk and Investments* held at Nottingham Trent University in November, 2003.
- Ens Economic Bureau, "Banks' Bad Loans Other Sticky Assets Touch Rs.2,36,000 Crore", *The New Indian Express*, Mumbai, January 5, 2006, p.13.

- Fed N. Kerlinger, *Methods of Factor Analysis: Foundations of Behavioural Research*, New York: Holt Reinhart and Winston Inc., 1973, p.470.
- Ganesan, P., “Determinants of Profit and Profitability of Public Sector Banks in India: A Profit Function Approach”, *Journal of Financial Management and Analysis*, Vol.14, No.1, 2001, pp. 27-37.
- Gourav Vallabh, Anoop Bhatia and Saurabh Mishra, “Non-Performing Assets of Indian Public, Private and Foreign Sector Banks” An Empirical Assessment”, *The ICAI Journal of Bank Management*, Vol.VI, No.3, August 2007, pp.7-28.
- Gupta and Debashish, “NPA Management: Innovation is the Key”, *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol.3, No.3, November, 1997.
- Gupta, S.P., *Statistical Methods*, Sultan Chand & Sons, New Delhi, 2006.
- Hiremath, G.M., Sastry, K.N.R. and Naik, A.D., “Deteriorating Potentiality of Tank Irrigation in Karnataka”, *Agricultural Bankers*, Vol.22, No.4, October-December, 1998, pp. 36-40.
- Indira Rajaraman and Garima Vasistha, “Non-Performing Loans of PSU Banks”, *Economic and Political Weekly*, February 2, 2002.
- Janardhan Rao, N. and Ravi Babu Adusumilli, “Asset Reconstruction Companies (ARCs) Cure for NPAs”, *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol.X1, Issue 12, December 2005, pp.52-54.
- Janathan Anderson, Berry H. Durston and Millicent Poole, *Thesis and Assignment Writing*, Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1987.
- John Neter, William Wasserman and G.A. Whitmore, *Applied Statistics*, Quoted in Library of Congress Cataloging Publications, Second Edition, p.739.
- Jugale, V.B., *Financial Sector Reforms in the World*, Serials Publications, New Delhi, 2006, p.216.
- Justin Nelson Michael, *A Study on Non-Performing Assets in Co-operative Banks with Reference to Cuddalore District Central Co-operative Bank Ltd., Tamilnadu*, Ph.D. thesis submitted to Annamalai University, Chidambaram, May 2005.

- Katuri Nageswara Rao, "NPAs Ground Realities", *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol.V, Issue VIII - April 2000, pp. 43-46.
- Kaveri, V.S., "Prevention of NPAs – Suggested Strategies", *IBA Bulletin*, Vol. XXIII, No.8, August 2001, pp. 7-9.
- Kaveri, V.S., "Relationship between Recovery and Profitability of Bank – A Study", *SBI Monthly Review*, Vol.33, 1995.
- Khasnobis, S., "NPAs: Emerging Challenges", *The Indian Banker*, Vol. I, No.11, November 2006, pp.17-20.
- Klingebl and Daniela, "The Use of Asset Management Companies in the Resolution of Banking Crisis: Cross-Country Experiences", *Working Paper*, No.2284, under Domestic Finance, Saving Financial System, Stock Markets, World Bank, 2000.
- Kothari, C.R., *Research Methodology – Methods and Techniques*, New Age International Publications (P) Ltd., New Delhi, 2007.
- Krishnamurthy, K.V., "At No Rate", *The Business Standard*, June 13, 2002.
- Kwan, Simon Robert and Eisenbies, "*An Analysis of Inefficiencies in Banking: A Stochastic Cost Frontier Approach*", Presented at a Seminar on Productivity Analysis at the University of George, October, 1994.
- Lakshmanan, C. and Dharmendran, A., "Impact of NPAs on the Performance Variables in Chennai Central Co-operative Bank", *Indian Co-operative Review*, Vol.44, No.4, April 2007, pp. 291-297.
- Levine, Stephan and Krehbiel, *Statistics for Managers – Using Microsoft Excel*, Prentice-Hall of India (P) Ltd., New Delhi, 2005.
- Mahanti, Tushar K.E.T., "Intelligence Group, Industrial Downturn- High Interest Burden Squeeze Commercial Bank Spreads", *The Economic Times*, April 17, 2002.
- Mamoria, C.B., *Rural Credit and Agricultural Co-operative in India*, Kitab Mahal, Allahabad, 1983,p.129.

- Manual on Deposits*, The Tamil Nadu State Apex Co-operative Bank Ltd., Chennai, January 1997, p. A-8.
- Master Circular of the NABARD N.B . BOS. HO/BOL/1577/B.57.2002.03 Dated 17.08.2002.pp.1-15
- Mathur, B.S., *Co-operation in India*, Sahitya Bhavan Publishers & Distributors (P) Ltd., Agra, 2001.
- Meena Sharma, “Problem of NPAs and Its Impact on Strategic Banking Variables”, *Finance India*, Vol.XIX, No.3, September 2005, pp.953-967.
- Monica Soni, “NPA Management by Rural Banks: A Critical Appraisal”, *Indian Journal of Accounting*, Vol.XXXIII, December 2002, pp.67-71.
- Muniappan, G.P., “Confederation of Indian Industry”, *Banking Submit 2002* at Mumbai on April 1, 2002.
- Murthy, J., Vishwanatha and Bayya Reddy, A., “Defaults of Financial Institutions at What Cost”, *The Chartered Accountant*, Vol.37, No.6, December 1988.
- NABARD, Prudential Norms on Income Recognition Asset Classification and Provisioning – SCBs and DCCBs, *Master Circular*, No.193/Dos-21/2002, 17th August 2002.
- Nagesh Pinge, “Risk Management A New Approach Needed”, *Chartered Financial Analyst*, October 2005, p.35.
- Narasimham, M., *Committee on Banking Sector Reforms*, 1998, p.75.
- Office of the Comptroller of Currency, *Bank Failure: An Evaluation of the Factors Contributing to the Failure of National Banks* (Washington DC: Office of the Comptroller of Currency, June 1988).
- Pathania, K.S., *Management of Co-operative Finance in India*, Anmol Publications (P) Ltd., New Delhi, 1998.
- Pati, A.P., “NPAs – Causes, Consequences and Cures”, *The Management Accountant*, Vol.34, No.11, November 1999, pp. 853-857.
- Phadhis, S.G., “NPA Management Experience of Co-operative Banks”, *Urban Credit*, March 1999, p. 29.

- Prasanna, G. Deshmukh, *Working of Co-operative Banks in India – Overview and Prospective*, Kanishka Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, 2002.
- Prem.S. Sarma, “Financial Sector Reforms and the Co-operatives”, *The Co-operator*, Vol.36, No.6, December 1998, pp.237-240.
- Rajendra Singh, “Empowering Banks for Recovery of NPAs”, *The Journal of Indian Institute of Banking & Finance*, January-March 2005, pp.5-13.
- Rajendran Kakker, “NPA Management – Role of Asset Reconstruction Companies”, *IBA Bulletin*, Vol.XXVI, No.12, December 2004.
- Rajendran, K., “Non-Performing Assets”, *Tamil Nadu Journal of Co-operation*, Vol.4, No.4, February 2004, pp.14-20.
- Ramachandra Reddy, B., *Management of Non-Performing Assets in Banking and Financial Institutions*, Edited Book, Serials Publications, New Delhi, 2004.
- Ranjana Kumar, “NPA Management for Better Banking, Proceedings of the Bank Economists Conference 2000” *-Banking in the New Millennium*, pp.68-70.
- RBI Bulletin Supplement to Annual Report 1993-94*, RBI Bombay, August 1994, p. 142.
- RBI Bulletin*, Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India 1995-96, RBI, Bombay, December 1996, p.108.
- RBI Bulletin*, Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India 1999-2000, RBI, Bombay, December 2000, p.128.
- RBI Circular to CCBs, RPCD. No.BC155/07.37/1995-96, RBI Bombay, June 1996, pp. 1-8.
- Reserve Bank of India Bulletin*, Supplement to Annual Report 1991-92, RBI, Bombay, October 1992, p.117.
- Reserve Bank of India, “Some Aspects and Issues Relating to NPAs in Commercial Banks”, *Reserve Bank of India Bulletin*, Vol.50, No.3, July 1999, pp. 913-936.

- Reserve Bank of India, "Trend and Progress of Banking in India 2000-01", Supplement to RBI Bulletin, Appendix II 9(B), December 2001, p.194.
- Reserve Bank of India, All India Rural Credit Review Committee, Bombay, 1969, p. 159.
- Reserve Bank of India, All Indian Rural Credit Survey: The General Report Summary, Bombay, 1955, p. 43.
- Reserve Bank of India, Report of the Committee to Review Arrangements for Institutional Credit for Agriculture and Rural Development (Craficard), Bombay, 1981, p. 383.
- Reserve Bank of India, *Report of the Working Group and Restructuring of Public Sector Banks*, RBI, Bombay, (Chairman M.S Verma)1999.
- Reserve Bank of India, Study on Geographical and Sectoral Distributor of NPAs in Banks, April 2001.
- Reserve Bank of India, Tarapore Committee, *The Report of the Committee on Capital Account Convertibility* RBI, Bombay.
- Reserve Bank of India, *The Report of the Agricultural Credit Review Committee*, RBI, Bombay, 1989.
- Reserve Bank of India, *The Report of the Working Committee*, RBI, Bombay, 1999.
- Ross Gary Howard, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Kentucky, 1996, p.126.
- Samal, B., "The NPA Overhang: Magnitude, Solution and Legal Reforms", *Vinimaya*, Vol.23, No.2, October-December 2002, pp.12-17.
- Sami Uddin and Mahfoozur Rahman, *Co-operative Sector in India*, S.Chand & Company (P) Lte., New Delhi, 1983.
- Sanjai Singh Rathore and Alka Singh, "Non-Performing Assets and Capital Adequacy", *Indian Journal of Accounting*, Vol.XXXV, No.1, December 2004, pp.78-81.

- Sanjay Kumar, “NPAs in Regional Rural Banks: Impact and Management”, *The Management Accountant*, Vol.35, No.11, November 2000, pp.855-858.
- Santi Gopal Maji and Soma Dey, “Management of NPAs in UCB: A Case Study of the Khatra People’s Co-operative Bank Ltd”, *The Management Account*, Vol.38, No.3, March 2003, p.195.
- Sardar Narinder Sing Gujral, “The NPA Problem Miles to Go”, *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol. IX, Issue 3, March 2003, pp. 73-78.
- Satish, D., “The Securitization Bill 2002 will it Perform?”, *Chartered Financial Analyst*, Vol. VIII, Issue 9, September 2002, pp.16-18.
- Satyanarayana, K. and Ganti Subrahmanyam, “Anatomy of NPAs of Commercial Banks”, *The ICAI Journal of Applied Finance*, Vol.6, No.3, July 2000, pp. 14-26.
- Satyanarayana, K., “Feasible NPA Levels of Banks for Capital Account Convertibility”, *Prajnan*, Vol.24, No.3, March 1998, pp.325-345.
- SCBs need \$13 bn to Support Asset Losses, *The Economic Times*, December 20, 2000.
- Selvan, K.G. and Samwel Kakuko Lopoyetum, “A Study on Non-performing Assets Management in Dharmapuri Town Co-operative Bank – A Case Study”, *Co-operative Perspective*, Vol.34, No.4, January-March 2000, pp.45-55.
- Selvaraju, R., Vasanthi, G. and Justin Nelson Michael, “Effect of NPAs on Operational Efficiency of CCBs”, *Indian Economic Panorama*, Vol.16, No.3, October 2006, p.34.
- Singh, R., “Profitability Management in Banks under Deregulated Environment”, *IBA Bulletin*, Vol.XXV, No.7, July 2003, pp. 19-26.
- Sivaprakasam, P., *Personnel Management in CCBs in India - Policies and Practies*, Kanishka Publishers & Distributors, New Delhi, 1993.
- Srinivas Rao, H., *Working of the Andhra Pradesh State Co-operative Bank – An Evaluation*, Ph.D. Thesis, Osmania University, Hyderabad in May 2002, Andhra Pradesh, India.

- Srinivas Subbarao, P., "Is Securitisation Ordinance Minimising NPAs or is Improving the Profits of PSBs by Reducing NPAs", *The Management Account*, Vol.38, No. 3, March 2003, pp.208-210.
- Swaminathan, S. and Anklesaria Aiyar, "Household Capitalism, The Consumer Finance Boom is mainly an investment Boom", *The Economic Times*, March 20, 2002.
- Tannan, M.L., *Banking Law and Practice in India*, Indian Law House, New Delhi, 2004.
- Tarapore, S.S., *The Committee on Capital Account Convertibility*, 1997, p.133.
- Thanikodi, R., CCBs in India: Problems and Remedies, *The Co-operator*, Vol.42, No.12, June 2005, P.523.
- The Madras Co-operative Manual Government of Madras, 1952,p. 94.
- The National Federation of State Co-operative Bank Limited Publication, "Concept and Computation of Prime Lending Rate", *The Co-operator*, Vol.XXXVII, No.3, September 1999, p.109.
- Toor, N.S., *Non-Performing Advances in Banks*, Skylark Publications, New Delhi, 1998.
- Tripathy, S.N., *Co-operatives for Rural Development*, Edited Books, Discovery Publishing House, New Delhi, 1998.
- Uppal, R.K. and Rimpi Kaur, "Banking Sector Reform: Rational, Efficacy and Agenda for Third Reforms", *Indian Journal of Marketing*, Vol.XXXVII, No.6, June 2007, pp.12-22.
- Valsamma Antony, "Co-operative Banks in the Grip of NPAs", *Southern Economist*, Vol.43, No.20, February 15, 2005, p.21.
- Vanniarajan, T., "Correlates of NPAs and Performance of Banks", *Indian Journal of Accounting*, Vol.XXXVI, No.2, June 2006, pp.72-77.
- Vashisht, A.K., "Commercial Banking in the Globalized Environment", *Political Economy Journal of India*, Vol.13, Issue 1 & 2, January-June, 2004, pp.1-11.

Venkitaramanan, S., “There is More to NPAs than Poor Credit Appraisal”, *The Business Line*, July 12, 1999.

Venkitaramanan, S., “Weak on Solutions- Comment on Trend and Progress of Banking 1999”, *The Economic Times*, December 1, 1999.

Wahab, A., *Commercial Banks under Reforms: Performance and Issue*, Edited Book, Deep and Deep Publications, New Delhi, 2001.

Westgaard, Sjur and Nicovan der wijst, *Default Probabilities in a Corporate Bank Portfolio: A Logistic Model Approach*, Elsevier, 2001.

Other References

Reports

Annual Reports of RBI at Bombay from 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Annual Reports of NABARD, Bombay, from 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd., Chennai, from 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Annual Reports of All DCCBs in Tamil Nadu from 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Report of Trend and Progress of Banking in India at Bombay from 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Statistical Table relating to Banks in India, Bombay, from 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Journals

Co-operative Perspective, Vaikunth Mehta National Institute of Co-operative Management, Pune.

Bank Quest – The Journal of Indian Institute of Banking & Finance, Mumbai.

IBA Bulletin, Indian Banks’ Association, Mumbai.

- Indian Co-operative Review*, National Co-operative Union of India, New Delhi.
- Prajnan* (Journal of Social and Management Science), National Institute of Bank Management, Pune.
- Tamilnadu Journal of Co-operation*, Tamilnadu Co-operative Union, Chennai.
- The Co-operator*, National Co-operative Union of India, New Delhi.
- The Journal of Indian Institute of Bankers*, Mumbai.
- The Maharashtra Co-operative Quarterly*, Mumbai.
- ICRA Bulletin*, Money & Finance, New Delhi.
- Southern Economist*, Bangalore.
- Vinimaya*, National Institute of Bank Management, Pune.
- The Journal of Banking Studies*, New Delhi.
- ICFAI Readers*, The ICFAI University Press, Hyderabad.
- Chartered Financial Analyst*, The ICFAI University Press, Hyderabad.
- Economic and Political Weekly*, Mumbai.
- Finance India*, Indian Institute of Finance, New Delhi.
- The Journal of Finance*, The Journal of the American Finance Association.
- The Journal of Business*, The University of Chicago.
- The ICFAI Journal of Bank Management*, The Institute of Bank Management and Research, The ICFAI University Press, Hyderabad.
- Indian Journal of Marketing*, New Delhi.

Commercial Paper

Business Standard.

The Economic Times.

The Financial Express.

The Hindu Business Line.

Financial Times.

Websites

<http://www.rbi.org.in>

<http://www.nabard.org.in>

<http://www.tnscbank.com>

<http://www.ncui.nic.in>

<http://www.tncu.tn.gov.in>

<http://www.tn.gov.in>

<http://www.worldbank.org>

ANNEXURE-A**“Non-Performing Assets in District
Central Co-operative Banks in Tamil Nadu -
An Empirical Study”**Questionnaire for Bank Officials

1. Personal Information

1. Name (Optional) : _____

2. Designation : _____

3. Name of the institution : _____

4. Position:

Top Level Management Middle Level Management Lower Level Management

5. Experience

1. Less than 10 years 2. 10-20 years 3. 20-30 years 4. Above 30 years

Please indicate your views based on your experience and expertise by placing a [✓] mark at the appropriate column in the five point response scale given below.

1. Strongly Agree (SA)
 2. Agree (A)
 3. No Opinion (N.O.)
 4. Disagree (D.A)
 5. Strongly Disagree (S.D.A.)

2. The following are the important reasons for higher NPAs in banks.**A. Bank Related Reasons:**

1. Siphoning of funds
 2. Lack of supervision and follow-up action
 3. Poor auditing practices
 4. Lack of proper co-ordination between various financial institutions and banks

	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA
1. Siphoning of funds					
2. Lack of supervision and follow-up action					
3. Poor auditing practices					
4. Lack of proper co-ordination between various financial institutions and banks					

5. Low skill of the officials in processing loan proposals					
6. Fear psychosis among banks for compromise settlements					
7. Lack of proper pre-sanction appraisal of credit proposals					
8. Deficiencies in post-credit supervision					
9. Lack of professionalism of bank's Board					
10. Over/under financing of project					
11. Direct lending by bank to priority sector					
12. Long interval between sanction and disbursements of loans					
13. Non adoption of K.Y.C. Norms					

B. Borrower Related Reasons

	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA
1. Diversion of funds					
2. Deficiency in credit appraisal standards					
3. Higher Rate of interest					
4. Lower Rate of interest					
5. Lack of proper project planning					
6. Inefficient financial management					
7. Inappropriate technology					
8. Unauthorized withdrawal of funds from bank A/C					
9. Non-Monitoring of Bank's accounts					
10. Time/cost overrun of project					
11. No demand for security					
12. Adoption of lenient approach on defaults					
13. Natural calamities like floods and accidents					

C. General Reasons

	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA
1. Political interference					
2. Lack of legal support through exemption to certain categories					
3. Slow legal process for recovery of bank dues					
4. Boom/Depression of capital market					
5. Liberalisation of government policies					
6. Product/marketing failure					
7. Industrial sickness and labour problem					

5. The impact of NPAs on Banking Norms

	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA
1. Erosion of profit					
2. Increasing spread (Interest Income)					
3. Increasing intermediation cost					
4. Increase in Provisions for bad & doubtful debits					
5. Declining Reserves and Surpluses					
6. Increase in market borrowings					
7. Contraction of credit					
8. Increased more legal Expenditure					
9. Increase in the interest rate					
10. Increasing investment in Govt. Securities to meet SLR					
11. Increase in the Case Reserve Ratio (CRR)					

6. Opinions to contain NPAs.

	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA
1. Problems of NPA can be contained to a great extent by maintaining a continuous rapport/relationship with borrower					
2. Borrowers have to be made more accountable/responsible to contain problem					
3. Involvement of Auditors, Accountants, Regulators, Representative bodies, would help recover bank dues in an effective manner					
4. Corporate Governance in corporate bodies can help improve the conduct of accounts with banks and bring down level of NPAs					
5. Banks will have to educate their employees about NPA and its effect on the banks' performance					

7. Opinions for improvement of Banking Performance

	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA
1. Improved Credit Appraisal System will help reduce NPAs					
2. Continuous monitoring and follow-up action are required for reducing NPAs					
3. Improved legal system with increased role of DRT will bring down NPAs					
4. Improved exchange of information will reduce NPAs					
5. Improved market Intelligence system will help reduce NPAs					
6. Avoiding political interference will help reduce NPAs					
7. Involvement of representative bodies will reduce NPAs					
8. Introduction of incentive/reward system to staff engaged in collection process will help reduce NPAs					

8. Opinions on Remedies for Reducing NPAs.

- 1. Proper selection of the borrowers' projects will reduce NPAs
- 2. Financing only viable projects will bring down NPAs
- 3. Extending need based financing will help reduce NPAs
- 4. Ensuring proper end-use will help reduce NPAs
- 5. Proper post sanction follow-up will reduce NPAs
- 6. Regular contact with borrowers will help reduce NPAs
- 7. Regular monitoring of the accounts will help reduce NPAs
- 8. Avoiding overdrawing extraneous debt will help reduce NPAs
- 9. Holding of recovery camps will reduce NPAs
- 10. Special Incentives for prompt repayment will reduce NPAs

SA	A	NO	DA	SDA

9. Opinions on borrowers' repaying Behavior.

- 1. Good borrowers are willing to repay
- 2. Good borrowers are not willing to repay
- 3. Bad borrowers are willing to repay
- 4. Bad borrowers are not willing to repay

SA	A	NO	DA	SDA

Annexure-B

PERCENTILE OF THE D (n) DISTRIBUTION

N	0.90	0.95	0.99
5	0.51	0.56	0.67
10	0.37	0.41	0.49
15	0.30	0.34	0.40
20	0.26	0.29	0.35
25	0.24	0.26	0.32
30	0.22	0.24	0.29
35	0.20	0.22	0.27
40	0.19	0.21	0.25
45	0.18	0.20	0.24
50	0.17	0.19	0.23
N>50	1.22/n	1.36/n	1.63/n

Source : john Neter, William Wassermann and G.A whitemore, applied static, quoted in library of congress. Cataloging in publication data, second Edition p.739.

ANNEXURE-C

PRUDENTIAL NORMS FOR COOPERATIVE BANKS
Asset Classification and Provisioning Statement
(For the year ended 31 March 199--)

(A) LOANS AND ADVANCES

	Category of Credit Facility						
	SAO Short Term	Cash Credit	ST(Non SAO)	Cash Credit &O/Ds	Bills Discounted Purchased	Term Loans (All Types)	Total
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
I. Amount outstanding							
II. Assets classification							
1. Standard							
2. Sub-standered (Overdues upto 3 yrs.)							
3. Doubtful							
i. Secured overdues							
a. Over 3 yrs. to 4 yrs.							
b. Over 4 yrs. to 6 yrs.							
c. Over 6 years.							
ii. Unsecured Over dues							
4. Loss assets							
III. Provisioning required							
1. Sub-standard (10% of items II(2))							
2. i). Doubtful assets.							
ii). 20% of item ii(3) (i) (a)							
iii). 30% of item II (3) (i) (b)							
iv). 50% of item II (3) (i) (c)							
v). 100% of item II (3) (ii)							
3. Loss assets (100% of item II (4))							
4. Total of item III (1) to (3)							

(B) OTHER ASSETS/LIABILITIES (OUTSTANDING)

Particulars	Provision Required	Made
(i) Income Recognition (a) Over interest taken to P&L A/c (b) Accrued interest taken to income a/c in the previous year but not realised (c) Fee Commission & Other income taken to P&L A/c in the previous year but not realised Total of (i) (ii) Depreciation in investments (a) Govt. securities/bonds, etc. (b) Share in other coop. Institutions (c) Other investments shares etc. Total of (ii) (iii) Frauds, embezzlements, etc. (iv) PF, Gratuity, etc. (v) Other liabilities like rent, rates, taxes, etc (vi) Contingent/off balance sheet exposures (vii) Interest on deposits and borrowings outstanding as liability Depreciation on other assets like land, building, furniture, fixtures, etc.		
Total		

- (C) (i) Total provision to be made in balance sheet item III
 (4) (Col.8) + total of col. 2 of part B)
 (ii) Actually made
 (iii) Deficit (-) /surplus (+)

ANNEXURE-D

Agriculture advances (direct finance to farmers) for which NPA norms are applicable

- 1) Short-term loan for rising i.e. for crop loans. In addition advances upto Rs. 1 lakh to farmers against pledge/ hypothecation of agricultural produce (including warehouse receipts) for a period not exceeding 6 months, where the farmers were given- crop loans for raising the produce, provided the borrowers draw credit from one bank.
- 2) Medium and long-term loans (provided directly to farmers for financing production and development needs)
 - i) **Purchase of agricultural implements and machinery**
 - a) Purchase of agricultural implements – Iron ploughs, harrows, hose, land-levelers, bund formers, hand tools, sprayers, dusters, hay-press, sugarcane crushers, thresher machines, etc.
 - b) Constructing, deepening clearing of surface wells, boring of wells, electrification of wells, purchase of oil engines and installation of electric motor and pumps.
 - c) Purchase and installation of turbine pumps, construction of field channels (open as well as underground) etc.
 - d) Construction of lift irrigation project.
 - e) Installation of sprinkler irrigation system.
 - f) Purchase generator sets for energisation of pump sets used for agricultural purposes.
 - ii) **Reclamation and Land Development Schemes**
 Bunding of firm leveling of land, terracing conversion of dry paddy into wet irrigable paddy land, wasteland development, development of firm drainage, reclamation of soil lands and prevention of salinisation reclamation of ravine lands, purchase bulldozers, etc.
 - iii) **Construction of farm building and structures, etc.**
 Bullock sheds, implement sheds, tractor and truck sheds, farm stores, etc.

iv) Construction and running of storage facilities

Construction and running of warehouses, Godowns, silos and loans granted to farmer for establishing cold storage used for storing own produce.

v) Production and processing of hybrid seeds for crops

vi) Payment of irrigation charges, etc.

Charges for hired water from wells and tube wells, canal water charges, maintenance and upkeep of oil engines and electric motors, payment of labour charges, electricity charges, marketing charges, service charges to Customs service Units, payment of development cess, etc.

3) Other types of direct finance to farmers

a) Short-term loans

i. To tradition/ non-traditional plantations and horticulture.

b) Medium and long term loans

i. Development loans to all plantations, horticulture, forestry and wasteland.

ANNEXURE – E
BASE DATA

Number of memberships in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	528	523	522	519	519	519	519
2	Coimbatore	998	1038	1042	1061	1076	1065	1055
3	Cuddalore	561	563	564	565	564	565	565
4	Dharmapuri	547	558	571	579	582	584	584
5	Dindigul	616	617	618	618	618	618	618
6	Erode	1374	1341	1359	1358	1357	1357	1241
7	Kancheepuram	770	773	777	777	782	774	769
8	Kanyakumari	520	522	519	516	516	516	515
9	Kumbakonam	579	580	582	587	591	591	591
10	Madurai	973	987	906	915	924	928	930
11	Nilgiris	295	295	296	298	298	300	299
12	Pudukkottai	255	255	255	255	252	248	248
13	Ramanathapuram	439	440	448	448	448	448	452
14	Salem	1952	1971	1959	1966	1967	1971	1968
15	Sivagangai	360	366	366	366	366	359	360
16	Thanjavur	490	491	492	494	493	494	495
17	Thiruchirapalli	976	982	986	1002	988	998	996
18	Tirunelveli	835	841	847	853	854	856	857
19	Tiruvannamalai	518	520	520	524	534	535	802
20	Thoothukudi	579	580	580	580	580	580	578
21	Vellore	637	669	670	670	670	644	619
22	Villupuram	701	704	710	714	707	714	718
23	Virudhunagar	535	527	515	511	499	496	496
	Total	16038	16143	16104	16176	16185	16160	16275

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Number of Branches in DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	61	61	61	61	62	63	63
2	Coimbatore	23	23	24	24	25	25	27
3	Cuddalore	24	25	25	25	25	24	24
4	Dharmapuri	37	37	37	39	40	40	40
5	Dindigul	25	27	29	29	29	29	29
6	Erode	32	32	31	31	29	29	29
7	Kancheepuram	43	43	45	45	45	46	45
8	Kanyakumari	14	14	15	16	17	16	17
9	Kumbakonam	33	33	33	33	33	32	33
10	Madurai	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
11	Nilgiris	16	16	17	17	16	11	11
12	Pudukkottai	20	21	21	21	21	21	20
13	Ramanathapuram	25	26	26	25	26	26	26
14	Salem	60	61	61	63	63	59	59
15	Sivagangai	28	29	29	29	29	28	28
16	Thanjavur	21	21	21	21	21	21	21
17	Thiruchirapalli	50	51	53	53	58	57	57
18	Tirunelveli	25	26	27	27	27	26	27
19	Tiruvannamalai	27	27	27	27	27	26	24
20	Thoothukudi	15	15	15	17	17	17	17
21	Vellore	35	35	35	35	35	34	34
22	Villupuram	21	21	21	21	21	21	20
23	Virudhunagar	32	32	33	33	33	30	30
	Total	708	717	727	733	740	722	722

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Share capital of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	38.75	46.00	58.63	78.25	87.64	96.78	96.37
2	Coimbatore	12.87	14.76	14.88	19.26	21.38	21.95	18.84
3	Cuddalore	8.32	9.11	9.47	11.16	13.40	15.13	17.05
4	Dharmapuri	17.92	21.40	21.09	22.58	30.49	32.26	32.87
5	Dindigul	7.67	8.71	9.20	10.53	11.20	12.06	13.22
6	Erode	10.69	11.53	12.40	13.55	14.16	14.78	16.87
7	Kancheepuram	12.02	17.67	17.54	21.15	22.55	26.60	27.87
8	Kanyakumari	6.99	8.32	8.58	9.31	9.93	10.88	11.29
9	Kumbakonam	11.75	12.20	12.65	13.26	14.13	14.78	16.29
10	Madurai	11.30	13.38	13.84	15.61	16.17	16.65	16.83
11	Nilgiris	3.72	4.20	5.18	5.77	5.97	6.35	6.52
12	Pudukkottai	7.46	8.11	8.15	8.72	9.43	10.08	10.68
13	Ramanathapuram	6.39	6.64	7.06	6.91	7.84	7.90	8.55
14	Salem	14.76	16.06	15.75	16.44	18.73	20.14	23.64
15	Sivagangai	6.77	8.20	8.52	10.42	11.19	11.53	12.01
16	Thanjavur	9.96	11.33	11.89	12.78	13.57	13.96	15.88
17	Thiruchirapalli	11.70	12.88	13.48	14.59	16.27	17.85	21.15
18	Tirunelveli	6.33	6.70	7.39	7.77	9.06	9.18	9.22
19	Tiruvannamalai	12.48	12.15	15.91	16.40	16.95	17.99	21.19
20	Thoothukudi	6.13	6.48	6.42	6.73	7.00	6.89	6.90
21	Vellore	7.80	9.38	9.00	10.76	11.63	12.95	15.08
22	Villupuram	11.06	12.35	12.73	15.23	16.43	18.47	21.73
23	Virudhunagar	7.10	7.39	7.56	7.87	8.30	8.94	9.29
	Total	249.94	284.95	307.32	355.05	393.42	424.10	449.34

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Reserves of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	103.67	123.72	141.08	145.14	186.06	222.87	238.42
2	Coimbatore	19.10	24.28	24.29	38.69	42.41	6.41	58.84
3	Cuddalore	10.95	11.71	12.33	19.83	25.01	3.13	29.86
4	Dharmapuri	10.33	16.10	19.29	27.71	47.45	72.20	72.04
5	Dindigul	14.82	13.18	13.66	24.48	32.38	66.44	70.81
6	Erode	10.40	11.06	11.76	17.81	23.30	31.00	35.10
7	Kancheepuram	20.19	34.55	34.03	59.15	73.24	73.08	93.12
8	Kanyakumari	8.48	8.61	12.27	13.00	13.54	18.56	18.31
9	Kumbakonam	21.36	24.44	20.69	35.93	51.54	75.59	40.72
10	Madurai	20.53	32.60	32.57	59.99	75.21	101.74	76.13
11	Nilgiris	4.97	6.25	10.28	8.30	8.30	21.49	16.08
12	Pudukkottai	7.10	8.89	8.87	14.10	18.17	24.65	24.73
13	Ramanathapuram	18.28	18.13	18.13	31.87	48.39	48.70	48.48
14	Salem	27.60	29.78	32.20	42.50	48.52	68.30	89.72
15	Sivagangai	12.14	17.02	15.44	34.77	40.50	56.33	35.05
16	Thanjavur	15.67	11.53	12.05	20.26	44.26	4.62	35.70
17	Thiruchirapalli	25.24	44.04	55.76	61.69	80.44	77.61	112.10
18	Tirunelveli	6.29	6.73	8.45	9.28	45.31	51.77	35.40
19	Tiruvannamalai	19.51	19.26	17.77	25.77	35.48	40.37	51.67
20	Thoothukudi	11.01	11.01	12.77	35.76	53.13	1.37	62.06
21	Vellore	7.36	10.03	11.36	17.14	22.34	22.34	27.34
22	Villupuram	22.16	26.35	27.27	38.22	42.34	58.98	60.95
23	Virudhunagar	7.73	11.33	11.89	20.37	22.90	34.75	24.17
	Total	424.89	520.60	564.21	801.76	1080.22	1182.30	1356.80

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Deposits of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	585.10	777.90	890.55	942.41	1070.18	1121.50	1116.26
2	Coimbatore	277.56	336.82	332.88	352.05	367.90	350.84	359.31
3	Cuddalore	211.62	244.50	264.25	312.46	324.97	338.71	349.29
4	Dharmapuri	175.12	237.77	246.04	247.42	267.15	259.12	259.84
5	Dindigul	176.94	201.47	218.75	226.46	248.82	245.31	238.83
6	Erode	251.16	293.55	301.86	320.27	333.58	315.47	327.50
7	Kancheepuram	261.07	291.33	323.17	342.45	357.80	358.06	323.58
8	Kanyakumari	81.79	126.85	92.92	133.23	160.36	158.49	166.83
9	Kumbakonam	196.03	231.07	250.61	269.96	282.68	256.03	245.83
10	Madurai	315.19	388.20	427.79	445.46	432.52	376.31	336.10
11	Nilgiris	80.25	94.81	100.02	106.67	103.95	91.70	92.66
12	Pudukkottai	109.39	122.10	142.29	156.83	169.88	168.16	163.46
13	Ramanathapuram	119.21	146.71	152.58	160.17	178.94	175.03	176.69
14	Salem	597.67	726.85	764.71	832.37	879.05	808.52	786.28
15	Sivagangai	101.16	143.93	146.62	152.71	176.33	155.32	146.87
16	Thanjavur	111.67	130.29	144.92	145.26	144.10	143.62	145.13
17	Thiruchirapalli	337.60	379.65	403.77	445.95	461.83	466.94	454.57
18	Tirunelveli	155.76	209.73	195.81	199.06	205.13	178.41	164.79
19	Tiruvannamalai	102.59	136.40	147.16	160.00	182.58	181.09	191.43
20	Thoothukudi	110.81	136.39	131.54	138.32	152.09	121.61	123.56
21	Vellore	203.04	250.53	264.53	275.74	290.11	290.65	283.42
22	Villupuram	152.03	216.08	240.09	264.89	290.27	307.83	317.42
23	Virudhunagar	171.41	199.23	209.76	220.08	240.62	233.57	219.73
	Total	4884.17	6022.16	6392.62	6850.22	7320.84	7102.29	6989.38

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Borrowings of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	11.63	00.43	00.23	00.97	34.10	15.60	34.68
2	Coimbatore	25.33	29.21	58.15	50.08	50.16	68.57	121.61
3	Cuddalore	28.57	17.07	20.20	41.89	50.25	61.10	85.84
4	Dharmapuri	179.40	243.23	333.12	340.79	268.48	247.83	283.13
5	Dindigul	23.45	19.09	27.61	34.93	54.47	77.15	99.38
6	Erode	56.85	49.11	65.02	85.19	48.52	85.92	73.59
7	Kancheepuram	59.42	46.84	69.61	80.57	39.09	52.13	58.00
8	Kanyakumari	59.46	21.44	52.37	47.17	42.13	88.67	86.91
9	Kumbakonam	89.35	62.34	68.75	79.48	101.86	114.62	134.59
10	Madurai	68.47	24.30	36.01	35.46	45.30	106.09	154.14
11	Nilgiris	12.98	16.11	18.06	22.80	28.07	36.90	46.48
12	Pudukkottai	39.06	37.46	38.74	51.03	58.42	80.57	89.90
13	Ramanathapuram	19.59	18.01	22.51	31.87	14.13	44.07	61.96
14	Salem	51.56	73.37	116.62	73.17	83.47	188.12	177.09
15	Sivagangai	46.01	35.91	44.80	59.43	69.05	91.54	104.63
16	Thanjavur	74.26	71.45	67.26	91.73	114.18	114.71	131.63
17	Thiruchirapalli	22.02	23.52	30.00	53.51	47.54	81.14	107.75
18	Tirunelveli	13.67	7.38	13.99	24.36	30.10	58.95	72.11
19	Tiruvannamalai	72.96	70.31	86.22	84.90	91.16	109.88	108.34
20	Thoothukudi	9.26	3.46	5.38	11.63	11.99	24.65	14.69
21	Vellore	41.58	21.07	53.35	118.95	97.58	95.04	127.68
22	Villupuram	88.47	86.32	60.04	65.71	104.51	135.23	158.15
23	Virudhunagar	19.52	22.49	26.26	25.84	24.30	31.88	44.38
	Total	1112.87	999.92	1314.30	1511.46	1508.86	2010.36	2376.66

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Loans and advances of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	404.64	432.47	563.96	738.58	817.08	899.74	910.95
2	Coimbatore	179.21	223.99	268.62	304.29	326.67	336.65	367.89
3	Cuddalore	160.43	191.32	202.85	237.99	292.54	325.75	350.40
4	Dharmapuri	328.72	443.38	550.81	549.19	491.71	487.31	551.66
5	Dindigul	161.67	174.20	209.14	238.45	263.19	290.80	315.53
6	Erode	173.87	187.69	218.58	244.72	254.61	271.39	298.86
7	Kancheepuram	256.90	289.55	308.57	350.20	364.67	397.39	383.44
8	Kanyakumari	125.71	126.38	142.59	157.79	180.69	219.75	234.73
9	Kumbakonam	241.54	240.74	250.79	267.62	306.37	296.21	324.97
10	Madurai	322.86	344.10	381.13	396.63	410.86	446.12	484.71
11	Nilgiris	56.71	73.63	92.43	97.25	105.93	106.51	114.80
12	Pudukkottai	128.91	138.46	154.10	180.59	202.98	232.56	243.03
13	Ramanathapuram	120.70	132.38	147.72	157.40	168.97	188.54	225.69
14	Salem	321.59	366.09	433.65	445.89	536.79	586.43	640.31
15	Sivagangai	134.33	147.10	164.94	178.94	208.96	213.79	222.30
16	Thanjavur	154.23	164.86	173.22	180.92	215.13	219.69	245.66
17	Thiruchirapalli	263.55	302.97	385.07	421.11	459.14	520.64	572.94
18	Tirunelveli	109.68	107.78	130.55	150.26	169.50	175.48	169.25
19	Tiruvannamalai	174.03	199.83	225.97	233.73	257.96	288.29	317.44
20	Thoothukudi	88.44	91.58	105.79	116.32	138.58	131.99	130.38
21	Vellore	167.16	211.33	262.64	315.03	352.33	374.62	373.02
22	Villupuram	262.21	294.33	279.29	315.01	362.56	416.33	452.63
23	Virudhunagar	123.42	124.66	133.12	152.03	169.55	196.87	202.83
	Total	4460.51	5008.82	5785.53	6429.94	7056.77	7622.85	8133.42

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Investments of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	333.23	513.34	514.16	445.89	573.07	565.56	596.01
2	Coimbatore	146.80	179.90	173.41	162.75	141.52	139.40	183.97
3	Cuddalore	60.43	87.27	106.23	140.75	50.00	117.08	139.78
4	Dharmapuri	42.72	66.06	75.49	77.30	83.80	83.90	86.63
5	Dindigul	59.53	78.99	76.02	67.23	75.53	71.73	69.76
6	Erode	149.44	185.14	185.29	209.10	180.98	186.63	168.20
7	Kancheepuram	99.90	96.28	150.02	144.87	134.99	130.88	146.72
8	Kanyakumari	20.37	32.16	35.03	35.03	41.23	44.62	43.22
9	Kumbakonam	56.58	64.47	78.91	79.47	79.13	72.80	73.84
10	Madurai	94.50	108.58	136.04	135.40	128.34	116.01	107.65
11	Nilgiris	7.33	37.60	28.91	29.95	29.95	23.49	28.22
12	Pudukkottai	28.07	32.28	44.24	42.33	46.79	45.35	43.82
13	Ramanathapuram	28.31	44.24	42.57	43.42	46.01	46.46	47.10
14	Salem	290.98	516.91	546.37	560.37	525.99	497.73	436.40
15	Sivagangai	29.94	42.04	40.54	41.58	49.62	45.10	41.24
16	Thanjavur	31.88	39.18	40.78	42.83	45.90	40.92	41.96
17	Thiruchirapalli	139.12	162.58	118.84	162.58	152.40	134.07	131.05
18	Tirunelveli	48.13	95.37	71.72	52.96	53.77	43.11	45.81
19	Tiruvannamalai	25.85	41.28	44.32	51.83	57.12	53.12	60.82
20	Thoothukudi	41.08	65.35	50.47	42.65	45.33	34.17	35.70
21	Vellore	87.00	82.31	86.88	104.11	96.35	88.64	88.84
22	Villupuram	39.81	59.45	87.14	87.49	96.30	34.09	119.92
23	Virudhunagar	64.34	101.69	109.45	96.16	101.72	70.82	64.37
	Total	1925.34	2732.47	2842.83	2856.05	2835.84	2685.68	2801.03

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Working Capital of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	800.58	1019.51	1160.87	1273.75	1491.47	1568.03	1594.14
2	Coimbatore	317.07	432.76	437.97	460.08	481.84	443.65	507.53
3	Cuddalore	279.57	310.69	337.51	415.99	440.30	438.63	529.30
4	Dharmapuri	372.43	502.41	599.93	610.79	566.17	588.26	575.91
5	Dindigul	248.87	278.78	316.92	337.59	385.77	438.57	432.31
6	Erode	361.12	405.00	434.46	479.85	465.34	489.35	502.19
7	Kancheepuram	386.59	422.22	496.34	544.11	541.72	571.48	569.30
8	Kanyakumari	167.79	176.28	200.71	221.35	247.55	296.64	310.82
9	Kumbakonam	335.56	399.64	387.67	421.64	473.49	481.76	481.36
10	Madurai	457.58	510.60	480.04	613.41	634.00	646.77	645.41
11	Nilgiris	99.80	121.37	145.02	156.02	146.29	165.22	172.67
12	Pudukkottai	173.45	192.47	219.80	251.37	277.94	307.06	311.76
13	Ramanathapuram	162.96	189.49	243.20	230.49	249.30	328.53	327.66
14	Salem	665.73	818.66	900.44	926.00	986.13	1014.07	1149.17
15	Sivagangai	219.32	262.99	253.10	257.31	316.18	295.15	301.74
16	Thanjavur	221.77	241.12	264.94	249.77	271.86	416.29	363.84
17	Thiruchirapalli	443.57	513.56	558.61	637.73	687.65	722.29	772.48
18	Tirunelveli	205.79	260.66	312.29	270.17	278.59	318.61	316.90
19	Tiruvannamalai	227.85	238.12	303.04	341.65	363.53	349.33	412.18
20	Thoothukudi	153.15	178.61	187.62	156.67	244.17	234.38	222.73
21	Vellore	255.35	324.65	378.90	422.59	496.79	459.74	499.11
22	Villupuram	328.68	373.01	394.91	438.59	511.78	567.78	569.57
23	Virudhunagar	227.23	231.01	286.06	302.53	328.70	331.16	314.38
	Total	7111.81	8403.61	9300.35	10019.45	10886.56	11472.75	11882.46

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Net Profit of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	+27.05	+28.31	+32.86	+46.90	+55.55	+47.05	+50.21
2	Coimbatore	-2.81	-0.11	+0.47	+6.45	+2.03	+1.56	+3.13
3	Cuddalore	+0.34	-1.79	+0.27	-2.56	+2.43	+1.01	+3.10
4	Dharmapuri	+0.18	+0.18	-4.63	-30.91	-16.59	-83.22	+64.97
5	Dindigul	+0.05	+0.08	-4.88	+2.36	+0.02	-26.32	+18.30
6	Erode	+0.65	+0.65	+0.78	+1.68	+2.02	+2.12	+2.77
7	Kancheepuram	+0.52	+0.79	+0.86	+1.78	+0.67	+0.47	+1.95
8	Kanyakumari	+0.30	+0.69	-1.52	+0.55	+0.93	+1.11	5.08
9	Kumbakonam	-3.37	-3.15	-3.60	+0.06	-30.86	-18.29	+27.78
10	Madurai	+0.33	-9.33	-5.69	+2.97	+0.63	-4.72	+0.67
11	Nilgiris	+0.07	+0.09	-1.99	+1.62	-1.63	+3.39	+7.83
12	Pudukkottai	-0.04	-0.14	-1.14	-0.23	+5.42	+1.26	+4.26
13	Ramanathapuram	+0.95	+1.31	+0.91	-7.81	-38.27	-33.74	+20.39
14	Salem	+3.07	+3.36	+3.49	+4.28	+4.35	+4.44	+5.04
15	Sivagangai	-0.72	-9.07	-7.41	-3.70	-2.71	-13.84	+28.13
16	Thanjavur	-2.67	-3.07	-12.30	+4.21	-26.85	+3.12	+37.65
17	Thiruchirapalli	+0.02	-8.31	+8.41	+0.28	-1.54	+17.47	+8.13
18	Tirunelveli	-0.44	+0.04	-11.43	-2.98	+15.44	-39.76	+9.53
19	Tiruvannamalai	-1.81	-3.43	-0.35	+1.00	+0.09	+8.91	+9.01
20	Thoothukudi	+0.08	-0.23	-9.49	-7.91	-9.87	-31.00	+15.06
21	Vellore	+0.38	-2.28	+1.05	+3.74	-2.94	+5.40	+5.49
22	Villupuram	+0.94	+2.03	+3.92	+4.75	+3.38	+1.85	+2.28
23	Virudhunagar	+0.47	-9.02	-4.44	-10.42	-1.11	-4.97	+19.08
	Total	+23.54	-12.40	-15.85	+16.11	-39.41	-156.70	+349.84

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Overdues of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in crores)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	16.89	10.38	11.53	9.80	12.97	16.66	13.79
2	Coimbatore	26.92	31.46	39.39	50.27	75.83	119.00	39.12
3	Cuddalore	15.79	16.75	22.92	13.83	34.43	65.07	20.56
4	Dharmapuri	2.76	3.67	47.78	98.25	237.46	272.83	37.42
5	Dindigul	30.03	28.43	36.32	31.25	44.56	75.26	36.61
6	Erode	8.98	8.89	12.29	18.74	100.04	48.12	31.48
7	Kancheepuram	39.26	37.80	52.13	49.66	71.07	79.11	66.89
8	Kanyakumari	7.99	7.01	7.41	7.96	13.26	14.62	18.02
9	Kumbakonam	54.30	50.42	55.02	44.89	86.84	105.17	33.45
10	Madurai	45.27	45.91	42.62	39.72	69.52	76.05	50.19
11	Nilgiris	14.69	16.89	20.67	17.79	30.77	34.07	19.64
12	Pudukkottai	30.28	36.08	40.76	40.66	73.55	74.79	22.64
13	Ramanathapuram	28.95	32.78	37.90	36.13	39.04	41.66	60.38
14	Salem	15.67	14.70	23.77	29.21	56.20	67.11	46.53
15	Sivagangai	30.48	29.30	37.51	61.38	53.20	41.08	16.35
16	Thanjavur	50.96	63.88	73.44	48.57	73.61	87.56	33.57
17	Thiruchirapalli	16.74	17.69	28.47	27.70	60.76	55.41	45.40
18	Tirunelveli	14.50	12.98	15.31	13.04	14.26	18.73	13.22
19	Tiruvannamalai	37.45	40.72	61.88	42.15	61.90	46.55	52.82
20	Thoothukudi	10.56	10.22	12.87	12.87	17.71	16.71	9.48
21	Vellore	15.34	14.68	16.02	18.25	77.82	104.27	43.65
22	Villupuram	29.27	27.53	31.48	32.41	53.09	44.64	40.95
23	Virudhunagar	16.77	19.09	16.01	16.89	19.72	23.11	10.03
	Total	559.85	577.26	743.50	761.42	1377.61	1527.58	762.19

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Recovery of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in lakhs)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	15341	17121	17599	10767	10193	62708	85196
2	Coimbatore	9278	8585	10765	12473	8775	11975	16453
3	Cuddalore	9603	12978	11123	16914	17287	20230	25774
4	Dharmapuri	10099	13463	14010	16844	6072	7016	39926
5	Dindigul	6792	8272	8637	10777	10071	12381	17601
6	Erode	9212	10792	13093	19241	15566	23399	24546
7	Kancheepuram	9310	10964	10174	15377	15817	17590	20572
8	Kanyakumari	3369	6805	11219	14697	13468	15845	17712
9	Kumbakonam	6097	7729	8828	8922	17274	8885	15718
10	Madurai	8466	8964	6798	7958	8071	15139	17967
11	Nilgiris	2069	2169	2722	3789	3677	4456	7077
12	Pudukkottai	5767	6591	7451	9539	20997	20776	26203
13	Ramanathapuram	3737	3717	3136	3870	7851	9172	16419
14	Salem	13186	14276	12638	18705	19629	25286	24003
15	Sivagangai	3437	3190	3942	9243	22565	15844	13124
16	Thanjavur	2968	2582	1525	5158	3201	3876	9518
17	Thiruchirapalli	14452	17184	17693	17934	20854	20816	33575
18	Tirunelveli	4137	4673	4227	6162	7126	6900	7499
19	Tiruvannamalai	5964	6918	6407	7229	5470	10735	12794
20	Thoothukudi	3090	3781	3115	5194	4490	5624	6546
21	Vellore	6620	6710	7544	12273	8312	10243	21325
22	Villupuram	8835	7798	8611	11006	12153	16417	19851
23	Virudhunagar	4058	4574	4441	6322	7232	7696	9354
	Total	165887	189836	195698	250394	266151	353009	488753

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Legal Expenses of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in lakhs)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	0.75	1.06	1.63	2.25	2.01	1.80	1.86
2	Coimbatore	0.34	0.93	0.86	0.90	1.99	1.40	2.20
3	Cuddalore	0.49	0.84	0.50	1.07	0.67	1.94	1.42
4	Dharmapuri	0.68	0.53	0.37	0.20	0.81	1.60	1.03
5	Dindigul	0.99	0.90	1.08	0.32	0.54	0.43	0.13
6	Erode	0.32	0.13	0.33	0.19	0.27	0.50	0.48
7	Kancheepuram	0.94	0.73	0.59	0.49	1.12	1.14	0.37
8	Kanyakumari	0.90	0.70	1.20	0.94	1.42	0.32	0.52
9	Kumbakonam	0.53	0.51	0.70	0.61	0.87	0.52	0.60
10	Madurai	0.72	2.16	0.76	1.94	1.10	1.43	0.72
11	Nilgiris	0.36	1.27	0.33	1.16	0.32	0.88	1.87
12	Pudukkottai	0.24	0.18	0.18	0.34	0.59	0.74	1.04
13	Ramanathapuram	0.71	0.86	0.30	0.29	1.05	1.25	1.39
14	Salem	-	-	0.19	1.20	0.62	1.11	1.02
15	Sivagangai	2.78	0.60	0.82	0.33	0.22	1.08	1.16
16	Thanjavur	0.57	0.62	0.94	0.38	1.89	0.59	0.91
17	Thiruchirapalli	0.48	1.02	0.70	0.30	0.50	0.69	0.78
18	Tirunelveli	0.69	1.71	1.04	0.76	1.76	1.77	1.31
19	Tiruvannamalai	0.07	0.21	0.32	0.54	0.37	1.06	0.72
20	Thoothukudi	0.13	0.11	0.34	0.29	0.31	0.74	0.90
21	Vellore	0.33	0.31	0.48	0.48	0.85	0.64	1.61
22	Villupuram	0.36	0.60	0.90	1.06	0.09	0.71	0.98
23	Virudhunagar	0.17	0.50	0.26	0.47	0.79	1.12	0.38
	Total	13.55	16.48	14.82	16.51	20.16	23.46	23.40

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.

Spread of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu

(Rs. in lakhs)

Sl. No	Name of the DCCB	1998 – 99	1999 – 2000	2000 – 01	2001 – 02	2002 – 03	2003 – 04	2004 - 05
1	Chennai	4294	4292	5058	6644	6857	7409	7234
2	Coimbatore	546	1293	1531	1880	2114	2283	2382
3	Cuddalore	677	493	895	1036	1463	1773	1776
4	Dharmapuri	1031	790	977	1032	1783	1250	17
5	Dindigul	547	492	602	945	1255	1570	1836
6	Erode	612	755	782	1304	1669	1971	1844
7	Kancheepuram	1343	1659	1950	2319	2664	3251	3660
8	Kanyakumari	385	355	564	556	440	1072	994
9	Kumbakonam	630	665	795	957	873	1084	1231
10	Madurai	1313	1213	1367	1685	2095	2806	2816
11	Nilgiris	408	-76	512	98	178	-175	88
12	Pudukkottai	362	-200	492	586	627	1094	1043
13	Ramanathapuram	568	689	646	845	501	1075	1589
14	Salem	1854	1913	2000	2456	2856	3957	3865
15	Sivagangai	490	339	438	370	650	856	878
16	Thanjavur	91	316	279	279	548	924	1094
17	Thiruchirapalli	1255	1653	2267	2633	3258	3670	3901
18	Tirunelveli	435	371	380	455	531	558	363
19	Tiruvannamalai	530	516	723	983	1333	1386	1683
20	Thoothukudi	-134	-356	-513	-369	275	410	582
21	Vellore	762	722	1070	1639	1462	1809	1962
22	Villupuram	1067	1654	1220	1552	1485	1821	2634
23	Virudhunagar	533	331	374	638	897	1235	1129
	Total	19599	19879	24409	30523	35814	43089	44601

Source: Annual Reports of TNSC Bank Ltd. at Chennai, 1998-99 to 2004-05.